

Supporting Information

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Appendix S1. Literature on sea turtle movements and connectivity.

The literature review gathered references for all seven sea turtle species through Scopus, Web of Science, and the Animal Biotelemetry Journal website on March 10, 2017, using the text string: “(<Genus species>) and (telemetry or tag* or isotop* or genetic* or mark or recapture) and (migrat* or connect* or move* or feed* or forag* or breed* or dispers* or nest* or aggregat* or ground* or site* or corridor or route* or track* or winter* or habitat*).” The “<Genus species>” text string was replaced by “*Caretta caretta*”, “*Chelonia mydas*”, “*Dermochelys coriacea*”, “*Eretmochelys imbricata*”, “*Lepidochelys kempii*”, “*Lepidochelys olivacea*”, and “*Natator depressus*” for loggerhead, green, leatherback, hawksbill, Kemp’s ridley, olive ridley, and flatback sea turtles, respectively. The Web of Science Core Collection and all other subscribed databases (BIOSIS Citation Index, Current Contents Connect, Data citation Index, Derwent Innovations Index, KCI-Korean Journal Database, MEDLINE, Russian Science Citation Index, SciELO Citation Index, and Zoological Record) were included in the Web of Science search. References were restricted to those published entirely in English and after 1989, a period where Thums et al. (2018) have shown there was a general increase in publishing research on animal movement using tracking technology.

The literature search returned 1,477 unique references, with 883 (about 60%) of papers containing relevant data on sea turtle area use, movements, and migratory connectivity. Relevant references were defined as publications 1) collecting primary data, 2) using specific analytical methods (from either observations, telemetry, capture-mark-recapture, stable isotopes, or genetic sampling), and 3) describing an important activity or purpose in one or more locations or sites. Similar to the tracking data contributed to the current study, more references were available for green (33%) and loggerhead (30%), with the least amount on Kemp’s ridley (4%) and flatback (1%) turtles (Figure S1.1).

The search was repeated on February 25, 2021, restricted to references published between 2017-2021, to determine the total number of references from the literature review that overlapped with references attributed to the telemetry datasets used in this study. Eight references identified by the updated literature review search matched with references that were attributed to the telemetry

data for this study. In total, 129 unique references were attributed to telemetry data used in this study, 77 (60%) of which were not found from the literature search.

Reference cited:

Thums, M., Fernández-Gracia, J., Sequeira, A. M. M., Eguíluz, V. M., Duarte, C. M., & Meekan, M. G. (2018). How big data fast tracked human mobility research and the lessons for animal movement ecology. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, 5(21), 1-21. doi:10.3389/fmars.2018.00021

Figure S1.1. Summary of relevant references from the first literature search only, by species and method (total n = 883). Cc = *Caretta caretta* (n = 308); Cm = *Chelonia mydas* (n = 339); Dc = *Dermochelys coriacea* (n = 117); Ei = *Eretmochelys imbricata* (n = 154); Lk = *Lepidochelys kempii* (n = 38); Lo = *Lepidochelys olivacea* (n = 52); Nd = *Natator depressus* (n = 11). The sum of references per species was greater than the total because some references included data on more than one species.

Table S1.2. Summary of the relevant references, by source, species, and method (Lit = literature review search; Cc = *Caretta caretta*, Cm = *Chelonia mydas*, Dc = *Dermochelys coriacea*, Ei = *Eretmochelys imbricata*, Lk = *Lepidochelys kempii*, Lo = *Lepidochelys olivacea*, Nd = *Natator depressus*; T = telemetry (from direct contributions or literature review), Td = telemetry data directly contributed and used in this study, Tlit = telemetry data identified by literature review, C = capture-mark-recapture, G = genetic, I = stable isotope, O = observation), where x = relevant information present or contributed, blank = no information). For full citation, refer to CiteID in Table S1.3.

CiteID	Lit	Species							Methods							
		Cc	Cm	Dc	Ei	Lk	Lo	Nd	T	Tdata	Tlit	C	G	I	O	
1	x				x									x		
2	x	x								x	x					
3	x	x								x		x				
4	x	x	x									x				
5	x		x		x					x		x				
6	x	x										x				
7	x		x							x		x				
8	x		x											x		
9	x		x									x				
10	x		x											x		
11	x	x													x	
12	x				x							x				
13	x	x										x				
14	x			x						x	x					
15	x		x											x		
16	x	x												x		
17	x			x										x		
18	x	x								x		x				
19	x				x		x			x	x					
20	x				x					x	x					
21	x		x							x	x					
22	x		x											x		
23	x		x									x		x		
24	x		x											x		
25	x		x											x		
26	x	x	x	x								x				
27	x		x									x				
28	x	x														x
29	x	x								x		x				
30	x	x								x		x				
31	x	x								x		x		x		
32	x		x		x								x			
33	x		x												x	
34	x	x	x				x								x	
35	x		x									x				
36	x		x							x		x				
37	x	x								x		x	x			
38	x	x													x	
39	x		x									x				
40	x	x	x	x	x							x				
41	x	x	x		x		x					x				
42	x		x											x		
43	x			x						x		x				
44	x			x						x		x				
45	x		x							x		x				
46	x		x										x			
47	x		x							x		x				
48	x		x										x			
49	x	x								x		x				
50	x	x					x			x	x					

CiteID	Lit	Species							Methods							
		<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	<i>Nd</i>	T	Tdata	Tlit	C	G	I	O	
51	x					x			x	x						
52	x						x				x					
53	x				x							x				
54	x	x											x			
55	x		x											x		
56	x				x										x	
57	x		x												x	
58	x		x												x	
59	x	x	x	x	x		x									x
60	x		x						x		x					
61	x						x		x		x					
62	x	x	x		x				x		x					
63	x				x							x				
64	x	x	x													x
65	x		x									x				
66	x				x							x				
67	x				x							x				
68	x				x							x				
69	x				x				x		x					
70	x				x							x				
71	x			x					x		x					
72	x			x					x		x					
73	x			x					x		x					
74	x			x					x		x	x				
75	x	x							x		x					
76	x	x							x		x					
77	x		x												x	
78	x				x				x		x					
79	x						x									x
80	x		x									x				
81	x		x										x			
82	x		x		x							x				
83	x		x									x				
84	x		x									x				
85	x		x									x				
86	x				x							x				
87	x		x									x				
88	x	x										x				
89	x		x											x		
90	x		x											x		
91	x				x							x				
92	x		x						x		x					
93	x		x						x		x					
94	x	x														x
95	x		x						x	x						
96	x				x									x		
97	x				x							x				
98	x				x				x		x					
99	x		x									x				
100	x	x	x						x	x						
101	x	x	x											x		
102	x		x											x		
103	x	x												x		
104	x	x										x				
105	x	x										x				
106	x	x										x				

CiteID	Lit	Species							Methods						
		<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	<i>Nd</i>	T	Tdata	Tlit	C	G	I	O
107	x				x							x			
108	x			x								x			
109	x		x												x
110	x		x										x		
111	x		x						x		x		x		
112	x	x											x		
113	x		x										x		
114	x	x											x		
115	x	x	x		x								x		
116	x	x			x								x		
117	x	x											x		
118	x				x								x		
119	x	x											x		
120	x					x	x						x		
121	x				x								x		
122	x	x	x										x		
123	x		x										x		
124	x	x											x		
125	x		x						x	x					x
126	x		x						x		x	x			
127	x	x										x			
128	x	x							x		x				
129	x	x										x			
130	x	x	x						x	x					
131	x	x	x									x			
132	x	x	x									x			
133	x				x								x		
134	x		x						x		x				
135	x				x								x		
136	x		x									x			
137	x			x					x		x				
138	x					x									x
139	x					x						x			
140	x					x						x			
141	x	x													x
142	x		x									x			
143	x	x											x		
144	x		x											x	
145	x	x												x	
146	x		x											x	
147	x	x												x	
148	x	x							x		x				
149	x	x							x		x				
150	x	x							x		x				
151	x		x	x	x								x		
152	x					x							x		
153	x	x											x		
154	x	x											x		
155	x	x											x		
156	x	x											x		
157	x				x							x			
158	x	x							x	x					
159	x	x							x	x					
160	x	x													x
161	x	x										x			
162	x	x							x	x					

CiteID	Lit	Species							Methods							
		<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	<i>Nd</i>	T	Tdata	Tlit	C	G	I	O	
163	x	x							x		x	x				
164	x	x														x
165	x	x												x		
166	x	x										x				
167	x	x												x		
168	x	x										x				
169	x	x							x	x						
170	x	x										x				
171	x			x					x		x					
172	x			x											x	
173	x				x									x		
174	x	x							x		x				x	
175	x	x							x		x				x	
176	x	x							x		x				x	
177	x			x								x				
178	x			x								x				
179	x	x												x		
180	x	x												x		
181	x	x	x									x				
182	x		x									x				
183	x				x							x				
184	x	x										x				
185	x						x		x		x					
186	x		x						x		x					
187	x						x		x		x	x				
188	x		x						x		x					
189	x		x		x							x				
190	x				x							x				
191	x		x											x		
192	x			x								x				
193	x		x						x		x					
194	x		x						x		x					
195	x		x									x				
196	x		x						x		x					
197	x		x									x		x		
198	x		x									x				
199	x		x						x		x					
200	x	x												x		
201	x	x												x	x	
202	x	x												x		
203	x		x									x				
204	x						x		x		x					
205	x						x					x				
206	x		x									x				
207	x		x									x				
208	x		x						x		x					
209	x		x									x				
210	x			x										x		
211	x				x				x		x					
212	x						x		x	x						
213	x		x											x		
214	x						x		x	x		x				
215	x				x									x		
216	x	x														x
217	x			x					x		x					
218	x		x									x				

CiteID	Lit	Species							Methods						
		<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	<i>Nd</i>	T	Tdata	Tlit	C	G	I	O
219	x		x										x		
220	x		x										x		
221	x		x										x		
222	x		x											x	
223	x				x								x		
224	x				x								x		
225	x				x							x			
226	x				x							x			
227	x				x							x			
228	x			x					x	x					
229	x			x					x	x					
230	x			x										x	
231	x						x					x			
232	x		x									x			
233	x			x					x		x				
234	x	x		x	x	x	x	x					x		
235	x				x							x			
236	x						x						x		
237	x			x											x
238	x			x								x			
239	x		x									x	x		
240	x			x									x		
241	x			x									x		
242	x		x										x		
243	x		x										x		
244	x			x									x		
245	x	x													x
246	x			x					x		x				
247	x	x							x		x				
248	x	x												x	
249	x						x								x
250	x			x								x			
251	x		x									x			
252	x		x									x			
253	x	x										x			
254	x	x	x									x	x		
255	x		x									x			
256	x		x									x			
257	x		x										x		
258	x	x											x		
259	x	x	x										x		
260	x	x											x		
261	x	x											x		
262	x		x									x			
263	x	x	x		x	x									x
264	x		x												x
265	x		x		x							x			
266	x	x	x				x		x		x				
267	x		x	x			x					x			
268	x		x									x			
269	x				x				x	x					
270	x		x										x		
271	x		x										x		
272	x		x									x	x		
273	x		x									x			
274	x	x							x		x				

CiteID	Lit	Species							Methods						
		<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	<i>Nd</i>	T	Tdata	Tlit	C	G	I	O
275	x	x							x		x				
276	x							x				x			
277	x		x										x		
278	x		x										x		
279	x		x										x		
280	x			x					x		x				
281	x			x					x	x					
282	x	x											x		
283	x		x										x		
284	x							x				x	x		
285	x		x									x			
286	x		x						x		x	x			
287	x	x	x						x		x				
288	x						x							x	
289	x						x		x		x				
290	x						x		x		x				
291	x						x		x		x				
292	x		x									x			
293	x		x				x		x	x		x			
294	x	x												x	
295	x	x												x	
296	x			x					x		x				
297	x	x												x	
298	x	x												x	
299	x		x						x		x				
300	x	x							x		x				
301	x			x								x			
302	x			x								x			
303	x							x			x				
304	x	x							x	x					
305	x						x					x			
306	x		x						x		x			x	
307	x	x							x	x					
308	x		x						x		x	x			
309	x		x						x		x				
310	x		x						x	x					
311	x			x								x			
312	x	x	x	x											x
313	x		x											x	
314	x	x							x	x					
315	x		x						x	x					
316	x		x									x			
317	x						x						x		
318	x			x								x			
319	x	x							x	x					
320	x		x				x					x			
321	x	x							x		x				
322	x		x						x		x				
323	x		x									x			
324	x	x													x
325	x	x							x		x				
326	x		x												x
327	x						x					x			
328	x		x									x			
329	x	x											x		
330	x	x												x	

CiteID	Lit	Species							Methods						
		<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	<i>Nd</i>	T	Tdata	Tlit	C	G	I	O
331	x		x												
332	x		x											x	
333	x				x							x			
334	x		x						x		x				
335	x	x							x		x				
336	x	x		x								x			
337	x		x						x	x		x			
338	x				x				x	x					
339	x				x				x	x					
340	x	x							x		x				
341	x	x							x		x				
342	x	x							x		x	x			
343	x	x							x		x				
344	x				x				x		x	x			
345	x				x							x			
346	x	x							x		x				
347	x		x						x		x				
348	x	x							x		x				
349	x	x											x		
350	x	x							x		x				
351	x	x													x
352	x	x													x
353	x	x													x
354	x		x						x		x				x
355	x	x													x
356	x	x							x		x				
357	x	x							x	x					
358	x	x							x	x					
359	x				x							x			
360	x				x								x		
361	x				x				x	x					
362	x	x							x	x					
363	x		x									x	x		
364	x	x										x			
365	x		x						x		x				
366	x		x						x		x				
367	x	x	x									x			
368	x		x						x		x				
369	x	x							x		x				
370	x		x						x		x				
371	x			x					x		x				
372	x	x							x		x	x			
373	x			x					x		x				
374	x			x					x		x				
375	x		x									x			
376	x		x						x	x					
377	x		x						x		x				
378	x	x	x									x			
379	x	x										x			
380	x			x								x			
381	x					x						x			
382	x		x									x			
383	x	x	x		x							x			
384	x				x							x			
385	x				x							x			
386	x			x					x		x				x

CiteID	Lit	Species							Methods						
		<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	<i>Nd</i>	T	Tdata	Tlit	C	G	I	O
387	x	x							x	x					
388	x	x	x					x	x	x					
389	x	x							x		x				
390	x	x							x	x					
391	x	x							x		x				
392	x		x						x		x				
393	x	x							x	x					
394	x	x							x	x					
395	x	x							x	x					
396	x		x						x	x					
397	x	x							x	x					
398	x	x	x						x	x					
399	x	x							x	x					
400	x	x							x	x					
401	x	x							x		x				
402	x							x					x		
403	x					x			x		x				
404	x					x			x		x				
405	x		x	x				x				x			
406	x					x						x			
407	x					x									x
408	x			x								x			
409	x	x												x	
410	x	x										x			
411	x	x							x		x				
412	x		x											x	
413	x			x								x			
414	x			x					x	x					
415	x		x									x			
416	x	x							x	x					
417	x	x							x	x					
418	x					x			x		x				
419	x			x								x			
420	x			x					x		x				
421	x			x					x		x				
422	x			x					x		x	x			
423	x			x					x		x				
424	x			x											x
425	x			x								x			
426	x		x									x			
427	x					x									x
428	x							x						x	
429	x		x											x	
430	x							x						x	
431	x		x											x	
432	x			x					x		x				
433	x			x					x		x				
434	x		x											x	
435	x		x											x	
436	x		x											x	
437	x		x											x	
438	x		x									x			
439	x					x						x			
440	x					x						x			
441	x					x						x			
442	x	x	x									x			

CiteID	Lit	Species							Methods						
		<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	<i>Nd</i>	T	Tdata	Tlit	C	G	I	O
443	x	x											x		
444	x		x										x		
445	x	x	x										x		
446	x	x	x										x		
447	x	x	x						x	x					
448	x	x												x	
449	x			x					x		x	x			
450	x		x		x								x		
451	x		x						x		x				
452	x		x						x		x				
453	x		x						x		x				
454	x		x		x		x		x		x	x			
455	x	x							x	x					
456	x	x							x		x				
457	x	x							x		x				
458	x		x									x			
459	x		x									x			
460	x				x								x		
461	x		x									x			
462	x		x						x		x				
463	x	x										x			
464	x	x											x		
465	x		x										x		
466	x		x										x		
467	x		x	x	x										x
468	x			x					x		x				
469	x	x										x			
470	x	x										x			
471	x		x						x		x				
472	x						x					x			
473	x	x										x			
474	x				x								x		
475	x	x											x		
476	x	x											x		
477	x	x										x			
478	x		x										x		
479	x				x				x		x				
480	x		x										x		
481	x				x										x
482	x	x							x		x				
483	x		x											x	
484	x				x								x		
485	x			x								x			
486	x	x	x						x	x					
487	x		x						x		x				
488	x				x							x			
489	x		x									x			
490	x		x									x			
491	x	x										x			
492	x		x									x			
493	x		x									x			
494	x		x									x			
495	x	x	x									x			
496	x				x							x			
497	x		x									x			
498	x		x									x			

CiteID	Lit	Species							Methods						
		<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	<i>Nd</i>	T	Tdata	Tlit	C	G	I	O
499	x		x									x			
500	x	x										x			
501	x		x									x			
502	x	x							x		x	x			
503	x		x									x			
504	x	x										x			x
505	x	x	x									x			
506	x	x	x						x	x					
507	x	x							x		x				
508	x	x	x												x
509	x				x							x			
510	x	x	x											x	
511	x		x											x	
512	x		x											x	
513	x		x									x			
514	x							x					x		
515	x			x					x		x				
516	x		x									x			
517	x	x							x		x				
518	x		x										x		
519	x	x							x	x					
520	x	x							x	x					
521	x		x						x	x					
522	x	x							x		x				
523	x			x					x	x					
524	x	x							x	x					
525	x	x							x	x					
526	x			x					x		x				
527	x			x					x		x				
528	x		x									x			
529	x		x						x		x	x			
530	x		x											x	
531	x		x						x		x				
532	x	x											x		
533	x	x											x		
534	x		x									x			
535	x		x									x			
536	x			x					x	x					
537	x	x							x	x					
538	x	x							x		x				
539	x	x							x		x				
540	x	x													x
541	x				x							x			
542	x	x							x	x					
543	x				x				x	x					
544	x	x							x	x					
545	x			x								x			
546	x			x									x		
547	x	x						x				x			
548	x	x											x		
549	x							x	x						
550	x		x										x		
551	x	x							x		x				
552	x				x				x	x					
553	x		x						x	x					
554	x		x						x	x					

CiteID	Lit	Species							Methods						
		<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	<i>Nd</i>	T	Tdata	Tlit	C	G	I	O
555	x		x						x	x					
556	x		x						x	x					
557	x		x						x	x					
558	x	x							x	x					x
559	x	x							x	x					
560	x		x						x	x		x			
561	x	x							x	x					
562	x	x	x					x	x	x					
563	x			x								x			
564	x							x			x				
565	x		x									x			
566	x	x							x		x				
567	x	x							x	x					
568	x	x							x	x					
569	x	x	x	x	x										x
570	x				x							x			
571	x		x									x			
572	x		x										x		
573	x	x	x		x				x		x	x			
574	x				x							x			
575	x	x							x	x					
576	x				x							x			
577	x	x										x			
578	x		x									x			
579	x				x				x	x					
580	x				x				x	x		x			
581	x	x										x			
582	x		x						x	x		x	x	x	
583	x	x											x		
584	x		x										x		
585	x				x								x		
586	x	x											x		
587	x				x								x		
588	x	x											x		
589	x	x											x		
590	x			x					x		x				
591	x				x							x			
592	x		x		x								x		
593	x				x								x		
594	x				x							x			
595	x				x								x		
596	x	x							x		x				
597	x		x										x		
598	x			x					x		x				
599	x	x							x		x	x			
600	x	x													x
601	x		x										x		
602	x		x										x		
603	x		x										x		
604	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x					x		
605	x		x										x		
606	x		x										x		
607	x		x						x		x				
608	x							x	x		x				
609	x				x									x	
610	x		x						x		x	x	x		

CiteID	Lit	Species								Methods					
		<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	<i>Nd</i>	T	Tdata	Tlit	C	G	I	O
611	x		x						x		x				
612	x	x							x		x				
613	x		x										x		
614	x		x										x		
615	x				x								x		
616	x		x										x		
617	x	x											x		
618	x		x										x		
619	x				x								x		
620	x		x		x								x		
621	x		x										x		
622	x	x											x		
623	x		x												x
624	x			x					x		x				
625	x				x				x		x				
626	x	x	x										x		
627	x	x							x		x				
628	x	x										x			
629	x				x							x			
630	x		x												x
631	x				x				x		x				
632	x	x												x	
633	x	x												x	
634	x	x							x		x			x	
635	x	x												x	
636	x						x					x			
637	x						x		x		x	x			
638	x				x				x		x				
639	x		x						x		x				
640	x		x						x	x					
641	x	x							x		x				
642	x		x						x		x				
643	x				x				x		x				
644	x	x	x				x		x		x				
645	x	x													x
646	x		x										x		
647	x						x		x		x				
648	x				x				x		x				
649	x	x							x		x				
650	x							x				x			
651	x							x				x			
652	x	x							x	x					
653	x	x													x
654	x	x							x	x					
655	x	x							x	x					
656	x	x							x	x					
657	x		x									x			
658	x		x									x			
659	x		x									x			
660	x		x										x		
661	x		x										x		
662	x	x							x		x				
663	x	x							x		x				
664	x		x						x		x				
665	x							x				x			
666	x		x									x			

CiteID	Lit	Species							Methods						
		<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	<i>Nd</i>	T	Tdata	Tlit	C	G	I	O
667	x	x										x			
668	x	x										x			
669	x				x								x		
670	x		x												x
671	x			x								x			
672	x			x					x	x					
673	x			x											x
674	x	x							x		x				
675	x						x		x	x					
676	x		x									x			
677	x		x						x	x					
678	x		x						x	x					
679	x			x								x			
680	x				x							x			
681	x				x							x			
682	x	x	x		x				x	x					
683	x				x				x	x					
684	x		x						x	x					
685	x				x				x	x					
686	x		x	x											x
687	x						x		x		x				
688	x						x		x		x				
689	x						x		x		x				
690	x						x		x		x				
691	x						x		x		x				
692	x	x							x		x				
693	x	x										x			
694	x	x							x		x				
695	x	x					x		x	x					
696	x	x							x		x				
697	x	x					x		x	x					
698	x	x					x		x	x					
699	x				x							x			
700	x						x						x		
701	x		x											x	
702	x		x										x		
703	x				x								x		
704	x		x										x		
705	x				x								x		
706	x	x											x		
707	x			x									x		
708	x		x										x		
709	x		x									x			
710	x				x								x		
711	x		x			x			x		x				
712	x		x										x		
713	x			x								x			
714	x	x							x		x				
715	x	x												x	
716	x	x												x	
717	x	x											x		
718	x		x										x		
719	x		x									x			
720	x		x									x			
721	x	x	x		x								x		
722	x	x							x	x					

CiteID	Lit	Species							Methods						
		<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	<i>Nd</i>	T	Tdata	Tlit	C	G	I	O
723	x						x		x	x					
724	x		x						x	x					
725	x	x							x	x		x	x		
726	x		x						x		x				
727	x		x						x	x					
728	x	x							x		x	x			
729	x	x	x									x			
730	x	x												x	
731	x			x								x			
732	x	x	x		x		x						x		
733	x						x					x			
734	x	x											x		
735	x		x									x			
736	x	x							x		x				
737	x						x		x		x				
738	x						x		x		x				
739	x	x										x			
740	x	x										x			
741	x	x							x		x				
742	x	x										x	x		
743	x	x							x		x				
744	x				x				x	x					
745	x				x							x			
746	x				x							x			
747	x		x						x		x				
748	x			x					x		x	x			
749	x	x	x		x							x			
750	x	x													x
751	x			x									x		
752	x			x								x			
753	x			x								x			
754	x			x								x			
755	x	x											x		
756	x		x										x		
757	x		x						x	x					
758	x	x		x					x	x				x	
759	x	x													x
760	x		x										x		
761	x		x										x		
762	x						x						x		
763	x			x					x		x				
764	x			x					x		x				
765	x					x						x			
766	x		x										x		
767	x		x									x			
768	x	x											x		
769	x	x							x		x				
770	x	x							x		x				
771	x	x							x		x				
772	x			x					x		x				
773	x	x	x	x			x					x			
774	x		x									x			
775	x		x		x							x			
776	x				x							x			
777	x				x							x			
778	x			x								x			

CiteID	Lit	Species							Methods						
		<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	<i>Nd</i>	T	Tdata	Tlit	C	G	I	O
779	x						x		x		x				
780	x	x										x			
781	x	x										x			
782	x	x									x				
783	x				x				x		x				
784	x	x							x		x				
785	x							x							x
786	x	x	x												x
787	x	x	x					x							x
788	x							x							x
789	x							x			x				
790	x							x			x				
791	x							x			x				
792	x	x							x	x					
793	x	x							x		x				
794	x	x							x		x				
795	x	x							x		x				
796	x	x													x
797	x	x							x		x				
798	x	x							x		x				
799	x	x													x
800	x	x													x
801	x				x							x			
802	x		x						x	x					
803	x			x					x		x				x
804	x		x						x		x				
805	x		x									x			
806	x		x						x		x				
807	x		x									x			
808	x		x						x	x					
809	x							x	x	x					
810	x							x	x	x					
811	x		x						x		x				
812	x		x									x			
813	x	x	x						x	x					
814	x		x												x
815	x		x												x
816	x		x												x
817	x				x										x
818	x		x												x
819	x		x												x
820	x	x													x
821	x	x													x
822	x	x													x
823	x	x													x
824	x		x												x
825	x		x												x
826	x	x													x
827	x							x			x				
828	x							x			x				
829	x							x							x
830	x		x		x							x			
831	x							x			x				
832	x							x			x				
833	x							x			x				
834	x							x			x				

CiteID	Lit	Species							Methods						
		<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	<i>Nd</i>	T	Tdata	Tlit	C	G	I	O
835	x					x			x		x				
836	x			x					x		x				
837	x			x					x		x				
838	x			x					x		x				
839	x			x					x		x				
840	x		x											x	
841	x	x	x						x		x	x			
842	x	x							x		x				
843	x		x						x		x				
844	x						x		x		x				
845	x	x							x	x					
846	x		x			x			x		x				
847	x		x									x			
848	x		x									x			
849	x				x							x			
850	x			x								x			
851	x			x								x	x		
852	x			x									x		
853	x			x								x			
854	x			x								x			
855	x	x											x		
856	x	x											x		
857	x		x						x	x					
858	x		x						x	x		x			
859	x				x				x		x				
860	x	x			x							x			
861	x		x		x				x		x		x		
862	x		x									x			
863	x		x				x		x		x				
864	x	x							x		x				
865	x						x		x		x				
866	x				x								x		
867	x				x								x		
868	x		x									x			
869	x			x								x			
870	x		x									x			
871	x						x					x	x		
872	x	x	x									x		x	
873	x	x		x								x			
874	x							x	x		x	x			
875	x					x									x
876	x		x	x	x		x					x			
877	x						x					x			
878	x			x								x			
879	x		x									x			
880	x				x				x		x	x	x		
881	x		x						x		x	x			
882	x			x					x		x	x			
883	x		x									x			
884	x			x					x		x	x			
885	x	x										x			
886	x	x							x		x	x			
887	x	x							x		x				
888	x			x								x			
889	x	x							x		x			x	
890	x		x						x		x				

CiteID	Lit	Species							Methods						
		<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	<i>Nd</i>	T	Tdata	Tlit	C	G	I	O
891	x	x										x			
892	x	x													x
893	x		x									x			
894	x	x								x	x				
895	x	x								x	x				
896	x	x								x	x				
897	x						x								x
898	x				x							x			
899	x				x					x		x			
900	x		x							x		x			
901	x	x													x
902	x		x												x
903	x	x													x
904	x	x								x		x			x
905	x	x													x
906	x	x								x		x			x
907	x			x										x	
908	x				x									x	
909	x	x								x	x				
910	x	x								x	x				
911	x		x												x
912	x				x									x	
913	x	x	x												x
914	x		x									x			
915	x		x	x	x										x
916	x		x												x
917	x				x							x	x		
918	x		x					x		x		x			
919	x				x					x		x			
920	x		x												x
921	x	x													x
922	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x						x	
923	x			x											x
924	x	x												x	
925	x		x									x			
926	x		x							x		x			
927	x				x					x		x			
928	x	x										x			
929	x	x										x			
930	x				x							x			
931	x		x							x		x			
932	x		x							x		x			
933	x							x		x		x			
934	x		x							x	x				
935	x	x	x							x	x				
936	x	x								x		x			
937	x	x											x		
938	x	x											x		
939	x			x						x		x			
940	x	x								x		x			
941	x			x						x	x				
942	x			x						x	x				
943	x				x					x		x			
944	x	x												x	
945	x														x
946	x	x	x									x			

CiteID	Lit	Species							Methods						
		<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	<i>Nd</i>	T	Tdata	Tlit	C	G	I	O
947	x		x									x			
948	x				x				x		x				
949	x				x							x			
950	x		x											x	
951	x		x											x	
952	x		x						x	x					
953	x		x						x	x					
954	x		x											x	
955	x	x							x		x				
956	x		x						x		x				
957	x		x						x		x	x			
958	x	x												x	
959	x	x												x	
960	x			x										x	
961	x		x		x							x			
962	x	x							x	x					
963	x	x		x					x	x					
964	x	x							x		x				
965	x	x							x		x				
966	x	x							x		x				x
967	x				x									x	
968	x		x									x			

Table S1.3. Bibliography for sea turtle movements and connectivity, combining all references from the literature review (first and updated; n = 891) and unique references from direct data contributions used within this study (n = 77).

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Appendix S2. Summary of all sea turtle telemetry data included in the current study.

Funding sources for individual datasets included: Betz Chair for Environment Science at Drexel University; British Chelonia Group; Center for the Dynamics and Evolution of the Land-Sea Interface; Cleveland Metroparks Zoo - Scott Neotropical Fund; Darwin Initiative; Deutsche Gesellschaft fuer Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) GmbH Philippines; Disney Worldwide Conservation Fund (STO-08-01); Emirates Nature – WWF; European Union Interreg; Florida Sea Turtle License Plate grant; FONCyT PICT 2013-2099 and 2017-1575; Fondo para la Conservación Ambiental from Banco Galicia; Friends of Long Marine Laboratory; Fundación Biodiversidad of the Ministerio de Pesca, Alimentación y Medio Ambiente ; Gabon Sea Turtle Partnership (with funding from the Marine Turtle Conservation Fund); Inter-American Institute for Global Change Research (IAI) CRN 2076; Jack Schrey Distinguished Professor of Biology at Indiana University - Purdue University Fort Wayne; Japan Bekko Association; Marilyn Davis Memorial Scholarship; National Marine Fisheries Service Species Recovery Grants to States Program; Natural Environment Research Council; Private donors to the Virginia Aquarium & Marine Science Foundation; Qatar National Research Fund; Society for the Study of Amphibians and Reptiles; Tagging of Pacific Predators Project; The Leatherback Trust; TOTAL Foundation; United States Navy Fleet Forces Command and Naval Facilities Engineering Command; University of California Santa Cruz Graduate Student Association; University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria; and Wildlife Conservation Society.

Table S2.4. Primary data providers for the sea turtle tracking data used in this study.

ProvID	First name	Last name	Organization
1	Susanne	Åkesson	Lund University
2	Joanna	Alfaro-Shigueto	ProDelphinus; University of Exeter; Universidad Científica del Sur
3	Diego Fernando	Amorocho Llanos	Research Center for Environmental Management and Development - CIMAD
4	Marina	Antonopoulou	Emirates Nature - World Wildlife Fund
5	George	Balazs	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, National Marine Fisheries Service, Pacific Islands Fisheries Science Center
6	Warren	Baverstock	The Aquarium and Dubai Turtle Rehabilitation Project
7	Janice	Blumenthal	Cayman Islands Department of Environment
8	Annette	Broderick	Centre for Ecology and Conservation, University of Exeter
9	Ignacio	Bruno	Instituto Nacional de Investigación y Desarrollo Pesquero (INIDEP)
10	Ali Fuat	Canbolat	EKAD (Ecological Research Society); Hacettepe University
11	Paolo	Casale	University of Pisa
12	Daniel	Cejudo	Biology Department of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria
13	Michael	Coyne	seaturtle.org
14	Andrew	DiMatteo	CheloniData, LLC

ProvID	First name	Last name	Organization
15	Kara	Dodge	New England Aquarium
16	Nicole	Esteban	Swansea University
17	Angela	Formia	Wildlife Conservation Society
18	Mariana M. P. B.	Fuentes	Florida State University
19	Julie	Garnier	The Zoological Society of London
20	Matthew	Godfrey	North Carolina Wildlife Resources Commission
21	Brendan	Godley	Centre for Ecology and Conservation, University of Exeter; Marine Turtle Research Group
22	Victoria	González Carman	Instituto de Investigaciones Marinas y Costeras (CONICET - UNMdP), Instituto de Investigación y Desarrollo Pesquero
23	Catherine	Hart	Grupo Tortuguero de las Californias A.C.; Investigación, Capacitación y Soluciones Ambientales y Sociales A.C. Tepic
24	Lucy	Hawkes	Centre for Ecology and Conservation, University of Exeter
25	Graeme	Hays	School of Life and Environmental Sciences, Deakin University
26	Nicholas	Hill	The Zoological Society of London
27	Sandra	Hochscheid	Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn
28	Yakup	Kaska	Dekamer - Sea Turtle Rescue Center; Pamukkale University
29	Yaniv	Levy	Israel Nature and Parks Authority; University of Haifa
30	César P.	Ley-Quiñónez	Instituto Politécnico Nacional, CIIDIR- SINALOA
31	Gwen	Lockhart	Naval Facilities Engineering Command; Virginia Aquarium Marine Science Foundation
32	Milagros	López-Mendilaharsu	Projeto TAMAR
33	Paolo	Luschi	University of Pisa
34	Jeffrey	Mangel	ProDelphinus; University of Exeter
35	Dimitris	Margaritoulis	ARCHELON, the Sea Turtle Protection Society of Greece
36	Sara	Maxwell	University of Washington
37	Catherine	McClellan	Duke University Marine Laboratory
38	Kristian	Metcalfe	University of Exeter
39	Antonio	Mingozzi	University of Calabria
40	Felix	Moncada	Biologo Pesquero y Jefe Programa de Tortugas Marinas Centro de Investigaciones Pesqueras (CIP)
41	Wallace	Nichols	California Academy of Sciences; Center for the Blue Economy

ProvID	First name	Last name	Organization
42	Denise	Parker	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, National Marine Fisheries Service, Pacific Islands Fisheries Science Center
43	Samir	Patel	Drexel University; Coonamessett Farm Foundation
44	Nicolas	Pilcher	Marine Research Foundation
45	Jeffrey	Polovina	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, National Marine Fisheries Service, Pacific Islands Fisheries Science Center
46	Andrew	Read	Duke University Marine Laboratory
47	ALan	Rees	ARCHELON, the Sea Turtle Protection Society of Greece; Centre for Ecology and Conservation, University of Exeter
48	David	Robinson	The Aquarium and Dubai Turtle Rehabilitation Project
49	Nathan	Robinson	Fundación Oceanogràfic
50	Alejandra G.	Sandoval-Lugo	Instituto Politécnico Nacional, CIIDIR- SINALOA
51	Gail	Schofield	Queen Mary University
52	Jeffrey	Seminoff	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, National Marine Fisheries Service, Southwest Fisheries Science Center
53	Erin	Seney	Marine Turtle Research Group, University of Central Florida
54	Robin	Snape	Centre for Ecology and Conservation, University of Exeter
55	Doğan	Sözbilen	Dekamer - Sea Turtle Rescue Center; Pamukkale University
56	Jesús	Tomás	Cavanilles Institute of Biodiversity and Evolutionary Biology, University of Valencia
57	Nuria	Varo-Cruz	Biology Department of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria; Instituto Canario de Ciencias Marinas
58	Natalie	Wildermann	Texas Sea Grant at Texas A&M University
59	Matthew	Witt	Centre for Ecology and Conservation, University of Exeter
60	Alan A.	Zavala-Norzagaray	Instituto Politécnico Nacional, CIIDIR- SINALOA

Table S2.5. Details for each telemetry tagged sea turtle with tracking data. Sex: F = female, M = male, blank = unknown sex; Age class: A = adult, J = juvenile, S = sub-adult; Days = number of days with location data; Start date = first date of tracking data; End date = last date of tracking data; Months = number of months with tracking data; Start month = first month of tracking data; End month = last month of tracking data; Years = number of years with tracking data; Start year = first year with tracking data; End year = last year with tracking data; Start marID: marine region ID associated with the start location (refer to MarID in Table S3.8 for marine region information ; CiteID1-4: citation IDs associated with the tracked animal (refer to the CiteID in Table S1.3 for full citation information); ProvID1-5: provider ID associated with the tracked animal (refer to ProvID in Table S2.1 for provider information).

Species	Tag ID	Sensor	Sex	Age class	Days	Start date	End date	Months	Start month	End month	Years	Start year	End year	Start marID	CiteID1	CiteID2	CiteID3	CiteID4	ProvID1	ProvID2	ProvID3	ProvID4	ProvID5
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	19580_97	Argos Doppler		J	106	1997-02-05	1997-05-28	4	2	5	1	1997	1997	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	19581_97	Argos Doppler	J		7	1997-04-23	1997-05-02	2	4	5	1	1997	1997	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	19582_97	Argos Doppler	J		122	1997-03-17	1997-07-31	5	3	7	1	1997	1997	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	19585_97	Argos Doppler	J		79	1997-02-16	1997-05-16	4	2	5	1	1997	1997	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	19586_97	Argos Doppler	J		164	1997-04-22	1997-10-17	7	4	10	1	1997	1997	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	19587_97	Argos Doppler	J		11	1997-04-10	1997-04-24	1	4	4	1	1997	1997	216	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	19590_98	Argos Doppler	J		107	1998-08-27	1998-12-12	5	8	12	1	1998	1998	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	19593_07	Argos Doppler			83	2007-01-28	2007-07-13	7	1	7	1	2007	2007	203	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	19593_11	Argos Doppler			77	2011-07-15	2012-01-27	7	1	12	2	2011	2012	103	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	19594_98	Argos Doppler	J		87	1998-02-07	1998-05-21	4	2	5	1	1998	1998	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	19595_11	Argos Doppler			151	2011-07-16	2013-09-14	12	1	12	3	2011	2013	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	19597_03	Argos Doppler			218	2003-04-02	2004-08-16	12	1	12	2	2003	2004	204	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	19598_98	Argos Doppler	J		160	1998-01-08	1998-07-19	7	1	7	1	1998	1998	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	19599_04	Argos Doppler			120	2004-01-16	2004-08-28	8	1	8	1	2004	2004	204	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	19599_98	Argos Doppler	J		185	1998-01-07	1998-08-01	8	1	8	1	1998	1998	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	19601_98	Argos Doppler			5	1998-10-19	1998-11-28	2	10	11	1	1998	1998	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	19602_99	Argos Doppler	J		7	1999-02-01	1999-03-23	2	2	3	1	1999	1999	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	19604_98	Argos Doppler	J		12	1998-11-02	1998-12-23	2	11	12	1	1998	1998	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	19606_03	Argos Doppler			71	2003-02-19	2003-08-10	7	2	8	1	2003	2003	204	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	19606_98	Argos Doppler	J		18	1998-01-19	1999-03-30	6	1	12	2	1998	1999	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	19608_98	Argos Doppler	J		157	1998-08-27	1999-02-09	7	1	12	2	1998	1999	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	22150_00	Argos Doppler	J		226	2000-03-05	2001-10-23	12	1	12	2	2000	2001	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	22151_11	Argos Doppler			120	2011-07-16	2013-10-29	12	1	12	3	2011	2013	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	22152_00	Argos Doppler	J		55	2000-02-03	2000-07-09	6	2	7	1	2000	2000	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	22153_00	Argos Doppler	J		140	2000-03-07	2000-11-08	9	3	11	1	2000	2000	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	22168_11	Argos Doppler			142	2011-07-13	2013-02-02	12	1	12	3	2011	2013	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	22172_00	Argos Doppler	J		16	2000-02-12	2000-04-02	3	2	4	1	2000	2000	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	22173_00	Argos Doppler	J		26	2000-01-17	2000-03-30	3	1	3	1	2000	2000	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	22174_99	Argos Doppler	J		105	1999-12-14	2000-09-09	10	1	12	2	1999	2000	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	22183_10	Argos Doppler			41	2010-04-10	2010-08-20	5	4	8	1	2010	2010	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	22270_11	Argos Doppler			154	2011-07-17	2013-08-02	12	1	12	3	2011	2013	103	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	22275_11	Argos Doppler			39	2011-07-21	2011-10-07	4	7	10	1	2011	2011	103	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	22278_10	Argos Doppler			95	2010-04-10	2011-01-17	10	1	12	2	2010	2011	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	22279_10	Argos Doppler			107	2010-04-10	2011-02-25	11	1	12	2	2010	2011	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	22534_00	Argos Doppler	J		73	2000-08-23	2001-02-01	7	1	12	2	2000	2001	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	22535_11	Argos Doppler			112	2011-07-16	2013-01-27	12	1	12	3	2011	2013	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	22981_04	Argos Doppler			82	2004-03-22	2004-08-27	6	3	8	1	2004	2004	204	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	23002_11	Argos Doppler			175	2011-07-16	2013-11-23	12	1	12	3	2011	2013	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	23045_11	Argos Doppler			119	2011-07-16	2013-02-16	12	1	12	3	2011	2013	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	23068_04	Argos Doppler			67	2004-12-01	2005-05-23	6	1	12	2	2004	2005	203	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	23513_04	Argos Doppler			50	2004-03-09	2005-03-20	5	1	5	2	2004	2005	204	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	23513_11	Argos Doppler			50	2011-07-16	2011-11-30	5	7	11	1	2011	2011	103	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	23537_11	Argos Doppler			103	2011-07-15	2012-02-12	8	1	12	2	2011	2012	103	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	23542_11	Argos Doppler			43	2011-07-16	2011-11-08	5	7	11	1	2011	2011	103	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	23559_04	Argos Doppler			32	2004-04-21	2004-06-25	3	4	6	1	2004	2004	203	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	24179_99	Argos Doppler	J		98	1999-02-03	1999-06-14	5	2	6	1	1999	1999	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	24181_97	Argos Doppler			43	1997-01-26	1997-03-20	3	1	3	1	1997	1997	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	24182_97	Argos Doppler	J		46	1997-09-11	1997-11-17	3	9	11	1	1997	1997	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	24184_97	Argos Doppler	J		19	1997-03-30	1997-05-11	3	3	5	1	1997	1997	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	24185_98	Argos Doppler	J		62	1998-02-08	1998-04-19	3	2	4	1	1998	1998	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	24192_03	Argos Doppler			140	2003-11-28	2004-07-22	9	1	12	2	2003	2004	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	24192_10	Argos Doppler			105	2010-04-10	2010-11-14	8	4	11	1	2010	2010	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	24193_11	Argos Doppler			5	2011-07-14	2011-07-23	1	7	7	1	2011	2011	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		

Species	Tag ID	Sensor	Sex	Age class	Days	Start date	End date	Months	Start month	End month	Years	Start year	End year	Start marID	CiteID1	CiteID2	CiteID3	CiteID4	ProvID1	ProvID2	ProvID3	ProvID4	ProvID5
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	24747_00	Argos Doppler		J	56	2000-06-02	2000-10-15	5	6	10	1	2000	2000	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	25358_10	Argos Doppler			113	2010-04-10	2011-03-26	12	1	12	2	2010	2011	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	25359_11	Argos Doppler			28	2011-07-18	2011-11-23	5	7	11	1	2011	2011	103	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	25359_98	Argos Doppler		J	39	1998-12-24	1999-07-22	8	1	12	2	1998	1999	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	25360_02	Argos Doppler			36	2002-05-05	2002-10-09	6	5	10	1	2002	2002	204	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	25360_10	Argos Doppler			146	2010-04-10	2011-07-15	12	1	12	2	2010	2011	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	25695_11	Argos Doppler			176	2011-07-17	2013-07-13	12	1	12	3	2011	2013	103	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	29060_11	Argos Doppler			22	2011-07-22	2011-10-14	4	7	10	1	2011	2011	103	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	29066_03	Argos Doppler			177	2003-12-24	2005-01-31	12	1	12	3	2003	2005	153	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	40470_08	Argos Doppler	M		10	2008-12-26	2009-02-16	3	1	12	2	2008	2009	203	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	40470_11	Argos Doppler			51	2011-07-15	2011-11-28	5	7	11	1	2011	2011	103	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	40471_11	Argos Doppler			113	2011-07-14	2013-01-30	12	1	12	3	2011	2013	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	40473_07	Argos Doppler			31	2007-12-04	2008-07-01	7	1	12	2	2007	2008	203	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	40605_11	Argos Doppler			18	2011-07-18	2011-09-24	3	7	9	1	2011	2011	103	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	40703_10	Argos Doppler			147	2010-04-10	2011-07-18	12	1	12	2	2010	2011	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	40719_10	Argos Doppler			128	2010-04-09	2011-02-23	11	1	12	2	2010	2011	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	40725_10	Argos Doppler			134	2010-04-09	2011-02-27	11	1	12	2	2010	2011	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	41315_06	Argos Doppler			19	2006-10-24	2007-01-20	4	1	12	2	2006	2007	102	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	41315_11	Argos Doppler			94	2011-07-16	2012-10-14	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	41423_07	Argos Doppler	F		16	2007-10-19	2008-04-05	7	1	12	2	2007	2008	204	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	41788_08	Argos Doppler	M		15	2008-01-23	2008-04-22	4	1	4	1	2008	2008	153	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	41789_08	Argos Doppler			38	2008-05-20	2008-11-09	7	5	11	1	2008	2008	153	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	42477_06	Argos Doppler	F		22	2006-07-22	2006-09-17	3	7	9	1	2006	2006	136	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	42479_06	Argos Doppler	F		19	2006-08-24	2006-10-27	3	8	10	1	2006	2006	136	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	42711_11	Argos Doppler			88	2011-07-16	2012-11-03	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	42712_11	Argos Doppler			211	2011-07-15	2012-09-19	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	103	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	42714_08	Argos Doppler			72	2008-06-12	2009-06-28	11	1	12	2	2008	2009	153	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	42714_11	Argos Doppler			190	2011-07-15	2013-09-01	12	1	12	3	2011	2013	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	42715_10	Argos Doppler			125	2010-04-10	2011-04-25	12	1	12	2	2010	2011	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	42717_10	Argos Doppler			153	2010-04-10	2011-09-10	12	1	12	2	2010	2011	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	4800_07	Argos Doppler	F		37	2007-02-09	2007-04-20	3	2	4	1	2007	2007	204	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	50135_11	Argos Doppler			246	2011-07-15	2013-07-09	12	1	12	3	2011	2013	103	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	50137_11	Argos Doppler			74	2011-11-12	2012-08-04	10	1	12	2	2011	2012	203	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	50138_10	Argos Doppler			223	2010-04-09	2011-09-18	12	1	12	2	2010	2011	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	50139_10	Argos Doppler			91	2010-04-10	2010-11-04	8	4	11	1	2010	2010	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	50140_10	Argos Doppler			5	2010-04-10	2010-04-18	1	4	4	1	2010	2010	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	50141_10	Argos Doppler			56	2010-04-10	2010-09-25	6	4	9	1	2010	2010	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	50144_05	Argos Doppler			60	2005-01-16	2005-07-08	7	1	7	1	2005	2005	153	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	50144_11	Argos Doppler			24	2011-07-17	2011-10-17	4	7	10	1	2011	2011	103	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	50145_05	Argos Doppler			98	2005-05-20	2006-03-11	11	1	12	2	2005	2006	204	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	50146_11	Argos Doppler			140	2011-07-15	2013-06-20	12	1	12	3	2011	2013	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	50151_11	Argos Doppler			37	2011-07-15	2011-10-03	4	7	10	1	2011	2011	103	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	50152_11	Argos Doppler			40	2011-07-15	2012-01-31	7	1	12	2	2011	2012	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	50154_10	Argos Doppler			11	2010-04-19	2011-01-11	6	1	12	2	2010	2011	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	50155_10	Argos Doppler			6	2010-04-10	2010-04-25	1	4	4	1	2010	2010	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	50158_10	Argos Doppler			135	2010-04-10	2011-05-31	12	1	12	2	2010	2011	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	5152_03	Argos Doppler			3	2003-06-04	2003-06-07	1	6	6	1	2003	2003	153	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	52693_11	Argos Doppler			157	2011-07-16	2012-07-28	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	52694_11	Argos Doppler			77	2011-07-14	2012-01-01	7	1	12	2	2011	2012	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	52695_09	Argos Doppler			32	2009-02-17	2009-06-02	5	2	6	1	2009	2009	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	52695_11	Argos Doppler			59	2011-07-18	2011-12-20	6	7	12	1	2011	2011	103	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	52697_11	Argos Doppler			173	2011-07-14	2012-09-27	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	52700_09	Argos Doppler			146	2009-04-15	2011-02-25	12	1	12	3	2009	2011	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	52701_09	Argos Doppler			65	2009-04-23	2010-03-22	12	1	12	2	2009	2010	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	52703_10	Argos Doppler			239	2010-04-11	2011-10-19	12	1	12	2	2010	2011	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	52704_09	Argos Doppler			107	2009-04-03	2010-07-24	12	1	12	2	2009	2010	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53743_05	Argos Doppler			109	2005-06-26	2006-08-22	12	1	12	2	2005	2006	204	455				5	42	45		

Species	Tag ID	Sensor	Sex	Age class	Days	Start date	End date	Months	Start month	End month	Years	Start year	End year	Start marID	CiteID1	CiteID2	CiteID3	CiteID4	ProvID1	ProvID2	ProvID3	ProvID4	ProvID5
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53743_07	Argos Doppler			29	2007-09-26	2008-04-23	7	1	12	2	2007	2008	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53745_05	Argos Doppler			22	2005-11-21	2006-02-03	4	1	12	2	2005	2006	204	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53745_07	Argos Doppler			127	2007-09-26	2008-08-17	12	1	12	2	2007	2008	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53746_05	Argos Doppler			70	2005-04-14	2005-11-07	8	4	11	1	2005	2005	204	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53746_07	Argos Doppler			45	2007-09-28	2008-05-05	7	1	12	2	2007	2008	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53747_05	Argos Doppler			95	2005-03-16	2005-11-21	9	3	11	1	2005	2005	203	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53748_05	Argos Doppler			24	2005-12-20	2006-03-07	4	1	12	2	2005	2006	203	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53749_09	Argos Doppler			124	2009-04-11	2010-03-22	12	1	12	2	2009	2010	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53750_05	Argos Doppler			25	2005-04-04	2005-06-30	3	4	6	1	2005	2005	102	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53750_07	Argos Doppler			159	2007-09-28	2008-12-31	10	3	12	2	2007	2008	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53751_07	Argos Doppler			98	2007-09-26	2008-09-08	12	1	12	2	2007	2008	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53753_07	Argos Doppler			77	2007-09-28	2008-10-08	9	3	11	2	2007	2008	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53754_11	Argos Doppler			143	2011-07-14	2012-07-01	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53756_07	Argos Doppler			22	2007-09-26	2008-01-02	5	1	12	2	2007	2008	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53758_05	Argos Doppler			37	2005-02-06	2005-05-29	4	2	5	1	2005	2005	153	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53758_11	Argos Doppler			92	2011-07-15	2012-02-26	8	1	12	2	2011	2012	103	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53759_11	Argos Doppler			133	2011-07-16	2012-06-06	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	103	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53760_07	Argos Doppler			46	2007-09-28	2008-08-11	7	6	12	2	2007	2008	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53761_07	Argos Doppler			83	2007-09-26	2008-06-06	10	1	12	2	2007	2008	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53764_07	Argos Doppler			115	2007-09-26	2008-08-07	12	1	12	2	2007	2008	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53767_11	Argos Doppler			134	2011-03-06	2011-11-07	9	3	11	1	2011	2011	204	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53768_06	Argos Doppler			52	2006-04-28	2006-09-24	6	4	9	1	2006	2006	105	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53769_06	Argos Doppler			9	2006-03-24	2006-06-04	3	3	6	1	2006	2006	205	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53769_11	Argos Doppler			100	2011-07-16	2012-12-03	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53770_06	Argos Doppler			32	2006-01-17	2006-05-17	5	1	5	1	2006	2006	204	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53770_11	Argos Doppler			7	2011-07-16	2011-08-07	2	7	8	1	2011	2011	103	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53771_06	Argos Doppler			34	2006-02-12	2006-07-14	6	2	7	1	2006	2006	204	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53771_11	Argos Doppler			24	2011-07-17	2011-10-17	4	7	10	1	2011	2011	103	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53772_06	Argos Doppler			27	2006-05-13	2006-09-08	5	5	9	1	2006	2006	204	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	57144_11	Argos Doppler			36	2011-07-17	2011-12-28	6	7	12	1	2011	2011	103	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	57146_10	Argos Doppler			129	2010-04-10	2011-05-16	12	1	12	2	2010	2011	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	57147_11	Argos Doppler			75	2011-07-15	2012-07-25	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	57148_11	Argos Doppler			21	2011-07-19	2011-10-19	4	7	10	1	2011	2011	103	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	57150_11	Argos Doppler			87	2011-07-16	2012-10-14	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	57152_11	Argos Doppler			41	2011-07-15	2011-10-27	4	7	10	1	2011	2011	103	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	65415_10	Argos Doppler			94	2010-04-10	2011-01-26	10	1	12	2	2010	2011	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	65416_10	Argos Doppler			84	2010-04-10	2011-01-02	10	1	12	2	2010	2011	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	65417_10	Argos Doppler			139	2010-04-10	2011-06-09	12	1	12	2	2010	2011	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	65418_09	Argos Doppler			83	2009-04-03	2010-03-26	12	1	12	2	2009	2010	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	65419_10	Argos Doppler			66	2010-04-10	2010-11-09	8	4	11	1	2010	2010	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	65420_10	Argos Doppler			67	2010-04-10	2010-11-08	8	4	11	1	2010	2010	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	65421_11	Argos Doppler			152	2011-07-15	2013-04-20	12	1	12	3	2011	2013	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	65422_10	Argos Doppler			24	2010-04-10	2010-06-27	3	4	6	1	2010	2010	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	65424_11	Argos Doppler			11	2011-07-17	2011-08-12	2	7	8	1	2011	2011	103	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	65426_11	Argos Doppler			133	2011-07-15	2012-04-18	10	1	12	2	2011	2012	103	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	65433_11	Argos Doppler			96	2011-07-13	2012-12-24	10	1	12	2	2011	2012	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	65435_11	Argos Doppler			31	2011-07-18	2011-11-27	5	7	11	1	2011	2011	103	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	65436_10	Argos Doppler			102	2010-04-10	2010-12-18	9	4	12	1	2010	2010	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	67469_07	Argos Doppler			9	2007-01-09	2007-02-25	2	1	2	1	2007	2007	203	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	67469_10	Argos Doppler	F		48	2010-04-07	2011-02-20	11	1	12	2	2010	2011	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	68329_10	Argos Doppler			18	2010-04-10	2010-07-03	4	4	7	1	2010	2010	105	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	68330_09	Argos Doppler	F		30	2009-11-25	2010-04-25	6	1	12	2	2009	2010	203	455				5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	68330_11	Argos Doppler			119	2011-07-16	2013-03-17	12	1	12	3	2011	2013	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	68331_09	Argos Doppler			68	2009-04-03	2010-03-10	12	1	12	2	2009	2010	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	68331_11	Argos Doppler			96	2011-07-14	2012-11-06	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	68332_09	Argos Doppler			114	2009-04-19	2010-08-21	12	1	12	2	2009	2010	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	68335_11	Argos Doppler			117	2011-07-13	2012-10-17	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45		

Species	Tag ID	Sensor	Sex	Age class	Days	Start date	End date	Months	Start month	End month	Years	Start year	End year	Start marID	CiteID1	CiteID2	CiteID3	CiteID4	ProvID1	ProvID2	ProvID3	ProvID4	ProvID5	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	68336_11	Argos Doppler			152	2011-07-13	2013-04-10	12	1	12	3	2011	2013	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	71905_07	Argos Doppler			32	2007-09-28	2008-01-12	5	1	12	2	2007	2008	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	71905_09	Argos Doppler			155	2009-04-05	2010-07-26	12	1	12	2	2009	2010	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	71906_07	Argos Doppler			98	2007-09-28	2008-06-10	10	1	12	2	2007	2008	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	71907_07	Argos Doppler			75	2007-09-28	2008-10-06	10	1	12	2	2007	2008	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	71909_06	Argos Doppler			134	2006-10-29	2007-08-01	11	1	12	2	2006	2007	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	71911_07	Argos Doppler			95	2007-09-28	2008-08-29	12	1	12	2	2007	2008	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	71912_07	Argos Doppler			43	2007-09-28	2008-07-26	10	1	12	2	2007	2008	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	71913_07	Argos Doppler			98	2007-09-26	2008-06-24	10	1	12	2	2007	2008	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	71914_07	Argos Doppler			93	2007-09-26	2008-10-12	11	1	12	2	2007	2008	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	71915_07	Argos Doppler			86	2007-09-26	2008-08-21	12	1	12	2	2007	2008	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	71916_07	Argos Doppler			87	2007-09-26	2008-06-04	10	1	12	2	2007	2008	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	71917_07	Argos Doppler			32	2007-09-26	2008-07-28	6	5	12	2	2007	2008	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	71918_07	Argos Doppler			141	2007-09-26	2008-09-10	12	1	12	2	2007	2008	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	71920_07	Argos Doppler			89	2007-09-26	2008-09-10	9	1	12	2	2007	2008	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	71921_07	Argos Doppler			125	2007-09-28	2008-11-05	12	1	12	2	2007	2008	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	71922_07	Argos Doppler			63	2007-09-26	2008-06-10	10	1	12	2	2007	2008	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	71923_07	Argos Doppler			47	2007-09-26	2008-08-01	8	1	12	2	2007	2008	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	88054_11	Argos Doppler			94	2011-07-16	2012-10-04	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	88056_09	Argos Doppler			138	2009-04-07	2010-12-15	12	1	12	2	2009	2010	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	88057_09	Argos Doppler			114	2009-04-07	2010-08-13	12	1	12	2	2009	2010	77	695	698	697	2	5	42	45			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	88060_11	Argos Doppler			52	2011-07-15	2011-11-10	5	7	11	1	2011	2011	103	695	698	697	2	5	42	45			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	88063_09	Argos Doppler			106	2009-04-03	2010-06-30	12	1	12	2	2009	2010	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	88068_11	Argos Doppler			51	2011-07-16	2012-04-06	10	1	12	2	2011	2012	104	695	698	697	2	5	42	45			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	42561a	Argos Doppler	F	A	249	2003-08-01	2006-04-26	9	1	12	3	2003	2006	27	100							7		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	29776a	Argos Doppler	F	A	82	2004-06-26	2005-07-10	10	1	12	2	2004	2005	27	100								7	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	49810a	Argos Doppler	F	A	106	2004-07-15	2006-05-20	9	1	12	3	2004	2006	27	100								7	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	58866b	Argos Doppler	F	J	111	2006-07-23	2007-06-01	10	1	12	2	2006	2007	95	158								11	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	67762a	Argos Doppler	F	A	140	2006-11-04	2008-01-07	12	1	12	3	2006	2008	95	158								11	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	67763a	Argos Doppler	J		43	2006-09-10	2006-11-14	3	9	11	1	2006	2006	95	158								11	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	67764a	Argos Doppler	J		53	2006-09-07	2007-05-19	8	1	12	2	2006	2007	38	158								11	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	67766a	Argos Doppler	M	S	14	2006-08-05	2006-09-12	2	8	9	1	2006	2006	95	158								11	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	67767a	Argos Doppler	J		9	2006-08-12	2006-09-23	2	8	9	1	2006	2006	95	158								11	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	67767b	Argos Doppler	J		92	2007-11-09	2008-07-19	9	1	12	2	2007	2008	95	158								11	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	41115a	Argos Doppler	M	A	61	2007-11-28	2008-07-11	8	2	12	2	2007	2008	98	162								11	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	41116a	Argos Doppler	M	A	61	2007-11-30	2008-08-16	10	1	12	2	2007	2008	209	162								11	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	65539a	Argos Doppler	M	A	34	2006-10-24	2007-01-06	4	1	12	2	2006	2007	209	162								11	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	65540a	Argos Doppler	M	A	51	2007-07-19	2007-11-26	5	7	11	1	2007	2007	98	162								11	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	65541a	Argos Doppler	M	A	62	2006-10-20	2007-08-08	11	1	12	2	2006	2007	209	162								11	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	65542a	Argos Doppler	M	A	82	2007-10-17	2008-07-25	10	1	12	2	2007	2008	98	162								11	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	86447a	Argos Doppler	M	A	82	2009-10-08	2011-06-24	12	1	12	3	2009	2011	119	162								11	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	86448a	Argos Doppler	M	A	90	2009-10-04	2011-02-20	12	1	12	3	2009	2011	98	162								11	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	86449a	Argos Doppler	M	A	44	2009-11-09	2011-07-12	11	1	12	3	2009	2011	209	162								11	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	86450a	Argos Doppler	M	A	79	2009-10-26	2011-01-09	9	1	12	3	2009	2011	209	162								11	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	15245a	Argos Doppler	S		104	2003-02-02	2003-07-08	6	2	7	1	2003	2003	98	159								11	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	41118a	Argos Doppler	J		72	2008-03-13	2008-10-09	8	3	10	1	2008	2008	209	159								11	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	4238a	Argos Doppler	S		31	2002-11-25	2003-07-31	8	1	12	2	2002	2003	127	159								11	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	44785b	Argos Doppler	J		145	2007-03-07	2007-09-23	7	3	9	1	2007	2007	98	159								11	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	49162b	Argos Doppler	J		53	2007-03-25	2007-07-23	5	3	7	1	2007	2007	98	159								11	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	58868b	Argos Doppler	J		90	2007-03-06	2007-08-27	6	3	8	1	2007	2007	98	159								11	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	117766	Argos Doppler	S		50	2012-07-14	2012-11-29	5	7	11	1	2012	2012	95	169								11	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	117767	Argos Doppler	J		93	2012-06-29	2013-06-10	12	1	12	2	2012	2013	95	169								11	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	117768	Argos Doppler	J		13	2012-06-26	2012-07-22	2	6	7	1	2012	2012	95	169								11	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	117769	Argos Doppler	M	S	10	2012-07-06	2012-09-10	3	7	9	1	2012	2012	95	169								11	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	117770	Argos Doppler	J		17	2012-06-29	2012-08-06	3	6	8	1	2012	2012	95	169								11	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	29051a	Argos Doppler	F	A	379	2003-07-03	2005-04-16	12	1	12	3	2003	2005	218	362	357			13	20	21	24		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	29052a	Argos Doppler	F	A	284	2003-07-03	2005-04-08	12	1	12	3	2003	2005	218	362	357			13	20	21	24		

Species	Tag ID	Sensor	Sex	Age class	Days	Start date	End date	Months	Start month	End month	Years	Start year	End year	Start marID	CiteID1	CiteID2	CiteID3	CiteID4	ProvID1	ProvID2	ProvID3	ProvID4	ProvID5
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	29053a	Argos Doppler	F	A	178	2003-07-10	2004-05-07	11	1	12	2	2003	2004	218	362	357			13	20	21	24	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	29349a	Argos Doppler	F	A	100	2003-07-05	2004-01-18	7	1	12	2	2003	2004	218	362	357			13	20	21	24	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	64703a	Argos Doppler	F	A	288	2006-07-29	2007-06-20	12	1	12	2	2006	2007	218	362				13	20	21	24	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	64704a	Argos Doppler	F	A	391	2006-07-28	2007-09-25	12	1	12	2	2006	2007	218	362				13	20	21	24	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	67768a	Argos Doppler	F	A	146	2006-07-09	2007-10-27	10	1	12	2	2006	2007	218	362				13	20	21	24	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	67771a	Argos Doppler	F	A	131	2006-07-11	2007-07-15	11	1	12	2	2006	2007	218	362				13	20	21	24	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	75972a	Argos Doppler	F	A	399	2007-07-12	2009-12-13	12	1	12	3	2007	2009	218	362				13	20	21	24	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	75973a	Argos Doppler	F	A	729	2007-07-14	2010-02-01	12	1	12	4	2007	2010	218	362				13	20	21	24	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	75974a	Argos Doppler	F	A	116	2007-07-21	2007-12-19	6	7	12	1	2007	2007	218	362				13	20	21	24	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	75975a	Argos Doppler	F	A	387	2007-07-18	2008-12-22	12	1	12	2	2007	2008	218	362				13	20	21	24	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	49817a	Argos Doppler	F	A	90	2004-06-12	2004-10-11	5	6	10	1	2004	2004	218	362	357			13	20	21	24	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	49820a	Argos Doppler	F	A	448	2004-06-11	2005-12-23	12	1	12	2	2004	2005	218	362	357			13	20	21	24	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	49821a	Argos Doppler	F	A	241	2004-06-13	2005-09-30	12	1	12	2	2004	2005	218	362	357			13	20	21	24	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	52199a	Argos Doppler	F	A	103	2004-07-09	2005-04-30	10	1	12	2	2004	2005	218	362	357			13	20	21	24	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	85274a	Argos Doppler	F	A	64	2008-06-26	2008-11-05	6	6	11	1	2008	2008	218	362				13	20	21	24	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	85275a	Argos Doppler	F	A	373	2008-06-28	2009-09-23	12	1	12	2	2008	2009	218	362				13	20	21	24	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	85276a	Argos Doppler	F	A	329	2008-07-09	2010-04-08	12	1	12	3	2008	2010	218	362				13	20	21	24	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	85277a	Argos Doppler	F	A	304	2008-07-31	2009-07-21	12	1	12	2	2008	2009	218	362				13	20	21	24	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	57668a	Argos Doppler	F	A	114	2005-07-23	2006-08-07	11	1	11	2	2005	2006	218	362	357			13	20	21	24	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	57669a	Argos Doppler	F	A	437	2005-07-23	2007-01-07	12	1	12	3	2005	2007	218	362	357			13	20	21	24	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	57670a	Argos Doppler	F	A	357	2005-07-24	2007-01-16	12	1	12	3	2005	2007	218	362	357			13	20	21	24	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	57671a	Argos Doppler	F	A	320	2005-08-02	2006-11-10	12	1	12	2	2005	2006	218	362	357			13	20	21	24	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	4413a	Argos Doppler	F	A	31	2004-08-20	2004-11-03	4	8	11	1	2004	2004	26	358				8	21	24		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	4416a	Argos Doppler	F	A	49	2004-10-17	2005-02-23	5	1	12	2	2004	2005	26	358				8	21	24		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	49814a	Argos Doppler	F	A	12	2004-08-01	2004-08-23	1	8	8	1	2004	2004	26	358				8	21	24		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	49819a	Argos Doppler	F	A	238	2004-08-08	2006-03-27	12	1	12	3	2004	2006	26	358				8	21	24		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	49827a	Argos Doppler	F	A	183	2004-08-27	2005-07-07	12	1	12	2	2004	2005	26	358				8	21	24		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	49828a	Argos Doppler	F	A	177	2004-08-11	2005-04-27	9	1	12	2	2004	2005	26	358				8	21	24		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	49829a	Argos Doppler	F	A	95	2004-08-04	2005-04-22	9	1	12	2	2004	2005	26	358				8	21	24		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	49830a	Argos Doppler	F	A	281	2004-08-15	2005-08-26	12	1	12	2	2004	2005	26	358				8	21	24		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	52200a	Argos Doppler	M	A	34	2004-08-17	2004-11-07	4	8	11	1	2004	2004	26	358				8	21	24		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	52201a	Argos Doppler	F	A	28	2004-07-29	2004-09-22	3	7	9	1	2004	2004	26	358				8	21	24		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	34110a	Argos Doppler	F	A	124	2005-10-25	2006-09-12	12	1	12	2	2005	2006	184	358				8	21	24		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	34169a	Argos Doppler	F	A	19	2005-08-11	2005-11-09	4	8	11	1	2005	2005	26	358				8	21	24		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	57393a	Argos Doppler	F	A	60	2005-08-07	2006-03-09	7	1	12	2	2005	2006	26	358				8	21	24		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	118184a	Argos Doppler	F	A	142	2012-06-01	2012-12-30	7	6	12	1	2012	2012	42	130	307	845		8	21	54		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	118185	Argos Doppler	F	A	643	2012-05-31	2015-11-03	12	1	12	4	2012	2015	42	130	307	845		8	21	54		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	15340a	Argos Doppler	F	A	166	2002-06-09	2003-01-17	8	1	12	2	2002	2003	42	130	307	845		8	21	54		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	15414a	Argos Doppler	F	A	84	2002-07-14	2003-08-12	12	1	12	2	2002	2003	42	130	307	845		8	21	54		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	29034a	Argos Doppler	F	A	179	2003-07-23	2005-04-04	10	1	12	3	2003	2005	42	130	307	845		8	21	54		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	29049a	Argos Doppler	F	A	25	2004-06-09	2004-08-14	3	6	8	1	2004	2004	42	130	307	845		8	21	54		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	29050a	Argos Doppler	F	A	224	2003-06-16	2007-04-18	11	1	12	5	2003	2007	42	130	307	845		8	21	54		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	29358a	Argos Doppler	F	A	16	2001-07-11	2001-09-29	3	7	9	1	2001	2001	42	130	307	845		8	21	54		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	29359a	Argos Doppler	F	A	44	2001-06-23	2001-08-11	3	6	8	1	2001	2001	42	130	307	845		8	21	54		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	34214a	Argos Doppler	F	A	28	2006-06-30	2006-09-02	4	6	9	1	2006	2006	42	130	307	845		8	21	54		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	4206a	Argos Doppler	F	A	68	2002-07-13	2002-11-19	5	7	11	1	2002	2002	42	130	307	845		8	21	54		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	4242a	Argos Doppler	F	A	129	2002-07-08	2003-09-03	10	1	12	2	2002	2003	42	130	307	845		8	21	54		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	43755c	Argos Doppler	F	A	163	2012-06-05	2012-11-25	6	6	11	1	2012	2012	42	130	307	845		8	21	54		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	4406a	Argos Doppler	F	A	80	2002-08-05	2002-10-28	3	8	10	1	2002	2002	42	130	307	845		8	21	54		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	4407a	Argos Doppler	F	A	155	2002-07-27	2003-08-11	12	1	12	2	2002	2003	42	130	307	845		8	21	54		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	52813	Argos Doppler	F	A	878	2011-06-18	2016-12-14	12	1	12	6	2011	2016	42	130	307	845		8	21	54		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	52815a	Argos Doppler	F	A	311	2011-06-11	2013-05-01	12	1	12	3	2011	2013	42	130	307	845		8	21	54		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	52816a	Argos Doppler	F	A	219	2011-06-27	2012-07-30	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	42	130	307	845		8	21	54		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	52817a	Argos Doppler	F	A	77	2010-05-31	2013-01-04	8	1	12	3	2010	2013	42	130	307	845		8	21	54		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	52819a	Argos Doppler	F	A	419	2011-06-06	2012-08-18	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	42	130	307	845		8	21	54		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53182a	Argos Doppler	F	A	176	2006-06-22	2007-06-07	12	1	12	2	2006	2007	42	130	307	845		8	21	54		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53184a	Argos Doppler	F	A	150	2006-08-05	2007-06-29	11	1	12	2	2006	2007	42	130	307	845		8	21	54		

Species	Tag ID	Sensor	Sex	Age class	Days	Start date	End date	Months	Start month	End month	Years	Start year	End year	Start marID	CiteID1	CiteID2	CiteID3	CiteID4	ProvID1	ProvID2	ProvID3	ProvID4	ProvID5
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	57384a	Argos Doppler	F	A	70	2005-06-08	2006-01-04	7	1	11	2	2005	2006	42	130	307	845		8	21		54	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	57389a	Argos Doppler	F	A	113	2005-07-01	2005-11-15	5	7	11	1	2005	2005	42	130	307	845		8	21		54	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	57391a	Argos Doppler	F	A	5	2005-06-25	2005-06-30	1	6	6	1	2005	2005	42	130	307	845		8	21		54	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	68557a	Argos Doppler	F	A	68	2007-06-13	2008-02-23	7	1	12	2	2007	2008	42	130	307	845		8	21		54	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	68561a	Argos Doppler	F	A	96	2007-06-21	2007-12-03	7	6	12	1	2007	2007	42	130	307	845		8	21		54	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	77171	Argos Doppler	F	A	321	2008-07-18	2010-06-23	12	1	12	3	2008	2010	42	130	307	845		8	21		54	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	77172a	Argos Doppler	F	A	68	2009-07-16	2010-02-16	7	1	11	2	2009	2010	42	130	307	845		8	21		54	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	86390a	Argos Doppler	F	A	186	2009-05-08	2011-02-15	12	1	12	3	2009	2011	94	486				21	29			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	86391a	Argos Doppler	F	A	53	2009-06-09	2011-08-24	5	5	9	3	2009	2011	94	486				21	29			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	86392a	Argos Doppler	F	A	142	2008-07-19	2009-11-05	10	1	12	2	2008	2009	94	486				21	29			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	86393a	Argos Doppler	F	A	61	2009-02-06	2009-08-19	5	2	8	1	2009	2009	94	486				21	29			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	93698a	Argos Doppler	F	A	131	2009-07-15	2010-06-01	11	1	12	2	2009	2010	94	486				21	29			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	93700a	Argos Doppler	F	A	168	2009-07-05	2009-12-31	6	7	12	1	2009	2009	94	486				21	29			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	93701a	Argos Doppler	M	A	259	2010-04-30	2012-07-02	12	1	12	3	2010	2012	94	486				21	29			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	49818a	Argos Doppler	S		337	2004-07-13	2005-06-25	12	1	12	2	2004	2005	218	304				13	20		21	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LoggerheadTurtle_X1	Argos Doppler	J		417	2009-02-12	2010-07-19	12	1	12	2	2009	2010	109	314				22	9			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LoggerheadTurtle_X2	Argos Doppler	J		86	2009-01-13	2009-04-12	4	1	4	1	2009	2009	110	314				22	9			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LoggerheadTurtle_X3	Argos Doppler	J		144	2010-11-19	2011-04-22	6	1	12	2	2010	2011	110	314				22	9			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LoggerheadTurtle_X4	Argos Doppler	J		120	2010-11-20	2011-05-29	7	1	12	2	2010	2011	7	314				22	9			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LoggerheadTurtle_X5	Argos Doppler	J		128	2010-11-19	2011-04-02	6	1	12	2	2010	2011	110	314				22	9			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LoggerheadTurtle_X6	Argos Doppler	J		306	2011-11-26	2012-12-03	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	7	314				22	9			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	101205	Argos Doppler	S		45	2015-07-19	2015-11-16	5	7	11	1	2015	2015	134	963				23	30		50	60
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	137338	Argos Doppler	S		71	2014-05-23	2014-09-05	5	5	9	1	2014	2014	134	963				23	30		50	60
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	44362	Argos Doppler	S		42	2014-05-24	2014-08-04	4	5	8	1	2014	2014	134	963				23	30		50	60
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	23658	Argos Doppler	S		9	2004-07-04	2005-04-27	4	1	7	2	2004	2005	134	962				23	30		50	60
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	137339	Argos Doppler	S		101	2014-05-25	2014-10-23	6	5	10	1	2014	2014	134	963				23	30		50	60
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	101217b	Argos Doppler	S		7	2013-06-07	2013-06-28	1	6	6	1	2013	2013	100	387				27				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	108716a	Argos Doppler	M	A	82	2011-10-02	2012-04-21	7	1	12	2	2011	2012	95	388				27				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	108717a	Argos Doppler	F	A	153	2011-09-23	2012-04-01	8	1	12	2	2011	2012	100	524				27				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	113532a	Argos Doppler	M	A	127	2012-05-30	2012-12-17	8	5	12	1	2012	2012	100	388				27				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	113533a	Argos Doppler	J		60	2012-07-11	2013-02-11	8	1	12	2	2012	2013	118	398				27				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	122144a	Argos Doppler	F	A	120	2013-07-31	2014-04-07	10	1	12	2	2013	2014	212	394				27				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	122145a	Argos Doppler	F	A	61	2013-08-01	2013-12-18	5	8	12	1	2013	2013	212	394				27				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	122146a	Argos Doppler	S		205	2012-09-27	2013-09-14	12	1	12	2	2012	2013	100	388				27				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	128845a	Argos Doppler	F	A	119	2013-10-02	2014-05-18	8	1	12	2	2013	2014	100	387				27				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	128847	Argos Doppler	J		713	2014-10-09	2016-12-31	12	1	12	3	2014	2016	100	894				27				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	21079a	Argos Doppler	J		244	2006-05-01	2007-04-20	12	1	12	2	2006	2007	119	400				27				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	21079b	Argos Doppler	J		135	2008-07-25	2009-01-31	7	1	12	2	2008	2009	127	399				27				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	34298a	Argos Doppler	F	A	40	2011-07-08	2011-12-16	4	7	12	1	2011	2011	212	397				27				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	46524a	Argos Doppler	F	A	60	2010-07-25	2011-02-21	8	1	12	2	2010	2011	212	395				27				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	46525a	Argos Doppler	F	A	109	2011-07-10	2012-05-02	10	1	11	2	2011	2012	212	397				27				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	46526a	Argos Doppler	J		302	2010-10-20	2011-12-14	12	1	12	2	2010	2011	95	388				27				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60663a	Argos Doppler	M	A	104	2011-06-17	2011-10-16	5	6	10	1	2011	2011	100	388				27				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60664a	Argos Doppler	F	A	109	2010-07-07	2011-01-04	7	1	12	2	2010	2011	119	400				27				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60669a	Argos Doppler	F	A	270	2010-07-02	2011-07-13	12	1	12	2	2010	2011	209	393				27				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60670a	Argos Doppler	F	A	146	2010-07-06	2011-09-25	11	1	12	2	2010	2011	119	400				27				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60670b	Argos Doppler	M	A	27	2013-06-07	2013-08-14	3	6	8	1	2013	2013	100	387				27				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60671a	Argos Doppler	F	A	33	2010-07-06	2011-02-15	5	1	12	2	2010	2011	119	400				27				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60671b	Argos Doppler	S		4	2013-06-09	2013-06-20	1	6	6	1	2013	2013	100	387				27				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	61809	Argos Doppler	A		171	2006-10-25	2007-05-03	8	1	12	2	2006	2007	100	524	390			27				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	78264a	Argos Doppler	S		206	2008-07-25	2009-03-13	9	1	12	2	2008	2009	127	399				27				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	95128a	Argos Doppler	F	S	164	2009-10-19	2010-08-27	11	1	12	2	2009	2010	100	524				27				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	95130a	Argos Doppler	F	A	15	2009-07-22	2009-08-08	2	7	8	1	2009	2009	119	400				27				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	108905a	Argos Doppler	F	A	263	2011-10-01	2013-07-20	12	1	12	3	2011	2013	212	447	813			28	55			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	108906a	Argos Doppler	F	A	16	2011-10-01	2012-07-03	6	1	12	2	2011	2012	212	447	813			28	55			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	108907a	Argos Doppler	S		87	2011-10-02	2012-02-02	5	1	12	2	2011	2012	212	447	813			28	55			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	108908a	Argos Doppler	M		44	2011-10-02	2012-07-28	9	1	11	2	2011	2012	212	447	813			28	55			

Species	Tag ID	Sensor	Sex	Age class	Days	Start date	End date	Months	Start month	End month	Years	Start year	End year	Start marID	CiteID1	CiteID2	CiteID3	CiteID4	ProvID1	ProvID2	ProvID3	ProvID4	ProvID5
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	108909a	Argos Doppler		S	8	2011-10-03	2011-11-27	2	10	11	1	2011	2011	212	447	813			28	55			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	120041a	Argos Doppler	F		54	2012-08-28	2012-11-19	4	8	11	1	2012	2012	63	447	813			28	55			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	120043a	Argos Doppler			47	2012-08-26	2014-01-31	7	1	12	3	2012	2014	212	447	813			28	55			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	120044a	Argos Doppler			44	2012-08-26	2013-08-28	7	1	12	2	2012	2013	212	447	813			28	55			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	148602	Argos Doppler	F	A	69	2015-10-03	2016-03-18	6	1	12	2	2015	2016	212	447	813			28	55			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	148604	Argos Doppler	F	A	220	2015-10-04	2016-10-19	12	1	12	2	2015	2016	212	447	813			28	55			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	108056	Argos Doppler			143	2011-11-22	2012-09-11	10	1	12	2	2011	2012	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	148883	Argos Doppler			129	2015-09-12	2016-02-15	6	1	12	2	2015	2016	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	175711	Argos Doppler			30	2018-06-23	2018-07-26	2	6	7	1	2018	2018	218	50				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	MMSC-09-123	Argos Doppler			188	2010-09-28	2012-09-11	11	1	12	3	2010	2012	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	NAIB1240CC	Argos Doppler			136	2013-10-21	2014-04-20	7	1	12	2	2013	2014	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQR201301	Argos Doppler			127	2013-05-23	2013-09-26	5	5	9	1	2013	2013	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQR201302	Argos Doppler; Global Positioning System			364	2013-05-23	2014-09-16	10	1	12	2	2013	2014	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQR201303	Argos Doppler; Global Positioning System			310	2013-05-23	2014-04-16	12	1	12	2	2013	2014	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQR201307	Argos Doppler			55	2013-06-27	2013-12-25	7	6	12	1	2013	2013	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQR201309	Argos Doppler			38	2013-06-13	2013-07-27	2	6	7	1	2013	2013	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQR201312	Argos Doppler; Global Positioning System			136	2013-07-22	2014-01-16	7	1	12	2	2013	2014	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQR201313	Argos Doppler			18	2013-09-19	2013-10-21	2	9	10	1	2013	2013	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQR201315	Argos Doppler; Global Positioning System			312	2013-09-08	2014-08-21	12	1	12	2	2013	2014	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQR201318	Argos Doppler; Global Positioning System			9	2013-09-13	2013-09-21	1	9	9	1	2013	2013	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQR201401	Argos Doppler			136	2014-06-05	2014-10-19	5	6	10	1	2014	2014	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQR201501	Argos Doppler			56	2015-05-17	2015-09-04	5	5	9	1	2015	2015	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQR201502	Argos Doppler			21	2015-05-16	2015-06-24	2	5	6	1	2015	2015	218	50				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQR201506	Argos Doppler			25	2015-05-31	2015-07-18	3	5	7	1	2015	2015	218	50				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQR201508	Argos Doppler			16	2015-07-02	2015-07-25	1	7	7	1	2015	2015	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQR201510	Argos Doppler			25	2015-07-02	2015-07-30	1	7	7	1	2015	2015	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQR201512	Argos Doppler			31	2015-08-06	2015-09-05	2	8	9	1	2015	2015	218	50				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQS20092046	Argos Doppler			61	2009-07-14	2009-09-29	3	7	9	1	2009	2009	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQS20092050	Argos Doppler			24	2009-08-14	2009-09-14	2	8	9	1	2009	2009	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQS20102131	Argos Doppler; Global Positioning System			92	2011-06-28	2011-09-28	4	6	9	1	2011	2011	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQS20102146	Global Positioning System			22	2011-06-28	2011-07-19	2	6	7	1	2011	2011	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQS20112004	Argos Doppler; Global Positioning System			207	2011-06-30	2012-02-05	9	1	12	2	2011	2012	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQS20112013	Argos Doppler; Global Positioning System			152	2011-10-19	2012-04-06	7	1	12	2	2011	2012	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQS20112019	Argos Doppler; Global Positioning System			164	2011-08-02	2012-01-24	6	1	12	2	2011	2012	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQS20112059	Argos Doppler; Global Positioning System			413	2012-07-14	2013-12-01	12	1	12	2	2012	2013	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQS20122090	Argos Doppler			36	2012-07-28	2012-09-18	3	7	9	1	2012	2012	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQS20122096	Argos Doppler			118	2012-09-08	2013-05-16	9	1	12	2	2012	2013	218	506				14	31			

Species	Tag ID	Sensor	Sex	Age class	Days	Start date	End date	Months	Start month	End month	Years	Start year	End year	Start marID	CiteID1	CiteID2	CiteID3	CiteID4	ProvID1	ProvID2	ProvID3	ProvID4	ProvID5
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQS20122108	Argos Doppler			106	2012-10-08	2013-06-07	9	1	12	2	2012	2013	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQS20122163	Argos Doppler			344	2013-08-28	2014-09-06	12	1	12	2	2013	2014	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQS20122176	Argos Doppler; Global Positioning System			55	2013-07-06	2013-09-13	3	7	9	1	2013	2013	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQS20122177	Argos Doppler; Global Positioning System			147	2013-06-16	2013-11-11	6	6	11	1	2013	2013	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQS20132003	Argos Doppler; Global Positioning System			146	2013-06-06	2013-12-10	7	6	12	1	2013	2013	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQS20132005	Argos Doppler; Global Positioning System			336	2013-06-06	2014-06-10	12	1	12	2	2013	2014	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQS20132006	Argos Doppler			93	2013-06-16	2013-10-01	5	6	10	1	2013	2013	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQS20132052	Argos Doppler			13	2014-09-08	2014-10-13	2	9	10	1	2014	2014	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQS20132086	Argos Doppler			86	2013-10-22	2014-06-28	9	1	12	2	2013	2014	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQS20132102	Argos Doppler			61	2013-10-22	2014-04-26	7	1	12	2	2013	2014	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQS20132106	Argos Doppler			236	2013-09-29	2014-09-09	12	1	12	2	2013	2014	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQS20132126	Argos Doppler			193	2013-11-03	2014-05-20	7	1	12	2	2013	2014	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQS20132141	Argos Doppler			52	2013-11-27	2014-07-10	9	1	12	2	2013	2014	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQS20132219	Argos Doppler			291	2014-06-14	2015-09-09	8	4	11	2	2014	2015	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQS20132225	Argos Doppler			168	2014-06-14	2015-01-20	8	1	12	2	2014	2015	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQS20142147	Argos Doppler			169	2014-10-21	2015-08-24	10	1	12	2	2014	2015	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQS20142177	Argos Doppler			16	2015-03-18	2015-04-11	2	3	4	1	2015	2015	218	50				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VAQS20142235	Argos Doppler			248	2015-03-18	2016-01-19	11	1	12	2	2015	2016	218	50				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	VIMS_MT-06-10-01	Argos Doppler			257	2007-06-29	2008-11-18	12	1	12	2	2007	2008	218	506				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	YorkSpi07-30-15-Cc	Argos Doppler			257	2007-06-29	2008-11-18	12	1	12	2	2007	2008	218	50				14	31			
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60768	Argos Doppler	F	A	215	2006-01-25	2007-09-28	12	1	12	2	2006	2007	19	542				32				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60769	Argos Doppler	F	A	274	2006-01-27	2008-07-27	12	1	12	3	2006	2008	19	542				32				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60770	Argos Doppler	F	A	480	2006-02-01	2009-08-13	12	1	12	4	2006	2009	19	542				32				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60771	Argos Doppler	F	A	493	2006-02-03	2009-07-19	12	1	12	4	2006	2009	19	542				32				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60772	Argos Doppler	F	A	102	2006-02-28	2007-04-19	11	1	12	2	2006	2007	19	542				32				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60773	Argos Doppler	F	A	106	2006-02-27	2007-09-07	12	1	12	2	2006	2007	19	542				32				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60774	Argos Doppler	F	A	501	2006-02-19	2009-03-03	12	1	12	4	2006	2009	19	542				32				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60775	Argos Doppler	F	A	254	2006-02-22	2009-09-11	12	1	12	4	2006	2009	19	542				32				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60776	Argos Doppler	F	A	162	2006-02-23	2007-07-11	12	1	12	2	2006	2007	19	542				32				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60777	Argos Doppler	F	A	292	2006-03-05	2008-06-08	12	1	12	3	2006	2008	19	542				32				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	Ellenia	Argos Doppler	F	A	1223	2011-07-08	2015-09-08	12	1	12	5	2011	2015	96	575				33			39	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	Eraclia	Argos Doppler	F	A	403	2013-07-24	2014-10-05	12	1	12	2	2013	2014	96	575				33			39	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	Esperia	Argos Doppler	F	A	28	2009-07-30	2009-09-25	3	7	9	1	2009	2009	96	575				33			39	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	Isodia	Argos Doppler	F	A	336	2011-07-10	2012-07-05	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	96	575				33			39	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	Kalabria	Argos Doppler	F	A	585	2010-07-15	2012-12-22	12	1	12	3	2010	2012	96	575				33			39	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	Lacinia	Argos Doppler	F	A	929	2010-07-04	2013-07-30	12	1	12	4	2010	2013	96	575				33			39	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	Zefferia	Argos Doppler	F	A	72	2009-07-16	2010-05-25	6	4	10	2	2009	2010	96	575				33			39	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	137403a	Argos Doppler	J		5	2015-04-11	2015-04-15	1	4	4	1	2015	2015	100	519				33				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	137404a	Argos Doppler	J		5	2015-08-06	2015-08-14	1	8	8	1	2015	2015	100	519				33				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	142188a	Argos Doppler	J		44	2014-10-11	2014-12-01	3	10	12	1	2014	2014	100	519				33				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	142927a	Argos Doppler	S		26	2015-04-11	2015-06-18	3	4	6	1	2015	2015	100	524				33				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	39103	Argos Doppler	J		56	2017-09-29	2018-02-07	6	1	12	2	2017	2018	100	519				33				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	41230a	Argos Doppler	F	A	218	2004-11-03	2005-08-24	10	1	12	2	2004	2005	95	525				33				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	49158a	Argos Doppler	F	A	134	2004-11-04	2005-07-27	9	1	12	2	2004	2005	95	525				33				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	40658a	Argos Doppler	M	A	69	2003-10-03	2003-12-23	3	10	12	1	2003	2003	95	568				33				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	107687a	Argos Doppler	F	A	308	2011-06-04	2013-01-24	10	1	12	3	2011	2013	100	524				33				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	137404	Argos Doppler	M	S	69	2016-06-05	2016-08-18	3	6	8	1	2016	2016	100	524				33				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	18262b	Argos Doppler	J		71	2007-05-10	2007-08-19	4	5	8	1	2007	2007	100	567				33				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	40664a	Argos Doppler	J		20	2010-06-19	2010-07-09	2	6	7	1	2010	2010	100	567				33				

Species	Tag ID	Sensor	Sex	Age class	Days	Start date	End date	Months	Start month	End month	Years	Start year	End year	Start marID	CiteID1	CiteID2	CiteID3	CiteID4	ProvID1	ProvID2	ProvID3	ProvID4	ProvID5	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	41231b	Argos Doppler	F	A	193	2005-07-19	2006-06-23	12	1	12	2	2005	2006	100	525								33	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	47059a	Argos Doppler	J	J	14	2006-05-28	2006-07-10	3	5	7	1	2006	2006	100	520									33
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	58868a	Argos Doppler	J	J	50	2005-07-22	2005-11-19	5	7	11	1	2005	2005	100	567									33
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	67765a	Argos Doppler	F	S	45	2008-04-20	2008-09-03	5	4	9	1	2008	2008	100	524									33
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	17433a	Argos Doppler	J	J	38	2006-02-03	2006-06-28	5	2	6	1	2006	2006	162	537									2 34
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	17435a	Argos Doppler	J	J	72	2007-02-08	2007-10-11	9	2	10	1	2007	2007	162	537									2 34
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	19242a	Argos Doppler	J	J	7	2007-01-17	2007-01-23	1	1	1	1	2007	2007	162	537									2 34
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	21128a	Argos Doppler	J	J	25	2007-01-14	2007-03-01	3	1	3	1	2007	2007	162	537									2 34
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	21138a	Argos Doppler	J	J	22	2007-01-14	2007-03-04	3	1	3	1	2007	2007	162	537									2 34
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	21143a	Argos Doppler	J	J	18	2007-01-15	2007-04-01	4	1	4	1	2007	2007	162	537									2 34
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	22175a	Argos Doppler	J	J	18	2003-04-14	2003-10-31	6	4	10	1	2003	2003	28	537									2 34
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	40654a	Argos Doppler	J	J	33	2005-07-15	2006-02-17	8	1	12	2	2005	2006	162	537									2 34
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	42971a	Argos Doppler	J	J	24	2007-02-05	2007-05-22	3	2	5	1	2007	2007	162	537									2 34
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	42997a	Argos Doppler	J	J	71	2005-04-07	2006-01-12	10	1	12	2	2005	2006	162	537									2 34
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	5154b	Argos Doppler	J	J	14	2006-02-13	2006-05-29	4	2	5	1	2006	2006	162	537									2 34
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	5157a	Argos Doppler	J	J	32	2003-10-24	2004-03-08	6	1	12	2	2003	2004	162	537									2 34
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	5159a	Argos Doppler	J	J	20	2004-01-03	2004-03-05	3	1	3	1	2004	2004	162	537									2 34
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	5395b	Argos Doppler	J	J	38	2006-11-15	2007-02-11	4	1	12	2	2006	2007	162	537									2 34
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	37116	Argos Doppler	J	J	7	2003-10-11	2004-07-21	3	3	10	2	2003	2004	218	559	562	558							38 46
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	37117	Argos Doppler	J	J	95	2002-10-01	2003-05-28	8	1	12	2	2002	2003	218	559	562	558							38 46
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	37118	Argos Doppler	J	J	128	2002-09-29	2003-04-01	8	1	12	2	2002	2003	218	559	562	558							38 46
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	37120	Argos Doppler	J	J	44	2003-10-12	2004-04-12	7	1	12	2	2003	2004	218	559	562	558							38 46
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	37121	Argos Doppler	J	J	114	2003-11-22	2004-08-26	10	1	12	2	2003	2004	218	559	562	558							38 46
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	37122	Argos Doppler	J	J	8	2003-11-17	2004-01-31	3	1	12	2	2003	2004	218	559	562	558							38 46
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	37192	Argos Doppler	J	J	130	2003-10-18	2004-07-20	10	1	12	2	2003	2004	218	559	562	558							38 46
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	37193	Argos Doppler	J	J	75	2003-10-19	2004-05-26	8	1	12	2	2003	2004	218	559	562	558							38 46
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	37194	Argos Doppler	J	J	100	2003-11-13	2004-08-18	10	1	12	2	2003	2004	218	559	562	558							38 46
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	37199	Argos Doppler	J	J	286	2002-10-01	2003-08-30	11	1	12	2	2002	2003	218	559	562	558							38 46
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	37200	Argos Doppler	J	J	182	2002-09-14	2004-07-03	12	1	12	3	2002	2004	218	559	562	558							38 46
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	37201	Argos Doppler	J	J	176	2002-10-04	2003-05-21	8	1	12	2	2002	2003	218	559	562	558							38 46
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	37202	Argos Doppler	J	J	111	2002-09-30	2003-03-02	7	1	12	2	2002	2003	218	559	562	558							38 46
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	37208	Argos Doppler	J	J	150	2002-10-06	2003-09-03	10	1	12	2	2002	2003	218	559	562	558							38 46
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	37213	Argos Doppler	J	J	120	2003-10-17	2004-04-24	7	1	12	2	2003	2004	218	559	562	558							38 46
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	37214	Argos Doppler	J	J	332	2003-10-29	2004-11-14	12	1	12	2	2003	2004	218	559	562	558							38 46
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	37217	Argos Doppler	J	J	16	2003-10-19	2004-02-15	5	1	12	2	2003	2004	218	559	562	558							38 46
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	37218	Argos Doppler	J	J	98	2003-10-15	2004-06-15	9	1	12	2	2003	2004	218	559	562	558							38 46
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	37219	Argos Doppler	J	J	23	2003-10-29	2004-11-23	3	1	11	2	2003	2004	218	559	562	558							38 46
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	37224	Argos Doppler	J	J	318	2003-05-31	2004-05-18	12	1	12	2	2003	2004	218	559	562	558							38 46
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	37225	Argos Doppler	J	J	57	2003-11-28	2004-05-06	7	1	12	2	2003	2004	218	559	562	558							38 46
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53957	Argos Doppler	J	J	140	2004-11-07	2005-09-13	11	1	12	2	2004	2005	218	559	562	558							38 46
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53959	Argos Doppler	J	J	281	2006-09-04	2007-06-11	10	1	12	2	2006	2007	218	561									38 46
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53962	Argos Doppler	J	J	57	2004-11-11	2005-07-10	9	1	12	2	2004	2005	218	559	562	558							38 46
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53963	Argos Doppler	J	J	62	2004-11-06	2005-05-22	7	1	12	2	2004	2005	218	559	562	558							38 46
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53964	Argos Doppler	J	J	81	2004-11-11	2005-11-15	11	1	12	2	2004	2005	218	559	562	558							38 46
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53965	Argos Doppler	J	J	242	2006-09-04	2007-05-08	9	1	12	2	2006	2007	218	561									38 46
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	53966	Argos Doppler	J	J	130	2004-11-06	2005-07-22	9	1	12	2	2004	2005	218	559	562	558							38 46
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	107883	Argos Doppler	F	A	10	2011-07-19	2011-08-10	2	7	8	1	2011	2011	61	654	655	652							43
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	107886	Argos Doppler	F	A	58	2011-07-11	2011-12-06	5	7	12	1	2011	2011	61	654	655	652							43
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	107888	Argos Doppler	F	A	81	2011-08-13	2011-12-20	5	8	12	1	2011	2011	61	654	655	652							43
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	107890	Argos Doppler	F	A	47	2011-07-28	2011-12-08	6	7	12	1	2011	2011	61	654	655	652							43
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	107891	Argos Doppler	F	A	113	2011-07-20	2012-01-28	7	1	12	2	2011	2012	61	654	655	652							43
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	107893	Argos Doppler	F	A	137	2011-07-27	2012-03-31	9	1	12	2	2011	2012	61	654	655	652							43
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	107894	Argos Doppler	F	A	108	2011-08-11	2011-12-15	5	8	12	1	2011	2011	61	654	655	652							43
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	107895	Argos Doppler	F	A	129	2011-07-08	2012-01-25	7	1	12	2	2011	2012	61	654	655	652							43
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	107896	Argos Doppler	F	A	133	2011-07-10	2011-12-20	6	7	12	1	2011	2011	63	654	655	652							43
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	107897	Argos Doppler	F	A	58	2011-07-12	2011-09-20	3	7	9	1	2011	2011	61	654	655	652							43
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	107898	Argos Doppler	F	A	67	2011-07-11	2012-03-17	6	2	11	2	2011	2012	61	654	655	652							43

Species	Tag ID	Sensor	Sex	Age class	Days	Start date	End date	Months	Start month	End month	Years	Start year	End year	Start marID	CiteID1	CiteID2	CiteID3	CiteID4	ProvID1	ProvID2	ProvID3	ProvID4	ProvID5
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	107900	Argos Doppler	F	A	124	2011-07-26	2012-01-21	7	1	12	2	2011	2012	61	654	655	652						43
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	11317	Argos Doppler	F	A	61	2011-07-27	2011-09-28	3	7	9	1	2011	2011	61	654	655	652						43
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	11414	Argos Doppler	F	A	67	2011-07-22	2011-11-14	5	7	11	1	2011	2011	61	654	655	652						43
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	11509	Argos Doppler	F	A	10	2011-07-16	2011-08-12	2	7	8	1	2011	2011	61	654	655	652						43
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	37794	Argos Doppler	F	A	49	2010-08-15	2010-11-14	4	8	11	1	2010	2010	119	654	655	652						43
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	37796	Argos Doppler	M	A	102	2011-06-21	2011-10-17	5	6	10	1	2011	2011	61	656								43
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	37799	Argos Doppler	F	A	35	2010-08-14	2011-01-16	6	1	12	2	2010	2011	63	654	655	652						43
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	37801	Argos Doppler	F	A	19	2010-08-17	2010-09-27	2	8	9	1	2010	2010	119	654	655	652						43
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	37802	Argos Doppler	F	A	84	2010-08-09	2011-01-06	6	1	12	2	2010	2011	119	654	655	652						43
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	133612	Argos Doppler	F	S	123	2014-02-28	2014-07-26	6	2	7	1	2014	2014	171	682								44
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	57362a	Argos Doppler	F	A	40	2005-07-06	2006-07-13	12	1	12	2	2005	2006	61	544								47
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	28082a	Argos Doppler	F	A	94	2003-05-14	2004-06-24	10	1	12	2	2003	2004	62	725								47
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	127971a	Argos Doppler	M	A	183	2013-06-25	2015-06-23	12	1	12	3	2013	2015	62	725								47
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	127972a	Argos Doppler	M	S	293	2013-06-24	2015-11-20	12	1	12	3	2013	2015	62	725								47
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	127972b	Argos Doppler	M	S	42	2016-03-19	2017-03-20	10	1	12	2	2016	2017	62	725								47
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	127973a	Argos Doppler	F	S	24	2013-06-25	2013-08-25	3	6	8	1	2013	2013	62	725								47
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	127974a	Argos Doppler	F	S	421	2013-06-27	2015-05-17	12	1	12	3	2013	2015	62	725								47
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	127975a	Argos Doppler	M	S	106	2013-08-04	2014-08-30	9	1	12	2	2013	2014	62	725								47
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	127976a	Argos Doppler	S	S	129	2013-06-17	2014-11-14	10	1	12	2	2013	2014	62	725								47
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	127977a	Argos Doppler	M	A	140	2013-06-19	2016-03-25	12	1	12	4	2013	2016	62	725								47
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	37469a	Argos Doppler	F	A	37	2006-05-14	2006-08-04	4	5	8	1	2006	2006	145	722								47
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	66306a	Argos Doppler	F	A	67	2006-05-22	2006-12-11	6	5	12	1	2006	2006	145	722								47
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	66307a	Argos Doppler	F	A	125	2006-06-08	2007-03-22	8	1	12	2	2006	2007	145	722								47
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	66308a	Argos Doppler	F	A	174	2006-05-14	2007-01-19	9	1	12	2	2006	2007	145	722								47
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	66309a	Argos Doppler	F	A	83	2006-05-17	2006-12-18	7	5	12	1	2006	2006	145	722								47
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	66310a	Argos Doppler	F	A	80	2006-05-26	2006-11-16	7	5	11	1	2006	2006	145	722								47
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	66311a	Argos Doppler	F	A	78	2006-05-16	2007-02-21	9	1	11	2	2006	2007	145	722								47
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	66312a	Argos Doppler	F	A	123	2006-05-18	2006-12-29	8	5	12	1	2006	2006	145	722								47
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	66313a	Argos Doppler	F	A	472	2006-05-17	2008-03-12	12	1	12	3	2006	2008	145	722								47
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	66314a	Argos Doppler	F	A	59	2006-05-30	2006-12-25	8	5	12	1	2006	2006	145	722								47
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_01	Global Positioning System	M	A	41	2007-05-08	2007-06-24	2	5	6	1	2007	2007	62	792								51
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_02	Global Positioning System	M	A	29	2007-05-10	2007-06-30	2	5	6	1	2007	2007	62	792								51
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_04	Global Positioning System	M	A	13	2007-05-11	2007-05-26	1	5	5	1	2007	2007	62	792								51
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_05	Global Positioning System	M	A	31	2007-05-08	2007-08-03	3	5	8	1	2007	2007	62	792								51
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_06	Global Positioning System	M	A	490	2008-05-03	2009-10-05	12	1	12	2	2008	2009	62	792								51
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_07	Global Positioning System	M	A	394	2008-05-03	2009-08-12	12	1	12	2	2008	2009	62	792								51
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_08	Global Positioning System	M	A	323	2008-05-04	2009-07-10	12	1	12	2	2008	2009	62	792								51
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_09	Global Positioning System	M	A	150	2009-05-05	2009-10-28	6	5	10	1	2009	2009	62	792								51
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_10	Global Positioning System	M	A	106	2009-05-03	2009-09-17	5	5	9	1	2009	2009	62	792								51
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_11	Global Positioning System	M	A	32	2009-05-08	2009-07-05	3	5	7	1	2009	2009	62	792								51
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_12	Global Positioning System	F	A	34	2009-05-23	2009-10-11	6	5	10	1	2009	2009	62	792								51
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_13	Global Positioning System	F	A	174	2009-05-03	2010-08-06	10	1	11	2	2009	2010	62	792								51
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_14	Global Positioning System	F	A	45	2009-05-02	2009-07-12	3	5	7	1	2009	2009	62	792								51

Species	Tag ID	Sensor	Sex	Age class	Days	Start date	End date	Months	Start month	End month	Years	Start year	End year	Start marID	CiteID1	CiteID2	CiteID3	CiteID4	ProvID1	ProvID2	ProvID3	ProvID4	ProvID5	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_15	Global Positioning System	M	A	356	2009-05-08	2010-05-11	12	1	12	2	2009	2010	62	792					51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_16	Global Positioning System	M	A	342	2009-05-07	2010-05-03	12	1	12	2	2009	2010	62	792					51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_17	Global Positioning System	M	A	326	2010-05-08	2011-05-05	12	1	12	2	2010	2011	62	792					51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_18	Global Positioning System	M	A	133	2010-05-03	2010-09-22	5	5	9	1	2010	2010	62	792					51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_19	Global Positioning System	M	A	378	2010-05-03	2011-09-03	11	1	11	2	2010	2011	62	792					51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_20	Global Positioning System	M	A	155	2010-05-03	2011-06-14	9	4	12	2	2010	2011	62	792					51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_21	Global Positioning System	M	A	80	2011-05-04	2011-08-05	4	5	8	1	2011	2011	62	792					51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_22	Global Positioning System	M	A	136	2011-05-06	2011-09-27	5	5	9	1	2011	2011	62	792					51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_23	Global Positioning System	M	A	95	2011-05-08	2011-08-14	4	5	8	1	2011	2011	62	792					51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_24	Global Positioning System	M	A	249	2011-05-07	2012-03-31	11	1	12	2	2011	2012	62	792					51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_25	Global Positioning System	M	A	345	2011-05-09	2012-05-06	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	62	792					51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_26	Global Positioning System	M	A	353	2011-05-13	2012-05-05	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	62	792					51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_27	Global Positioning System	M	A	80	2011-05-14	2011-08-08	4	5	8	1	2011	2011	62	792					51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_28	Global Positioning System	M	A	92	2012-05-05	2012-08-05	4	5	8	1	2012	2012	62	792					51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_29	Global Positioning System	M	A	451	2012-05-06	2013-08-12	12	1	12	2	2012	2013	62	792					51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_30	Global Positioning System	M	A	197	2012-05-12	2013-01-24	9	1	12	2	2012	2013	62	792					51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_31	Global Positioning System	M	A	312	2012-05-06	2013-10-20	12	1	12	2	2012	2013	62	792					51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_32	Global Positioning System	M	A	197	2012-05-07	2013-08-29	11	1	12	2	2012	2013	62	792					51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_33	Global Positioning System	M	A	216	2012-05-15	2014-01-12	12	1	12	3	2012	2014	62	792					51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_34	Global Positioning System	M	A	216	2012-05-07	2014-01-12	11	1	12	3	2012	2014	62	792					51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_35	Global Positioning System	M	A	52	2008-05-15	2008-07-20	3	5	7	1	2008	2008	62	792					51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_36	Global Positioning System	M	A	32	2008-05-09	2008-06-17	2	5	6	1	2008	2008	62	792					51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_37	Global Positioning System	F	A	135	2008-05-15	2009-01-07	9	1	12	2	2008	2009	62	792					51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_38	Global Positioning System	M	A	103	2008-06-10	2009-04-15	11	1	12	2	2008	2009	62	792					51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_39	Global Positioning System	M	A	30	2009-05-02	2009-06-16	2	5	6	1	2009	2009	62	792					51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_40	Global Positioning System	F	A	99	2008-01-02	2009-02-27	8	1	12	2	2008	2009	38	792					51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_41	Global Positioning System	F	A	47	2008-05-24	2008-08-19	4	5	8	1	2008	2008	62	792					51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_42	Global Positioning System	F	A	128	2008-05-24	2009-02-20	10	1	12	2	2008	2009	62	792					51				

Species	Tag ID	Sensor	Sex	Age class	Days	Start date	End date	Months	Start month	End month	Years	Start year	End year	Start marID	CiteID1	CiteID2	CiteID3	CiteID4	ProvID1	ProvID2	ProvID3	ProvID4	ProvID5
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_43	Global Positioning System	F	A	11	2009-09-13	2009-09-27	1	9	9	1	2009	2009	61	792				51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_44	Global Positioning System	M	A	45	2009-05-09	2009-07-23	3	5	7	1	2009	2009	62	792				51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_46	Global Positioning System	F	A	17	2009-09-26	2009-10-14	2	9	10	1	2009	2009	38	792				51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_47	Global Positioning System	F	A	65	2009-05-05	2009-09-27	5	5	9	1	2009	2009	62	792				51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_48	Global Positioning System	F	A	45	2009-07-02	2009-10-14	4	7	10	1	2009	2009	62	792				51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_49	Global Positioning System	F	A	18	2009-07-03	2009-10-12	4	7	10	1	2009	2009	62	792				51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_50	Global Positioning System	F	A	26	2009-07-02	2009-08-31	2	7	8	1	2009	2009	62	792				51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_51	Global Positioning System	F	A	52	2009-07-31	2009-10-14	4	7	10	1	2009	2009	95	792				51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_52	Global Positioning System	F	A	6	2009-08-07	2009-08-13	1	8	8	1	2009	2009	62	792				51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_53	Global Positioning System	M	A	40	2010-05-09	2010-11-09	5	5	11	1	2010	2010	62	792				51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_54	Global Positioning System	M	A	84	2010-05-11	2011-03-22	11	1	12	2	2010	2011	62	792				51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_55	Global Positioning System	M	A	22	2010-05-10	2011-04-02	4	4	7	2	2010	2011	62	792				51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	LogTurtle_56	Global Positioning System	M	A	244	2010-05-09	2011-01-15	9	1	12	2	2010	2011	62	792				51				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60528	Argos Doppler	J		599	2006-06-10	2008-07-07	12	1	12	3	2006	2008	193	417	909			57				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60529a	Argos Doppler	J		100	2006-06-14	2006-11-02	6	6	11	1	2006	2006	193	417	909			57				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60530	Argos Doppler	J		454	2006-07-01	2008-06-30	12	1	12	3	2006	2008	193	417				57				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60531a	Argos Doppler	J		199	2006-11-05	2007-08-09	10	1	12	2	2006	2007	193	417				57				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60532	Argos Doppler	J		247	2006-12-02	2009-09-17	12	1	12	4	2006	2009	193	417				57				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60533	Argos Doppler	J		92	2006-03-29	2006-07-17	5	3	7	1	2006	2006	193	417	909			57				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60534	Argos Doppler	J		105	2006-03-29	2006-10-13	8	3	10	1	2006	2006	193	417	909			57				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60535	Argos Doppler	J		166	2006-04-06	2006-11-20	8	4	11	1	2006	2006	193	417	909			57				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60536	Argos Doppler	J		159	2006-03-31	2006-12-19	10	3	12	1	2006	2006	193	417	909			57				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60537	Argos Doppler	J		133	2006-06-08	2007-03-05	10	1	12	2	2006	2007	193	417	909			57				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60523b	Argos Doppler	M	A	170	2006-05-14	2007-10-19	11	1	12	2	2006	2007	26	416	910			57				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60524a	Argos Doppler	M	A	210	2006-06-02	2007-04-28	11	1	12	2	2006	2007	26	416	910			57				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	60525a	Argos Doppler	F	A	466	2006-08-11	2008-04-03	12	1	12	3	2006	2008	26	416				57				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	2340	Argos Doppler	J		32	2000-06-25	2000-09-05	4	6	9	1	2000	2000	168	896				12		57		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	2367	Argos Doppler	J		70	1999-11-05	2000-03-23	5	1	12	2	1999	2000	193	896	909			12		57		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	2393	Argos Doppler	J		141	1999-11-04	2000-08-08	10	1	12	2	1999	2000	193	896	909			12		57		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	2433	Argos Doppler	J		125	1999-11-01	2000-05-25	7	1	12	2	1999	2000	193	896	909			12		57		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	2918	Argos Doppler	J		51	2000-01-30	2000-08-14	8	1	8	1	2000	2000	193	896				12		57		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	3218	Argos Doppler	J		36	1999-09-03	2000-03-08	7	1	12	2	1999	2000	193	896				12		57		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	3328	Argos Doppler	J		57	1999-09-23	2000-08-15	12	1	12	2	1999	2000	168	896	909			12		57		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	3342	Argos Doppler	J		31	2000-04-08	2000-07-05	4	4	7	1	2000	2000	193	896	909			12		57		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	3602	Argos Doppler	J		98	2000-01-30	2000-09-26	9	1	9	1	2000	2000	193	896				12		57		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	12956	Argos Doppler	J		24	1998-11-29	1999-01-16	3	1	12	2	1998	1999	193	896				12		57		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	1605	Argos Doppler	M	A	7	1999-09-02	1999-11-17	3	9	11	1	1999	1999	26	895	910			12		57		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	1963	Argos Doppler	M	A	4	1999-07-30	1999-08-27	2	7	8	1	1999	1999	26	895	910			12		57		
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	78455	Argos Doppler	J		13	2008-09-04	2008-09-28	1	9	9	1	2008	2008	193	319	909			57				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	78456	Argos Doppler	J		134	2008-12-19	2010-01-11	12	1	12	3	2008	2010	193	319				57				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	78457	Argos Doppler	J		73	2009-02-15	2009-07-11	6	2	7	1	2009	2009	193	319	909			57				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	78458	Argos Doppler	J		211	2009-02-16	2010-06-07	12	1	12	2	2009	2010	193	319	909			57				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	78459	Argos Doppler	J		122	2008-12-23	2009-10-01	11	1	12	2	2008	2009	193	319				57				
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	78460	Argos Doppler	J		55	2008-10-08	2009-04-02	6	2	12	2	2008	2009	193	319				57				

Species	Tag ID	Sensor	Sex	Age class	Days	Start date	End date	Months	Start month	End month	Years	Start year	End year	Start marID	CiteID1	CiteID2	CiteID3	CiteID4	ProvID1	ProvID2	ProvID3	ProvID4	ProvID5	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	78461	Argos Doppler		J	258	2008-09-05	2010-04-18	12	1	12	3	2008	2010	193	319	909							57	
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	78462	Argos Doppler		J	106	2009-02-14	2009-11-08	10	2	11	1	2009	2009	193	319	909								57
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	78463	Argos Doppler		J	231	2009-03-13	2012-03-21	12	1	12	4	2009	2012	193	319									57
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	78464	Argos Doppler		J	162	2009-02-15	2010-04-06	12	1	12	2	2009	2010	193	319	909								57
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	94949	Argos Doppler		J	145	2009-07-08	2010-03-30	9	1	12	2	2009	2010	193	319	909								57
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	94950	Argos Doppler		J	177	2009-08-29	2010-12-02	12	1	12	2	2009	2010	193	319	909								57
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	94951	Argos Doppler		J	443	2009-10-25	2012-02-23	12	1	12	4	2009	2012	193	319									57
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	94952	Argos Doppler		J	49	2009-06-16	2009-09-27	4	6	9	1	2009	2009	193	319	909								57
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	94954	Argos Doppler		J	17	2009-08-14	2009-09-15	2	8	9	1	2009	2009	193	319	909								57
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	94955	Argos Doppler		J	432	2009-08-14	2012-03-16	12	1	12	4	2009	2012	193	319	909								57
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	94956	Argos Doppler		J	39	2010-05-28	2010-09-01	5	5	9	1	2010	2010	193	319									57
<i>Caretta caretta</i>	94957	Argos Doppler		J	47	2009-09-09	2009-11-08	3	9	11	1	2009	2009	193	319	909								57
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	131467	Argos Doppler		F	A	13	2014-05-16	2014-06-05	2	5	6	1	2014	2014	49	21								3
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	66890a	Argos Doppler		F	A	25	2006-09-15	2007-01-16	5	1	12	2	2006	2007	27	95								7
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	42560a	Argos Doppler		F	A	28	2003-08-01	2003-11-18	4	8	11	1	2003	2003	27	100								7
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	42905a	Argos Doppler		F	A	100	2003-08-22	2004-05-27	10	1	12	2	2003	2004	27	100								7
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	33870a	Argos Doppler		F	A	36	2004-09-02	2004-11-17	3	9	11	1	2004	2004	27	100								7
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	33871a	Argos Doppler		F	A	19	2004-08-30	2004-09-26	2	8	9	1	2004	2004	27	100								7
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	49811a	Argos Doppler		F	A	47	2004-08-19	2004-12-30	4	8	12	1	2004	2004	27	100								7
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	34089a	Argos Doppler		F	A	50	2005-08-21	2006-01-17	6	1	12	2	2005	2006	27	100								7
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	34106a	Argos Doppler		F	A	111	2005-08-30	2006-08-23	9	1	12	2	2005	2006	27	100								7
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	34107a	Argos Doppler		F	A	29	2005-07-25	2005-10-12	4	7	10	1	2005	2005	27	100								7
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	49822a	Argos Doppler		F	A	44	2004-07-16	2004-10-20	4	7	10	1	2004	2004	212	858	130	310						10
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	49823a	Argos Doppler		F	A	91	2004-07-18	2004-11-07	5	7	11	1	2004	2004	212	858	130	310						10
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	49825a	Argos Doppler		F	A	42	2004-07-22	2004-09-11	3	7	9	1	2004	2004	212	858	130	310						10
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	49826a	Argos Doppler		F	A	66	2005-07-18	2006-01-30	6	1	12	2	2005	2006	212	858	130	310						10
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	57382a	Argos Doppler		F	A	40	2005-07-20	2005-09-08	3	7	9	1	2005	2005	212	858	130	310						10
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	57387a	Argos Doppler		F	A	24	2005-07-18	2005-08-11	2	7	8	1	2005	2005	212	858	130	310						10
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	57388a	Argos Doppler		F	A	15	2005-07-13	2005-08-03	2	7	8	1	2005	2005	212	858	130	310						10
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	Greenturtle_X1	Global Positioning System		F	A	103	2012-10-18	2013-02-01	5	1	12	2	2012	2013	148	376								16 25
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	Greenturtle_X2	Global Positioning System		F	A	241	2012-10-14	2013-08-01	11	1	12	2	2012	2013	148	376								16 25
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	Greenturtle_X3	Global Positioning System		F	A	175	2012-10-13	2013-06-05	9	1	12	2	2012	2013	148	376								16 25
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	Greenturtle_X4	Global Positioning System		F	A	219	2012-10-14	2013-05-25	8	1	12	2	2012	2013	148	376								16 25
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	Greenturtle_X5	Global Positioning System		F	A	182	2012-10-21	2013-06-04	9	1	12	2	2012	2013	148	376								16 25
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	Greenturtle_X6	Global Positioning System		F	A	456	2012-10-23	2014-04-29	12	1	12	3	2012	2014	148	376								16 25
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	Greenturtle_X7	Global Positioning System		F	A	424	2012-10-24	2014-01-19	12	1	12	3	2012	2014	148	376								16 25
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	Greenturtle_X8	Global Positioning System		F	A	203	2012-10-25	2013-07-24	10	1	12	2	2012	2013	148	376								16 25
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	159774	Argos Doppler; Global Positioning System		J		56	2016-05-12	2016-09-21	5	5	9	1	2016	2016	217	934	935							18 58
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	159776	Argos Doppler; Global Positioning System		J		102	2016-05-06	2016-08-26	4	5	8	1	2016	2016	217	934	935							18 58
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	159778	Argos Doppler; Global Positioning System		J		12	2016-05-06	2016-05-18	1	5	5	1	2016	2016	217	934	935							18 58
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	159781	Argos Doppler; Global Positioning System		J		124	2016-05-07	2016-09-26	5	5	9	1	2016	2016	217	934	935							18 58

Species	Tag ID	Sensor	Sex	Age class	Days	Start date	End date	Months	Start month	End month	Years	Start year	End year	Start marID	CiteID1	CiteID2	CiteID3	CiteID4	ProvID1	ProvID2	ProvID3	ProvID4	ProvID5
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	159783	Argos Doppler; Global Positioning System		J	13	2016-05-08	2016-06-28	2	5	6	1	2016	2016	217	934	935			18	58			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	150427	Argos Doppler	F	A	40	2015-07-03	2015-09-06	3	7	9	1	2015	2015	42	125				8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	150428	Argos Doppler	F	A	48	2015-07-04	2015-08-28	2	7	8	1	2015	2015	42	125				8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	150429a	Argos Doppler	F	A	108	2015-07-01	2015-11-23	5	7	11	1	2015	2015	42	125				8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	150430	Argos Doppler	F	A	58	2015-07-01	2015-09-12	3	7	9	1	2015	2015	42	125				8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	150431	Argos Doppler	F	A	50	2015-07-02	2015-08-28	2	7	8	1	2015	2015	42	125				8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	95097a	Argos Doppler	F	A	161	2009-07-13	2010-11-02	10	1	12	2	2009	2010	42	858	130	310		8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	95098a	Argos Doppler	F	A	37	2009-07-26	2009-11-05	5	7	11	1	2009	2009	42	858	130	310		8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	95099a	Argos Doppler	M	A	69	2009-06-08	2009-08-28	3	6	8	1	2009	2009	42	952				8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	95100a	Argos Doppler	F	A	14	2009-07-20	2009-08-10	2	7	8	1	2009	2009	42	858	130	310		8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	95101a	Argos Doppler	F	A	53	2009-07-09	2011-06-20	10	1	12	3	2009	2011	42	858	130	310		8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	95102a	Argos Doppler	F	A	46	2009-07-25	2009-11-03	5	7	11	1	2009	2009	42	858	130	310		8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	52820a	Argos Doppler	F	A	148	2010-07-06	2012-07-01	12	1	12	3	2010	2012	42	858	130	310		8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	52827a	Argos Doppler	F	A	147	2010-07-07	2011-08-12	12	1	12	2	2010	2011	42	858	130	310		8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	52846a	Argos Doppler	F	A	97	2010-07-09	2011-02-21	8	1	12	2	2010	2011	42	858	130	310		8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	52888a	Argos Doppler	F	A	56	2010-07-23	2010-11-08	5	7	11	1	2010	2010	42	858	130	310		8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	52949a	Argos Doppler	F	A	161	2010-07-11	2011-10-22	12	1	12	2	2010	2011	42	858	130	310		8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	86898a	Argos Doppler	F	A	109	2010-07-06	2011-06-04	10	1	12	2	2010	2011	42	858	130	310		8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	86900a	Argos Doppler	F	A	234	2010-07-14	2011-08-29	12	1	12	2	2010	2011	42	858	130	310		8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	36638a	Argos Doppler	F	A	210	2003-07-15	2004-06-23	12	1	12	2	2003	2004	42	858	130	310		8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	36639a	Argos Doppler	F	A	157	2004-06-25	2005-07-13	11	1	12	2	2004	2005	42	858	130	310		8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	4148a	Argos Doppler	F	A	105	1998-08-02	1999-05-15	10	1	12	2	1998	1999	42	858	130	310		8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	4149a	Argos Doppler	F	A	102	1998-07-31	1999-03-07	9	1	12	2	1998	1999	42	858	130	310		8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	4150a	Argos Doppler	F	A	124	1998-07-28	1999-05-16	11	1	12	2	1998	1999	42	858	130	310		8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	4228a	Argos Doppler	F	A	71	2002-07-28	2003-12-10	9	1	12	2	2002	2003	42	858	130	310		8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	4404a	Argos Doppler	F	A	139	2002-07-15	2003-07-22	12	1	12	2	2002	2003	42	858	130	310		8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	4405a	Argos Doppler	F	A	157	2002-07-30	2003-09-03	11	1	12	2	2002	2003	42	858	130	310		8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	49813a	Argos Doppler	F	A	167	2004-07-23	2005-05-30	11	1	12	2	2004	2005	42	858	130	310		8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	49815a	Argos Doppler	F	A	28	2004-07-10	2004-09-03	3	7	9	1	2004	2004	42	858	130	310		8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	49816a	Argos Doppler	F	A	125	2004-07-23	2005-07-15	11	1	12	2	2004	2005	42	858	130	310		8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	5910a	Argos Doppler	F	A	27	1999-07-20	1999-08-31	2	7	8	1	1999	1999	42	858	130	310		8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	6582a	Argos Doppler	F	A	21	1999-07-27	2000-01-11	3	1	8	2	1999	2000	42	858	130	310		8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	6598a	Argos Doppler	F	A	40	1999-07-20	2000-03-17	8	1	12	2	1999	2000	42	858	130	310		8	21	54		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	86394a	Argos Doppler	F	A	22	2008-07-16	2008-08-19	2	7	8	1	2008	2008	94	486	857			21	29			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	93699a	Argos Doppler	F	A	43	2009-06-27	2009-08-20	3	6	8	1	2009	2009	159	486	857			21	29			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	93702a	Argos Doppler	F	A	198	2009-06-20	2010-06-09	12	1	12	2	2009	2010	94	486	857			21	29			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	72127a	Argos Doppler	F	A	17	2007-04-12	2007-05-13	2	4	5	1	2007	2007	139	293				19	21	26		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	75966a	Argos Doppler	F	A	8	2008-07-28	2008-08-04	2	7	8	1	2008	2008	140	293				19	21	26		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	75967a	Argos Doppler	F	A	21	2008-08-19	2008-09-09	2	8	9	1	2008	2008	140	293				19	21	26		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	82837a	Argos Doppler	F	A	21	2009-05-21	2009-06-10	2	5	6	1	2009	2009	140	293				19	21	26		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	GreenTurtle_X1	Argos Doppler		J	34	2008-04-02	2008-09-13	5	4	9	1	2008	2008	8	315				22	9			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	GreenTurtle_X2	Argos Doppler		J	256	2008-04-24	2009-02-15	11	1	12	2	2008	2009	8	315				22	9			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	GreenTurtle_X3	Argos Doppler		J	107	2008-12-19	2009-05-03	6	1	12	2	2008	2009	8	315				22	9			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	GreenTurtle_X4	Argos Doppler		J	107	2009-02-20	2009-07-18	6	2	7	1	2009	2009	7	315				22	9			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	GreenTurtle_X5	Argos Doppler		J	290	2010-03-09	2011-03-01	12	1	12	2	2010	2011	8	315				22	9			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	GreenTurtle_X6	Argos Doppler		J	247	2009-03-10	2009-12-25	10	3	12	1	2009	2009	8	315				22	9			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	GreenTurtle_X7	Argos Doppler		J	49	2009-02-18	2009-04-27	3	2	4	1	2009	2009	8	315				22	9			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	GreenTurtle_X8	Argos Doppler		J	127	2010-01-06	2010-08-01	8	1	8	1	2010	2010	110	315				22	9			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	GreenTurtle_X9	Argos Doppler		J	156	2010-12-16	2011-06-07	7	1	12	2	2010	2011	8	315				22	9			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	1084	Argos Doppler	F	A	83	1997-01-25	1997-05-16	5	1	5	1	1997	1997	134	337				23	41			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	20622	Argos Doppler			18	1999-08-06	1999-09-09	2	8	9	1	1999	1999	136	337				23	41			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	21218	Argos Doppler	F	A	17	2001-03-02	2001-04-19	2	3	4	1	2001	2001	136	337				23	41			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	21219	Argos Doppler	F	A	66	2001-02-19	2001-08-29	7	2	8	1	2001	2001	136	337				23	41			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	21221	Argos Doppler	F	A	33	2001-02-27	2001-07-27	6	2	7	1	2001	2001	136	337				23	41			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	3847	Argos Doppler	F	A	4	1997-08-10	1997-08-19	1	8	8	1	1997	1997	134	337				23	41			

Species	Tag ID	Sensor	Sex	Age class	Days	Start date	End date	Months	Start month	End month	Years	Start year	End year	Start marID	CiteID1	CiteID2	CiteID3	CiteID4	ProvID1	ProvID2	ProvID3	ProvID4	ProvID5
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	3848	Argos Doppler	F	A	3	1997-08-07	1997-08-13	1	8	8	1	1997	1997	134	337				23	41			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	3849	Argos Doppler	F	A	7	1997-08-13	1997-09-09	2	8	9	1	1997	1997	134	337				23	41			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	5523	Argos Doppler	F	A	12	1997-08-17	1997-10-07	3	8	10	1	1997	1997	134	337				23	41			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	21411a	Argos Doppler	F	A	8	2007-05-03	2007-06-25	2	5	6	1	2007	2007	134	802				23	52			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	108718a	Argos Doppler	M	A	5	2012-05-19	2012-05-30	1	5	5	1	2012	2012	94	396				27				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	113531a	Argos Doppler	M	A	15	2012-07-15	2012-09-15	3	7	9	1	2012	2012	118	398				27				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	88236b	Argos Doppler	F	A	27	2010-06-28	2010-09-06	4	6	9	1	2010	2010	61	388				27				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	120040a	Argos Doppler	F	A	50	2012-08-08	2012-11-29	4	8	11	1	2012	2012	212	447	813			28	55			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	VAQS20072055	Argos Doppler	F	A	53	2007-10-23	2008-02-24	5	1	12	2	2007	2008	218	506				14	31			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	VAQS20082129	Argos Doppler			41	2009-06-24	2009-08-17	3	6	8	1	2009	2009	218	506				14	31			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	11678 (E4)	Argos Doppler	F	A	37	1998-06-04	1998-07-10	2	6	7	1	1998	1998	9	640				1	25	33		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	11679 (A)	Argos Doppler	F	A	16	1997-04-27	1997-05-16	2	4	5	1	1997	1997	9	521				1	25	33		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	11679 (E1)	Argos Doppler	F	A	9	1998-06-01	1998-06-11	1	6	6	1	1998	1998	9	640				1	25	33		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	11680 (E5)	Argos Doppler	F	A	38	1998-06-03	1998-07-13	2	6	7	1	1998	1998	9	640				1	25	33		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	11681 (E7)	Argos Doppler	F	A	34	1998-06-13	1998-07-22	2	6	7	1	1998	1998	9	640				1	25	33		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	11682 (C7)	Argos Doppler	F	A	31	1997-07-02	1997-08-06	2	7	8	1	1997	1997	9	521	640			1	25	33		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	11683 (C8)	Argos Doppler	F	A	44	1997-06-28	1997-08-13	3	6	8	1	1997	1997	9	521	640			1	25	33		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	11683 (E6)	Argos Doppler	F	A	21	1998-06-05	1998-06-25	1	6	6	1	1998	1998	9	640				1	25	33		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	4394 (C2)	Argos Doppler	F	A	63	1998-06-03	1998-08-20	3	6	8	1	1998	1998	9	640				1	25	33		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	4395 (C1)	Argos Doppler	F	A	32	1998-06-29	1998-07-31	2	6	7	1	1998	1998	9	640				1	25	33		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	4650 (E2)	Argos Doppler	F	A	29	1998-05-30	1998-07-09	3	5	7	1	1998	1998	9	640				1	25	33		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	4651 (E3)	Argos Doppler	F	A	38	1998-06-03	1998-07-10	2	6	7	1	1998	1998	9	640				1	25	33		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	4662 (C3)	Argos Doppler	F	A	46	1998-06-03	1998-07-20	2	6	7	1	1998	1998	9	521	640			1	25	33		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	6611 (C4)	Argos Doppler	F	A	34	1997-05-12	1997-06-16	2	5	6	1	1997	1997	9	521	640			1	25	33		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	6614 (C5)	Argos Doppler	F	A	37	1997-06-23	1997-07-31	2	6	7	1	1997	1997	9	521	640			1	25	33		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	6615 (C6)	Argos Doppler	F	A	22	1997-06-25	1997-07-27	2	6	7	1	1997	1997	9	521	640			1	25	33		
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	138424	Argos Doppler	J		32	2014-06-17	2014-08-27	3	6	8	1	2014	2014	52	557				38				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	138426	Argos Doppler	M	S	101	2014-06-19	2014-10-10	5	6	10	1	2014	2014	52	557				38				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	138427	Argos Doppler	M	S	37	2014-06-20	2014-07-29	2	6	7	1	2014	2014	52	557				38				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	37189	Argos Doppler	J		56	2003-11-22	2004-05-11	7	1	12	2	2003	2004	218	562				38	46			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	37190	Argos Doppler	J		17	2003-11-09	2004-01-20	3	1	12	2	2003	2004	218	562				38	46			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	37195	Argos Doppler	J		17	2003-11-05	2003-12-19	2	11	12	1	2003	2003	218	562				38	46			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	37196	Argos Doppler	J		67	2003-10-30	2004-02-14	5	1	12	2	2003	2004	218	562				38	46			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	37210	Argos Doppler	J		5	2003-11-02	2003-11-12	1	11	11	1	2003	2003	218	562				38	46			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	59248	Argos Doppler	J		9	2005-08-04	2005-09-23	2	8	9	1	2005	2005	218	560				38	46			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	59250	Argos Doppler	J		17	2006-06-06	2006-07-21	2	6	7	1	2006	2006	218	560				38	46			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	59261	Argos Doppler	J		32	2006-06-13	2006-11-13	4	6	11	1	2006	2006	218	560				38	46			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	59262a	Argos Doppler	J		18	2006-08-17	2006-10-30	3	8	10	1	2006	2006	218	560				38	46			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	59263a	Argos Doppler	J		16	2006-10-07	2006-11-04	2	10	11	1	2006	2006	218	560				38	46			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	59264a	Argos Doppler	J		3	2006-06-09	2006-06-17	1	6	6	1	2006	2006	218	560				38	46			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	59265	Argos Doppler	J		55	2006-10-07	2007-02-20	5	1	12	2	2006	2007	218	560				38	46			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	59266a	Argos Doppler	J		2	2006-05-24	2006-06-25	2	5	6	1	2006	2006	218	560				38	46			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	43773a	Argos Doppler	J		35	2010-03-16	2010-04-29	2	3	4	1	2010	2010	57	554	556	555		38				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	43784a	Argos Doppler	J		142	2010-03-21	2010-11-11	9	3	11	1	2010	2010	57	554	556	555		38				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	43785a	Argos Doppler	J		40	2010-03-21	2010-06-19	4	3	6	1	2010	2010	57	554	556	555		38				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	68393a	Argos Doppler	J		20	2011-11-26	2012-01-05	3	1	12	2	2011	2012	57	554	556	555		38				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	68396a	Argos Doppler	J		92	2010-11-09	2011-07-17	8	1	12	2	2010	2011	57	554	556	555		38				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	73420a	Argos Doppler	S		68	2010-11-01	2011-01-09	3	1	12	2	2010	2011	57	554	556	555		38				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	86899a	Argos Doppler	S		89	2010-03-28	2010-09-02	7	3	9	1	2010	2010	57	554	556	555		38				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	68395a	Argos Doppler	J		31	2010-11-24	2011-05-04	6	1	12	2	2010	2011	57	554	556	555		38				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	68397a	Argos Doppler	S		34	2011-02-01	2011-05-05	4	2	5	1	2011	2011	52	554	553			38				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	73419a	Argos Doppler	S		105	2011-01-28	2011-06-05	6	1	6	1	2011	2011	52	554	553			38				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	140874	Argos Doppler	F	A	55	2015-09-04	2015-11-05	3	9	11	1	2015	2015	166	684				44				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	140875	Argos Doppler	F	A	73	2015-09-07	2015-11-22	3	9	11	1	2015	2015	123	684				44				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	140876	Argos Doppler	F	A	33	2015-07-12	2015-08-21	2	7	8	1	2015	2015	223	684				44				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	140877	Argos Doppler	F	A	38	2015-07-05	2015-08-15	2	7	8	1	2015	2015	123	684				44				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	140878	Argos Doppler	F	A	149	2015-09-04	2016-02-15	6	1	12	2	2015	2016	166	684				44				

Species	Tag ID	Sensor	Sex	Age class	Days	Start date	End date	Months	Start month	End month	Years	Start year	End year	Start marID	CiteID1	CiteID2	CiteID3	CiteID4	ProvID1	ProvID2	ProvID3	ProvID4	ProvID5	
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	140879	Argos Doppler	F	A	70	2015-09-04	2015-11-14	3	9	11	1	2015	2015	166	684								44	
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	140880	Argos Doppler	F	A	103	2015-09-04	2016-01-10	5	1	12	2	2015	2016	123	684									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	140881	Argos Doppler	F	A	120	2015-07-05	2015-12-05	6	7	12	1	2015	2015	123	684									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	140882	Argos Doppler	F	A	66	2015-09-04	2015-11-16	3	9	11	1	2015	2015	123	684									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	140883	Argos Doppler	F	A	60	2015-07-06	2015-09-09	3	7	9	1	2015	2015	123	684									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	148463	Argos Doppler	F	A	112	2015-09-04	2016-01-07	5	1	12	2	2015	2016	166	684									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	148464	Argos Doppler	F	A	205	2015-09-05	2016-06-26	10	1	12	2	2015	2016	123	684									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	148465	Argos Doppler	F	A	61	2015-07-06	2016-01-21	6	1	12	2	2015	2016	123	684									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	148466	Argos Doppler	F	A	181	2015-09-07	2016-03-22	7	1	12	2	2015	2016	123	684									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	148467	Argos Doppler	F	A	20	2015-09-06	2015-10-05	2	9	10	1	2015	2015	123	684									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	148468	Argos Doppler	F	A	48	2015-07-06	2015-09-01	3	7	9	1	2015	2015	123	684									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	148469	Argos Doppler	F	A	61	2015-09-06	2015-11-07	3	9	11	1	2015	2015	123	684									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	148470	Argos Doppler	F	A	93	2015-09-05	2015-12-19	4	9	12	1	2015	2015	123	684									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	148471	Argos Doppler	F	A	80	2015-07-05	2015-09-23	3	7	9	1	2015	2015	123	684									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	148472	Argos Doppler	F	A	73	2015-07-05	2015-10-16	4	7	10	1	2015	2015	123	684									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	161130	Argos Doppler	F	A	84	2016-07-19	2016-10-25	4	7	10	1	2016	2016	123	684									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	161131	Argos Doppler	F	A	97	2016-07-19	2016-10-29	4	7	10	1	2016	2016	123	684									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	161132	Argos Doppler	F	A	75	2016-07-20	2016-11-10	5	7	11	1	2016	2016	123	684									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	161133	Argos Doppler	F	A	115	2016-07-20	2016-11-19	5	7	11	1	2016	2016	123	684									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	161134	Argos Doppler	F	A	37	2016-07-19	2016-09-02	3	7	9	1	2016	2016	123	684									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	161137	Argos Doppler	M	A	55	2016-06-10	2016-08-03	3	6	8	1	2016	2016	166	684									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	161138	Argos Doppler	M	A	80	2016-06-16	2016-09-09	4	6	9	1	2016	2016	166	684									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	161135	Argos Doppler	J	J	34	2017-07-29	2017-11-04	5	7	11	1	2017	2017	121	678									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	161136	Argos Doppler	J	J	99	2017-06-28	2017-10-10	5	6	10	1	2017	2017	121	678									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	161139	Argos Doppler	J	J	65	2017-06-25	2017-09-29	4	6	9	1	2017	2017	121	678									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	23562a	Argos Doppler	J	J	90	2004-12-14	2005-06-21	5	3	12	2	2004	2005	126	677									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	23563a	Argos Doppler	J	J	6	2004-12-15	2005-01-29	2	1	12	2	2004	2005	126	677									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	23564a	Argos Doppler	J	J	67	2004-12-14	2005-03-18	4	1	12	2	2004	2005	126	677									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	23565a	Argos Doppler	J	J	76	2004-12-14	2007-05-16	5	1	12	3	2004	2007	126	677									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	102641	Argos Doppler	F	J	137	2011-02-23	2011-09-01	8	2	9	1	2011	2011	122	684									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	102642	Argos Doppler	M	J	132	2011-02-10	2011-08-29	6	2	8	1	2011	2011	122	684									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	102643	Argos Doppler	M	J	331	2011-01-31	2012-03-30	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	122	684									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	105427	Argos Doppler	J	J	144	2011-02-20	2011-10-09	9	2	10	1	2011	2011	122	684									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	105428	Argos Doppler	F	J	175	2011-02-20	2011-08-31	7	2	8	1	2011	2011	122	684									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	133595	Argos Doppler	M	J	57	2015-03-12	2015-06-06	4	3	6	1	2015	2015	171	682									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	133596	Argos Doppler	F	J	83	2015-03-13	2015-06-12	4	3	6	1	2015	2015	171	682									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	133597	Argos Doppler	F	J	49	2015-03-13	2015-05-03	3	3	5	1	2015	2015	171	682									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	133598	Argos Doppler	F	J	76	2015-03-17	2015-07-19	5	3	7	1	2015	2015	171	682									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	133599	Argos Doppler	F	J	66	2015-01-26	2015-07-28	7	1	7	1	2015	2015	11	682									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	133600	Argos Doppler	M	S	124	2014-11-12	2015-05-28	7	1	12	2	2014	2015	171	682									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	133601	Argos Doppler	F	J	211	2014-11-16	2016-03-12	10	1	12	3	2014	2016	171	682									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	133602	Argos Doppler	M	J	129	2014-11-11	2015-05-29	7	1	12	2	2014	2015	171	682									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	133603	Argos Doppler	M	J	213	2014-11-19	2015-07-27	9	1	12	2	2014	2015	171	682									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	133604	Argos Doppler	F	J	161	2014-11-18	2015-07-29	9	1	12	2	2014	2015	11	682									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	133605	Argos Doppler	F	J	135	2014-11-19	2015-05-24	7	1	12	2	2014	2015	11	682									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	133607	Argos Doppler	F	J	58	2015-03-13	2015-05-24	3	3	5	1	2015	2015	171	682									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	133608	Argos Doppler	F	J	73	2015-03-11	2015-06-17	4	3	6	1	2015	2015	171	682									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	133609	Argos Doppler	M	J	41	2015-03-11	2015-05-16	3	3	5	1	2015	2015	171	682									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	133610	Argos Doppler	F	J	54	2015-03-14	2015-06-15	4	3	6	1	2015	2015	171	682									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	133611	Argos Doppler	F	J	49	2015-03-12	2015-05-12	3	3	5	1	2015	2015	171	682									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	133613	Argos Doppler	F	J	82	2014-02-28	2014-06-23	5	2	6	1	2014	2014	171	682									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	142838	Argos Doppler	M	J	62	2015-03-12	2015-05-27	3	3	5	1	2015	2015	171	682									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	142839	Argos Doppler	F	J	81	2015-03-12	2015-06-11	4	3	6	1	2015	2015	171	682									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	142840	Argos Doppler	M	J	62	2015-03-11	2015-05-24	3	3	5	1	2015	2015	171	682									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	142843	Argos Doppler	F	J	63	2015-03-14	2015-06-21	4	3	6	1	2015	2015	171	682									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	142844	Argos Doppler	M	J	87	2015-03-13	2015-06-12	4	3	6	1	2015	2015	171	682									44
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	142847	Argos Doppler	M	J	83	2015-03-11	2015-07-07	5	3	7	1	2015	2015	171	682									44

Species	Tag ID	Sensor	Sex	Age class	Days	Start date	End date	Months	Start month	End month	Years	Start year	End year	Start marID	CiteID1	CiteID2	CiteID3	CiteID4	ProvID1	ProvID2	ProvID3	ProvID4	ProvID5				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	67557a	Argos Doppler	F	A	28	2006-09-16	2006-10-24	2	9	10	1	2006	2006	223	953								44				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	67558a	Argos Doppler	F	A	36	2006-11-01	2007-02-04	4	1	12	2	2006	2007	223	953								44				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	67559a	Argos Doppler	F	A	36	2006-09-15	2007-12-09	8	3	12	2	2006	2007	223	953								44				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	78002a	Argos Doppler	F	A	18	2007-09-26	2008-01-23	3	1	10	2	2007	2008	223	953								44				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	78003a	Argos Doppler	F	A	54	2007-09-26	2008-01-03	5	1	12	2	2007	2008	223	953								44				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	78182a	Argos Doppler	F	A	123	2008-07-28	2009-03-30	9	1	12	2	2008	2009	223	953								44				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	49082a	Argos Doppler	F	A	41	2006-07-09	2006-10-08	4	7	10	1	2006	2006	202	727	857							35	47			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	75968a	Argos Doppler	F	A	71	2008-08-26	2008-12-09	5	8	12	1	2008	2008	145	724								47				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	82836a	Argos Doppler	F	A	55	2008-09-27	2009-01-25	5	1	12	2	2008	2009	145	724								47				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	112054	Argos Doppler		S	43	2011-11-26	2012-07-02	6	1	12	2	2011	2012	215	757								6	48			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	118217	Argos Doppler		S	39	2012-06-30	2013-04-09	5	4	9	2	2012	2013	215	757								6	48			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	119279	Argos Doppler		S	60	2012-06-30	2012-12-27	4	6	12	1	2012	2012	215	757								6	48			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	119864	Argos Doppler	F	A	58	2012-06-30	2012-10-01	5	6	10	1	2012	2012	215	757								6	48			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	55884	Argos Doppler		S	16	2005-02-13	2005-12-02	3	2	12	1	2005	2005	215	757								6	48			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	55885	Argos Doppler	F	A	231	2008-02-16	2008-11-01	10	2	11	1	2008	2008	214	757								6	48			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	61002	Argos Doppler		S	121	2010-06-08	2010-10-27	5	6	10	1	2010	2010	215	757								6	48			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	99066	Argos Doppler	F	A	152	2009-11-11	2010-09-17	11	1	12	2	2009	2010	215	757								6	48			
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	19581	Argos Doppler	F	A	17	2003-02-26	2003-04-17	3	2	4	1	2003	2003	49	808								52				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	19604	Argos Doppler	F	A	23	2003-03-13	2003-04-27	2	3	4	1	2003	2003	49	808								52				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	42972	Argos Doppler	F	A	39	2005-04-10	2005-06-05	3	4	6	1	2005	2005	49	808								52				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	42974	Argos Doppler	F	A	25	2005-04-11	2005-06-06	3	4	6	1	2005	2005	49	808								52				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	42984	Argos Doppler	F	A	18	2005-04-12	2005-06-06	3	4	6	1	2005	2005	49	808								52				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	42988	Argos Doppler	F	A	38	2005-04-02	2005-06-02	3	4	6	1	2005	2005	49	808								52				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	42989	Argos Doppler	F	A	14	2005-04-10	2005-06-04	3	4	6	1	2005	2005	49	808								52				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	42991	Argos Doppler	F	A	14	2005-04-11	2005-06-01	3	4	6	1	2005	2005	49	808								52				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	42994	Argos Doppler	F	A	22	2005-04-10	2005-05-11	2	4	5	1	2005	2005	49	808								52				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	42998	Argos Doppler	F	A	19	2005-05-01	2005-05-31	1	5	5	1	2005	2005	80	808								52				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	5154	Argos Doppler	F	A	51	2003-03-02	2003-05-05	3	3	5	1	2003	2003	49	808								52				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	7298	Argos Doppler	F	A	36	2003-03-09	2003-06-10	4	3	6	1	2003	2003	49	808								52				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	137177	Argos Doppler		J	71	2014-04-26	2014-07-28	4	4	7	1	2014	2014	193	582								57				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	137178	Argos Doppler		J	48	2014-05-28	2014-09-30	5	5	9	1	2014	2014	193	582								57				
<i>Chelonia mydas</i>	137179	Argos Doppler		J	39	2014-06-21	2014-11-29	6	6	11	1	2014	2014	193	582								57				
<i>Derموchelys coriacea</i>	27579	Argos Doppler	M	A	158	2009-09-03	2010-03-25	7	1	12	2	2009	2010	218	229	228							15				
<i>Derموchelys coriacea</i>	82051	Argos Doppler	M	A	242	2008-08-10	2009-04-09	9	1	12	2	2008	2009	218	229	228							15				
<i>Derموchelys coriacea</i>	82052	Argos Doppler	F	A	259	2008-07-29	2009-04-19	10	1	12	2	2008	2009	218	229	228							15				
<i>Derموchelys coriacea</i>	82053	Argos Doppler	M	A	200	2008-08-23	2009-04-14	9	1	12	2	2008	2009	218	229	228							15				
<i>Derموchelys coriacea</i>	82054	Argos Doppler		S	160	2008-08-29	2009-03-07	8	1	12	2	2008	2009	218	229	228							15				
<i>Derموchelys coriacea</i>	82055	Argos Doppler		S	150	2008-08-10	2009-01-09	6	1	12	2	2008	2009	218	229	228							15				
<i>Derموchelys coriacea</i>	82056	Argos Doppler		S	319	2009-07-10	2010-08-28	12	1	12	2	2009	2010	218	229	228							15				
<i>Derموchelys coriacea</i>	82057	Argos Doppler		S	199	2009-08-27	2010-06-01	11	1	12	2	2009	2010	218	229	228							15				
<i>Derموchelys coriacea</i>	122425	Argos Doppler	F	A	77	2012-10-26	2013-01-11	4	1	12	2	2012	2013	57	941	942	672						8	13	17	21	59
<i>Derموchelys coriacea</i>	122426	Argos Doppler	F	A	165	2012-10-26	2013-04-15	7	1	12	2	2012	2013	57	941	942	672						8	13	17	21	59
<i>Derموchelys coriacea</i>	122427	Argos Doppler	F	A	176	2012-10-27	2013-04-20	7	1	12	2	2012	2013	57	941	942	672						8	13	17	21	59
<i>Derموchelys coriacea</i>	122428	Argos Doppler	F	A	147	2012-10-27	2013-03-26	6	1	12	2	2012	2013	57	941	942	672						8	13	17	21	59
<i>Derموchelys coriacea</i>	122429	Argos Doppler	F	A	185	2012-10-27	2013-05-03	8	1	12	2	2012	2013	57	941	942	672						8	13	17	21	59
<i>Derموchelys coriacea</i>	122430	Argos Doppler	F	A	13	2012-10-28	2012-11-09	2	10	11	1	2012	2012	57	941	942	672						8	13	17	21	59
<i>Derموchelys coriacea</i>	122431	Argos Doppler	F	A	146	2012-10-28	2013-03-23	6	1	12	2	2012	2013	57	941	942	672						8	13	17	21	59
<i>Derموchelys coriacea</i>	122432	Argos Doppler	F	A	136	2012-10-28	2013-03-15	6	1	12	2	2012	2013	57	941	942	672						8	13	17	21	59
<i>Derموchelys coriacea</i>	122433	Argos Doppler	F	A	252	2012-10-28	2013-07-09	10	1	12	2	2012	2013	57	941	942	672						8	13	17	21	59
<i>Derموchelys coriacea</i>	122434	Argos Doppler	F	A	122	2012-10-29	2013-03-03	6	1	12	2	2012	2013	57	941	942	672						8	13	17	21	59
<i>Derموchelys coriacea</i>	57378	Argos Doppler	F	A	134	2006-02-24	2007-04-13	7	2	12	2	2006	2007	58	941	942	672						8	13	17	21	59
<i>Derموchelys coriacea</i>	57381	Argos Doppler	F	A	142	2006-02-24	2007-01-21	8	1	11	2	2006	2007	58	941	942	672						8	13	17	21	59
<i>Derموchelys coriacea</i>	57383	Argos Doppler	F	A	10	2005-12-12	2005-12-21	1	12	12	1	2005	2005	58	941	942	672						8	13	17	21	59
<i>Derموchelys coriacea</i>	57390	Argos Doppler	F	A	13	2006-02-25	2006-03-09	2	2	3	1	2006	2006	58	941	942	672						8	13	17	21	59
<i>Derموchelys coriacea</i>	57663	Argos Doppler	F	A	231	2006-03-19	2007-02-20	12	1	12	2	2006	2007	58	941	942	672						8	13	17	21	59
<i>Derموchelys coriacea</i>	57666	Argos Doppler	F	A	37	2005-12-11	2006-02-06	3	1	12	2	2005	2006	58	941	942	672						8	13	17	21	59
<i>Derموchelys coriacea</i>	65693	Argos Doppler	F	A	54	2006-03-09	2006-09-06	5	3	9	1	2006	2006	58	941	942	672						8	13	17	21	59

Species	Tag ID	Sensor	Sex	Age class	Days	Start date	End date	Months	Start month	End month	Years	Start year	End year	Start marID	CiteID1	CiteID2	CiteID3	CiteID4	ProvID1	ProvID2	ProvID3	ProvID4	ProvID5
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	65694	Argos Doppler	F	A	59	2006-03-12	2006-06-04	4	3	6	1	2006	2006	58	941	942	672		8	13	17	21	59
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	68562	Argos Doppler	F	A	36	2007-01-27	2007-03-09	3	1	3	1	2007	2007	58	941	942	672		8	13	17	21	59
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	68563	Argos Doppler	F	A	26	2007-02-09	2007-03-08	2	2	3	1	2007	2007	58	941	942	672		8	13	17	21	59
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	80620	Argos Doppler	F	A	219	2008-02-12	2008-10-09	9	2	10	1	2008	2008	58	941	942	672		8	13	17	21	59
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	80621	Argos Doppler	F	A	119	2008-02-12	2008-07-12	6	2	7	1	2008	2008	58	941	942	672		8	13	17	21	59
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	80622	Argos Doppler	F	A	36	2008-02-12	2008-03-24	2	2	3	1	2008	2008	58	941	942	672		8	13	17	21	59
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	80623	Argos Doppler	F	A	58	2008-02-12	2008-05-13	4	2	5	1	2008	2008	58	941	942	672		8	13	17	21	59
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	80624	Argos Doppler	F	A	25	2008-02-15	2008-04-18	3	2	4	1	2008	2008	58	941	942	672		8	13	17	21	59
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	89071	Argos Doppler	F	A	162	2008-12-09	2009-05-29	6	1	12	2	2008	2009	57	941	942	672		8	13	17	21	59
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	89072	Argos Doppler	F	A	129	2008-12-10	2009-04-17	5	1	12	2	2008	2009	57	941	942	672		8	13	17	21	59
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	89073	Argos Doppler	F	A	122	2008-12-15	2009-05-14	6	1	12	2	2008	2009	57	941	942	672		8	13	17	21	59
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	89074	Argos Doppler	F	A	190	2008-12-16	2009-06-25	7	1	12	2	2008	2009	57	941	942	672		8	13	17	21	59
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	89075	Argos Doppler	F	A	343	2008-12-08	2009-11-22	12	1	12	2	2008	2009	57	941	942	672		8	13	17	21	59
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	89076	Argos Doppler	F	A	379	2008-12-17	2010-01-01	12	1	12	3	2008	2010	57	941	942	672		8	13	17	21	59
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	92577	Argos Doppler	F	A	196	2009-02-18	2009-09-02	8	2	9	1	2009	2009	58	941	942	672		8	13	17	21	59
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	92578	Argos Doppler	F	A	176	2009-02-18	2009-08-18	7	2	8	1	2009	2009	58	941	942	672		8	13	17	21	59
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	92579	Argos Doppler	F	A	122	2009-02-21	2009-10-06	9	2	10	1	2009	2009	58	941	942	672		8	13	17	21	59
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	92580	Argos Doppler	F	A	134	2009-02-21	2009-07-07	6	2	7	1	2009	2009	58	941	942	672		8	13	17	21	59
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	92581	Argos Doppler	F	A	204	2009-12-07	2010-06-29	7	1	12	2	2009	2010	57	941	942	672		8	13	17	21	59
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	92582	Argos Doppler	F	A	130	2009-12-08	2010-04-19	5	1	12	2	2009	2010	57	941	942	672		8	13	17	21	59
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	161232a	Argos Doppler	M	A	101	2017-02-17	2017-07-19	6	2	7	1	2017	2017	134	963				23	30	50	60	
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	15119	Argos Doppler	F		161	2002-07-10	2003-07-21	11	1	12	2	2002	2003	64	281	281			25				
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	15121z	Argos Doppler	F		179	2002-07-05	2003-06-03	11	1	12	2	2002	2003	64	281	281			25				
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	15122z	Argos Doppler			75	2005-07-21	2005-10-15	4	7	10	1	2005	2005	25	281	281			25				
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	21914z	Argos Doppler	F		189	2003-06-28	2004-09-02	8	1	12	2	2003	2004	64	281	281			25				
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	21915	Argos Doppler	F		176	2003-05-19	2004-06-11	11	1	12	2	2003	2004	64	281	281			25				
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	21920z	Argos Doppler	F		246	2003-04-06	2004-03-05	11	1	12	2	2003	2004	64	281	281			25				
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	21923z	Argos Doppler	F		168	2003-03-31	2004-05-24	12	1	12	2	2003	2004	64	281	281			25				
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	29358z	Argos Doppler	F		206	2003-07-10	2004-03-21	9	1	12	2	2003	2004	176	281	281			25				
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	4394	Argos Doppler	F		166	2003-06-15	2003-12-14	7	6	12	1	2003	2003	64	281	281			25				
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	4395	Argos Doppler	F		239	2003-06-18	2004-02-24	9	1	12	2	2003	2004	64	281	281			25				
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	48917z	Argos Doppler			124	2005-07-16	2005-11-20	5	7	11	1	2005	2005	25	281	281			25				
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	48918z	Argos Doppler			119	2005-08-31	2006-07-07	10	3	12	2	2005	2006	93	281	281			25				
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	60278z	Argos Doppler			179	2006-09-14	2007-06-20	10	1	12	2	2006	2007	24	281	281			25				
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	60279z	Argos Doppler			73	2006-09-08	2006-11-19	3	9	11	1	2006	2006	24	281	281			25				
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	66360z	Argos Doppler			216	2006-06-29	2007-02-16	9	1	12	2	2006	2007	93	281	281			25				
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	26001	Argos Doppler	F	A	11	2006-03-01	2006-05-23	3	3	5	1	2006	2006	79	14				32				
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	26001a	Argos Doppler	F	A	26	2005-12-14	2006-01-08	2	1	12	2	2005	2006	19	14				32				
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	26003	Argos Doppler	F	A	240	2005-12-17	2007-01-08	12	1	12	3	2005	2007	19	14				32				
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	26075	Argos Doppler	F	A	154	2005-12-17	2006-08-26	9	1	12	2	2005	2006	19	14				32				
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	10987	Argos Doppler	F	A	177	1999-02-01	1999-09-11	8	2	9	1	1999	1999	188	523				33				
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	14055	Argos Doppler	F	A	227	1999-02-01	1999-09-30	8	2	9	1	1999	1999	188	523				33				
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	18262	Argos Doppler	F	A	156	2003-01-30	2003-07-16	7	1	7	1	2003	2003	188	523				33				
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	21041	Argos Doppler	F	A	28	2000-01-30	2000-06-16	6	1	6	1	2000	2000	188	523				33				
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	21042	Argos Doppler	F	A	35	2000-02-02	2000-04-02	3	2	4	1	2000	2000	139	523				33				
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	21043	Argos Doppler	F	A	36	2001-02-13	2001-05-20	4	2	5	1	2001	2001	188	523				33				
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	21044	Argos Doppler	F	A	47	2001-02-14	2001-06-08	5	2	6	1	2001	2001	188	523				33				
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	26613	Argos Doppler	F	A	94	1996-01-17	1996-05-18	5	1	5	1	1996	1996	188	523	414			33				
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	29359	Argos Doppler	F	A	60	2002-01-15	2002-03-15	3	1	3	1	2002	2002	188	523				33				
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	151811	Argos Doppler	J		52	2016-02-10	2016-07-04	5	2	7	1	2016	2016	162	536				2			34	
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	151812	Argos Doppler	J		5	2016-03-18	2016-03-22	1	3	3	1	2016	2016	162	536				2			34	
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	151813	Argos Doppler	J		83	2017-04-29	2017-08-11	5	4	8	1	2017	2017	162	536				2			34	
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	170459	Argos Doppler	J		73	2017-09-07	2017-11-23	3	9	11	1	2017	2017	162	536				2			34	
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	131966	Argos Doppler	J		47	2014-06-25	2014-08-10	3	6	8	1	2014	2014	162	536				2			34	
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	131967	Argos Doppler	J		18	2016-05-20	2016-06-06	2	5	6	1	2016	2016	162	536				2			34	
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	131984	Argos Doppler	J		52	2015-09-19	2015-11-11	3	9	11	1	2015	2015	162	536				2			34	
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	131985	Argos Doppler	J		205	2015-11-20	2016-09-10	10	1	12	2	2015	2016	162	536				2			34	

Species	Tag ID	Sensor	Sex	Age class	Days	Start date	End date	Months	Start month	End month	Years	Start year	End year	Start marID	CiteID1	CiteID2	CiteID3	CiteID4	ProvID1	ProvID2	ProvID3	ProvID4	ProvID5
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	107887	Argos Doppler	F	A	138	2013-01-17	2013-06-05	6	1	6	1	2013	2013	188	758								49
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	107889	Argos Doppler	F	A	83	2013-01-14	2015-04-03	4	1	4	2	2013	2015	188	758								49
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	107892	Argos Doppler	F	A	20	2013-01-14	2013-02-02	2	1	2	1	2013	2013	188	758								49
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	1079011	Argos Doppler	F	A	33	2011-11-11	2011-12-13	2	11	12	1	2011	2011	188	758								49
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	1079012	Argos Doppler	F	A	148	2012-01-10	2012-06-05	6	1	6	1	2012	2012	188	758								49
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	107902	Argos Doppler	F	A	46	2011-11-15	2011-12-30	2	11	12	1	2011	2011	188	758								49
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	107903	Argos Doppler	F	A	19	2011-12-12	2011-12-30	1	12	12	1	2011	2011	139	758								49
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	107904	Argos Doppler	F	A	112	2012-01-10	2012-05-01	5	1	5	1	2012	2012	188	758								49
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	107905	Argos Doppler	F	A	121	2012-01-23	2012-05-23	5	1	5	1	2012	2012	188	758								49
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	1079061	Argos Doppler	F	A	128	2012-01-26	2012-06-08	6	1	6	1	2012	2012	140	758								49
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	1079062	Argos Doppler	F	A	144	2012-12-29	2013-05-30	6	1	12	2	2012	2013	188	758								49
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	107908	Argos Doppler	F	A	116	2012-02-14	2012-06-09	5	2	6	1	2012	2012	188	758								49
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	107909	Argos Doppler	F	A	87	2012-02-28	2012-05-24	4	2	5	1	2012	2012	188	758								49
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	107910	Argos Doppler	F	A	126	2012-02-28	2012-09-22	7	2	9	1	2012	2012	188	758								49
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	107913	Argos Doppler	F	A	106	2013-02-13	2013-05-29	4	2	5	1	2013	2013	188	758								49
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	107914	Argos Doppler	F	A	111	2013-01-25	2013-05-15	5	1	5	1	2013	2013	188	758								49
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	107915	Argos Doppler	F	A	83	2013-01-25	2015-04-14	4	1	4	2	2013	2015	188	758								49
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	377951	Argos Doppler	F	A	44	2013-01-05	2013-02-23	2	1	2	1	2013	2013	188	758								49
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	377952	Argos Doppler	F	A	61	2013-02-16	2013-04-17	3	2	4	1	2013	2013	188	758								49
<i>Dermodochelys coriacea</i>	37801	Argos Doppler	F	A	64	2013-02-02	2013-04-06	3	2	4	1	2013	2013	188	758								49
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	120597	Argos Doppler	J		49	2013-07-26	2013-09-24	3	7	9	1	2013	2013	161	19								3
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	121983	Argos Doppler	J		20	2014-10-05	2015-01-11	4	1	12	2	2014	2015	33	19								3
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	121984	Argos Doppler	J		66	2014-10-05	2015-02-08	5	1	12	2	2014	2015	33	19								3
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	121985	Argos Doppler	J		16	2013-03-23	2014-04-19	2	3	4	2	2013	2014	33	19								3
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	121986	Argos Doppler	J		4	2013-03-07	2014-04-09	2	3	4	2	2013	2014	33	19								3
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	126736	Argos Doppler	S		152	2017-09-20	2018-04-30	8	1	12	2	2017	2018	161	19								3
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	131466	Argos Doppler	M	A	60	2014-10-17	2014-12-29	3	10	12	1	2014	2014	37	20								3
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	131468	Argos Doppler	S		268	2016-09-26	2017-09-03	12	1	12	2	2016	2017	161	19								3
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	131893	Argos Doppler	J		15	2014-04-26	2014-06-16	3	4	6	1	2014	2014	136	339					30	50		60
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	131894	Argos Doppler	J		10	2013-09-16	2014-01-05	5	1	12	2	2013	2014	136	339					30	50		60
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	150546	Argos Doppler	F	A	636	2015-07-19	2018-07-29	12	1	12	4	2015	2018	134	339					30	50		60
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	161234	Argos Doppler	F	A	88	2016-12-19	2018-07-17	12	1	12	3	2016	2018	136	339					30	50		60
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	161233	Argos Doppler	F	A	46	2018-04-16	2018-08-12	5	4	8	1	2018	2018	136	339					30	50		60
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	44362b	Argos Doppler	J		6	2012-07-29	2012-09-19	3	7	9	1	2012	2012	136	338					30	50		60
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	55608	Argos Doppler	F	A	46	2005-02-09	2006-01-18	12	1	12	2	2005	2006	19	543								32
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	55609	Argos Doppler	F	A	5	2005-02-07	2005-02-21	1	2	2	1	2005	2005	19	543								32
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	55610	Argos Doppler	F	A	97	2005-02-06	2005-10-22	9	2	10	1	2005	2005	19	543								32
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	55611	Argos Doppler	F	A	97	2005-02-07	2005-10-03	9	2	10	1	2005	2005	19	543								32
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	55612	Argos Doppler	F	A	91	2005-02-10	2005-12-25	11	2	12	1	2005	2005	19	543								32
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	55613	Argos Doppler	F	A	15	2005-02-10	2005-02-28	1	2	2	1	2005	2005	19	543								32
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	55614	Argos Doppler	F	A	8	2005-02-11	2005-03-20	2	2	3	1	2005	2005	19	543								32
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	55615	Argos Doppler	F	A	127	2005-02-17	2007-03-06	12	1	12	3	2005	2007	19	543								32
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	55616	Argos Doppler	F	A	106	2005-02-12	2007-01-26	12	1	12	3	2005	2007	19	543								32
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	55617	Argos Doppler	F	A	161	2005-02-12	2006-07-24	12	1	12	2	2005	2006	19	543								32
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	55618	Argos Doppler	F	A	35	2005-02-23	2005-04-19	3	2	4	1	2005	2005	19	543								32
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	55619	Argos Doppler	F	A	8	2005-02-26	2005-03-12	2	2	3	1	2005	2005	19	543								32
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	55620	Argos Doppler	F	A	131	2005-02-28	2006-07-07	12	1	12	2	2005	2006	19	543								32
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	55621	Argos Doppler	F	A	110	2005-02-27	2007-03-04	12	1	12	3	2005	2007	19	543								32
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	55622a	Argos Doppler	F	A	34	2005-03-28	2005-10-19	8	3	10	1	2005	2005	19	543								32
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	138423	Argos Doppler	J		44	2015-12-01	2016-02-03	3	1	12	2	2015	2016	57	552								38
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	138425	Argos Doppler	J		107	2015-11-11	2016-05-15	7	1	12	2	2015	2016	57	552								38
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	138428	Argos Doppler	J		86	2015-11-18	2016-04-25	6	1	12	2	2015	2016	57	552								38
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	138429	Argos Doppler	J		44	2015-12-04	2016-01-16	2	1	12	2	2015	2016	57	552								38
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	138430	Argos Doppler	J		123	2015-11-20	2016-05-21	7	1	12	2	2015	2016	57	552								38
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	15496	Argos Doppler	J		3	1998-10-02	1998-12-23	2	10	12	1	1998	1998	39	580			579					40
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	15497	Argos Doppler	J		23	1999-10-24	2000-07-29	10	1	12	2	1999	2000	39	580			579					40
<i>Eretmodochelys imbricata</i>	15498	Argos Doppler	J		33	1998-11-20	2000-05-27	8	1	12	3	1998	2000	39	580			579					40

Species	Tag ID	Sensor	Sex	Age class	Days	Start date	End date	Months	Start month	End month	Years	Start year	End year	Start marID	CiteID1	CiteID2	CiteID3	CiteID4	ProvID1	ProvID2	ProvID3	ProvID4	ProvID5
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	15499	Argos Doppler			15	1999-09-23	1999-11-07	3	9	11	1	1999	1999	39	580	579	269					40	
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	15500	Argos Doppler			60	1998-11-08	1999-10-08	10	1	12	2	1998	1999	39	580	579	269					40	
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	20388	Argos Doppler			55	1999-10-30	2000-12-14	11	1	12	2	1999	2000	39	580	579	269					40	
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	20414	Argos Doppler			39	1999-12-05	2001-03-18	9	3	12	3	1999	2001	39	580	579	269					40	
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	20415	Argos Doppler			14	1999-11-22	2000-01-28	3	1	12	2	1999	2000	39	580	579	269					40	
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	27241	Argos Doppler			21	1997-03-25	1998-07-23	4	3	7	2	1997	1998	39	580	579	269					40	
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	27242	Argos Doppler			5	1997-03-21	1997-11-24	4	3	11	1	1997	1997	41	580	579	269					40	
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	27243	Argos Doppler			11	1997-10-26	1998-05-27	3	5	11	2	1997	1998	39	580	579	269					40	
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	27245	Argos Doppler			7	1996-07-11	1998-08-09	3	7	12	3	1996	1998	41	580	579	269					40	
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	27246	Argos Doppler			2	1997-04-09	1997-04-17	1	4	4	1	1997	1997	41	580	579	269					40	
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	27248	Argos Doppler			29	1997-04-09	1997-12-07	4	4	12	1	1997	1997	41	580	579	269					40	
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	27249	Argos Doppler			26	1997-04-09	1998-01-10	5	1	12	2	1997	1998	41	580	579	269					40	
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	27250	Argos Doppler			2	1996-07-19	1996-07-22	1	7	7	1	1996	1996	41	580	579	269					40	
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	118975	Argos Doppler	F	A	418	2013-04-03	2014-06-18	12	1	12	2	2013	2014	146	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	118977	Argos Doppler	F	A	203	2013-04-02	2013-10-25	7	4	10	1	2013	2013	146	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	118978	Argos Doppler	F	A	126	2013-05-03	2013-09-06	5	5	9	1	2013	2013	145	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	118979	Argos Doppler	F	A	43	2013-05-04	2013-07-09	3	5	7	1	2013	2013	145	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	10511	Argos Doppler	F	A	113	1999-05-11	1999-11-28	7	5	11	1	1999	1999	215	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	10512	Argos Doppler	F	A	130	1999-05-11	2000-03-18	11	1	12	2	1999	2000	215	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	105834	Argos Doppler	F	A	124	2011-04-13	2011-10-11	7	4	10	1	2011	2011	146	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	105835	Argos Doppler	M	A	195	2011-04-16	2012-01-23	10	1	12	2	2011	2012	146	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	105836	Argos Doppler	F	A	18	2011-04-13	2011-05-04	2	4	5	1	2011	2011	146	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	105837	Argos Doppler	F	A	339	2011-04-14	2012-06-25	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	146	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	105838	Argos Doppler	F	A	31	2011-04-14	2011-06-21	3	4	6	1	2011	2011	146	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	105840	Argos Doppler	F	A	21	2011-04-18	2011-06-03	3	4	6	1	2011	2011	145	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	105841	Argos Doppler	F	A	177	2011-04-20	2011-12-26	9	4	12	1	2011	2011	145	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	105842	Argos Doppler	F	A	287	2011-04-21	2012-05-24	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	215	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	105843	Argos Doppler	F	A	287	2011-04-21	2012-12-28	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	215	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	105844	Argos Doppler	F	A	443	2011-04-20	2013-05-05	12	1	12	3	2011	2013	215	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	105845	Argos Doppler	F	A	201	2011-05-01	2012-04-16	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	171	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	105846	Argos Doppler	F	A	88	2011-04-29	2011-09-26	6	4	9	1	2011	2011	171	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	105847	Argos Doppler	F	A	81	2011-04-29	2011-08-29	5	4	8	1	2011	2011	171	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	105848	Argos Doppler	F	A	426	2011-05-01	2012-12-12	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	171	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	105849	Argos Doppler	F	A	267	2011-04-28	2013-04-21	12	1	12	3	2011	2013	171	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	105850	Argos Doppler	F	A	128	2011-05-03	2012-11-25	8	5	12	2	2011	2012	215	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	105851	Argos Doppler	F	A	59	2011-05-03	2011-08-19	4	5	8	1	2011	2011	215	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	105852	Argos Doppler	F	A	436	2011-05-09	2012-12-04	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	215	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	105853	Argos Doppler	F	A	383	2011-05-09	2012-09-04	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	215	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	105854	Argos Doppler	F	A	446	2011-05-10	2013-02-20	12	1	12	3	2011	2013	91	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	105855	Argos Doppler	F	A	105	2011-05-09	2011-09-06	5	5	9	1	2011	2011	91	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	105856	Argos Doppler	F	A	304	2011-05-09	2012-08-03	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	91	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	105857	Argos Doppler	F	A	297	2011-05-09	2012-06-04	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	91	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	105858	Argos Doppler	F	A	126	2011-05-10	2011-11-11	7	5	11	1	2011	2011	91	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115249	Argos Doppler	F	A	171	2012-04-19	2012-12-12	9	4	12	1	2012	2012	146	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115250	Argos Doppler	F	A	153	2012-04-19	2012-12-06	9	4	12	1	2012	2012	146	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115251	Argos Doppler	F	A	268	2012-04-18	2013-03-28	12	1	12	2	2012	2013	146	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115252	Argos Doppler	F	A	112	2012-04-19	2012-09-06	6	4	9	1	2012	2012	146	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115253	Argos Doppler	F	A	167	2012-04-19	2012-12-18	9	4	12	1	2012	2012	146	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115254	Argos Doppler	F	A	58	2012-04-21	2012-12-11	7	4	12	1	2012	2012	145	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115255	Argos Doppler	F	A	195	2012-04-21	2013-01-10	10	1	12	2	2012	2013	145	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115256	Argos Doppler	F	A	92	2012-04-21	2012-08-26	5	4	8	1	2012	2012	145	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115257	Argos Doppler	F	A	54	2012-04-22	2012-07-07	4	4	7	1	2012	2012	145	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115258	Argos Doppler	F	A	94	2012-04-24	2012-09-04	6	4	9	1	2012	2012	145	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115259	Argos Doppler	F	A	293	2012-04-26	2013-05-06	12	1	12	2	2012	2013	215	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115260	Argos Doppler	F	A	223	2012-05-02	2013-04-30	12	1	12	2	2012	2013	215	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115261	Argos Doppler	F	A	267	2012-05-03	2013-05-08	12	1	12	2	2012	2013	215	683	685						4	44
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115262	Argos Doppler	F	A	100	2012-05-03	2012-09-01	5	5	9	1	2012	2012	215	683	685						4	44

Species	Tag ID	Sensor	Sex	Age class	Days	Start date	End date	Months	Start month	End month	Years	Start year	End year	Start marID	CiteID1	CiteID2	CiteID3	CiteID4	ProvID1	ProvID2	ProvID3	ProvID4	ProvID5
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115263	Argos Doppler	F	A	213	2012-05-03	2013-05-08	12	1	12	2	2012	2013	215	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115264	Argos Doppler	F	A	136	2012-05-06	2012-11-27	7	5	11	1	2012	2012	171	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115265	Argos Doppler	F	A	158	2012-05-06	2013-03-23	10	1	12	2	2012	2013	171	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115266	Argos Doppler	F	A	210	2012-05-06	2013-05-07	12	1	12	2	2012	2013	171	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115267	Argos Doppler	F	A	199	2012-05-08	2013-05-09	12	1	12	2	2012	2013	171	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115268	Argos Doppler	F	A	159	2012-05-09	2013-01-21	9	1	12	2	2012	2013	171	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115269	Argos Doppler	F	A	192	2012-05-10	2013-01-07	9	1	12	2	2012	2013	171	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115270	Argos Doppler	F	A	79	2012-05-09	2012-09-23	5	5	9	1	2012	2012	171	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115271	Argos Doppler	F	A	9	2012-05-23	2012-06-03	2	5	6	1	2012	2012	215	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115272	Argos Doppler	F	A	246	2012-05-23	2013-05-08	12	1	12	2	2012	2013	215	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115273	Argos Doppler	F	A	111	2012-05-24	2013-05-03	12	1	12	2	2012	2013	215	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115274	Argos Doppler	F	A	248	2012-05-23	2013-05-08	12	1	12	2	2012	2013	215	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115275	Argos Doppler	F	A	214	2012-05-23	2013-05-07	12	1	12	2	2012	2013	215	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115276	Argos Doppler	F	A	234	2012-05-23	2013-05-08	12	1	12	2	2012	2013	215	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115277	Argos Doppler	F	A	238	2012-05-23	2013-05-08	12	1	12	2	2012	2013	215	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115278	Argos Doppler	F	A	197	2012-05-26	2013-03-27	11	1	12	2	2012	2013	215	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	115279	Argos Doppler	F	A	247	2012-05-26	2013-05-08	12	1	12	2	2012	2013	215	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	118976	Argos Doppler	F	A	77	2012-06-01	2012-09-14	4	6	9	1	2012	2012	145	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	119857	Argos Doppler	F	A	346	2012-05-15	2013-08-07	12	1	12	2	2012	2013	171	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	119858	Argos Doppler	F	A	243	2012-05-16	2013-04-29	12	1	12	2	2012	2013	171	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	119859	Argos Doppler	F	A	67	2012-05-19	2012-08-11	4	5	8	1	2012	2012	171	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	119860	Argos Doppler	F	A	390	2012-05-19	2013-08-08	12	1	12	2	2012	2013	171	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	119861	Argos Doppler	F	A	224	2012-05-15	2013-06-05	12	1	12	2	2012	2013	171	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	52975	Argos Doppler	F	A	548	2010-04-18	2013-05-05	12	1	12	4	2010	2013	91	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	52976	Argos Doppler	F	A	318	2010-04-19	2011-09-28	12	1	12	2	2010	2011	91	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	52977	Argos Doppler	F	A	107	2010-04-18	2010-09-19	6	4	9	1	2010	2010	91	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	52978	Argos Doppler	F	A	197	2010-04-18	2011-06-13	12	1	12	2	2010	2011	91	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	52979	Argos Doppler	F	A	162	2010-04-18	2011-07-30	12	1	12	2	2010	2011	91	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	52981	Argos Doppler	F	A	59	2010-05-07	2010-10-14	6	5	10	1	2010	2010	215	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	52982	Argos Doppler	F	A	370	2010-05-11	2012-04-26	12	1	12	3	2010	2012	215	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	52983	Argos Doppler	F	A	122	2010-05-11	2011-03-25	10	1	12	2	2010	2011	215	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	52984	Argos Doppler	F	A	110	2010-05-12	2010-11-16	7	5	11	1	2010	2010	215	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	52989	Argos Doppler	F	A	361	2010-05-10	2011-11-03	12	1	12	2	2010	2011	215	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	52999	Argos Doppler	F	A	82	2010-05-05	2011-03-02	11	1	12	2	2010	2011	146	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	53002	Argos Doppler	F	A	86	2010-05-05	2010-12-29	8	5	12	1	2010	2010	146	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	53003	Argos Doppler	F	A	31	2010-05-04	2010-07-08	3	5	7	1	2010	2010	146	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	53006	Argos Doppler	F	A	105	2010-05-02	2011-02-13	10	1	12	2	2010	2011	146	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	53009	Argos Doppler	F	A	56	2010-05-14	2011-01-23	8	1	12	2	2010	2011	171	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	53010	Argos Doppler	F	A	15	2010-05-20	2010-07-06	3	5	7	1	2010	2010	171	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	53011	Argos Doppler	F	A	100	2010-05-15	2011-07-20	10	1	12	2	2010	2011	171	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	53012	Argos Doppler	F	A	25	2010-05-03	2011-01-30	6	1	9	2	2010	2011	146	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	53013	Argos Doppler	F	A	138	2010-05-15	2011-05-10	11	1	12	2	2010	2011	171	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	53015	Argos Doppler	F	A	114	2010-05-15	2011-04-23	10	1	12	2	2010	2011	171	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	73008	Argos Doppler	F	A	332	2011-05-09	2012-08-17	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	171	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	73011	Argos Doppler	F	A	340	2011-05-04	2012-07-13	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	171	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	73014	Argos Doppler	F	A	154	2011-05-08	2011-11-06	7	5	11	1	2011	2011	171	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	73015	Argos Doppler	F	A	404	2011-05-13	2012-11-11	12	1	12	2	2011	2012	171	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	73016	Argos Doppler	F	A	113	2011-05-21	2011-10-18	6	5	10	1	2011	2011	171	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	74305a	Argos Doppler	F	A	92	2007-05-15	2007-12-30	8	5	12	1	2007	2007	146	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	74306a	Argos Doppler	F	A	53	2007-05-13	2007-09-20	5	5	9	1	2007	2007	146	683	685			4		44		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	133606	Argos Doppler	M	A	86	2014-03-11	2014-06-19	4	3	6	1	2014	2014	171	682					44			
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	133614	Argos Doppler	F	J	80	2014-03-13	2014-06-11	4	3	6	1	2014	2014	171	682					44			
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	142841	Argos Doppler	F	J	42	2015-03-11	2015-06-01	3	3	6	1	2015	2015	171	682					44			
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	142842	Argos Doppler	M	J	81	2015-03-15	2015-06-21	4	3	6	1	2015	2015	171	682					44			
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	142846	Argos Doppler	M	J	3	2015-03-27	2015-04-07	2	3	4	1	2015	2015	171	682					44			
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	80007a	Argos Doppler	F	A	59	2008-10-07	2010-05-19	9	1	12	3	2008	2010	46	361	744					56		
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	80008a	Argos Doppler	F	A	528	2008-10-28	2010-09-25	12	1	12	3	2008	2010	46	361	744					56		

Species	Tag ID	Sensor	Sex	Age class	Days	Start date	End date	Months	Start month	End month	Years	Start year	End year	Start marID	CiteID1	CiteID2	CiteID3	CiteID4	ProvID1	ProvID2	ProvID3	ProvID4	ProvID5	
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	80009a	Argos Doppler	F	A	10	2008-12-23	2009-01-02	2	1	12	2	2008	2009	46	361	744							56	
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	80010a	Argos Doppler	F	A	230	2008-09-19	2009-11-30	12	1	12	2	2008	2009	46	361	744								56
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	80011a	Argos Doppler	F	A	23	2008-08-12	2008-10-03	3	8	10	1	2008	2008	46	361	744								56
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	80012a	Argos Doppler	F	A	210	2008-11-03	2009-11-02	12	1	12	2	2008	2009	46	361	744								56
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	85701a	Argos Doppler	F	A	784	2008-08-29	2012-03-22	12	1	12	5	2008	2012	46	361	744								56
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	85702a	Argos Doppler	F	A	924	2008-08-30	2011-08-15	12	1	12	4	2008	2011	46	361	744								56
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	85703a	Argos Doppler	F	A	114	2009-08-07	2009-12-22	5	8	12	1	2009	2009	46	361	744								56
<i>Eretmochelys imbricata</i>	85704a	Argos Doppler	F	A	624	2009-02-06	2012-01-15	12	1	12	4	2009	2012	46	361	744								56
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	159775	Global Positioning System	J		10	2016-05-09	2016-05-18	1	5	5	1	2016	2016	217	934	935								18 58
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	159777	Argos Doppler; Global Positioning System	J		57	2016-05-12	2016-07-10	3	5	7	1	2016	2016	217	934	935								18 58
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	159779	Argos Doppler; Global Positioning System	J		63	2016-05-09	2016-07-12	3	5	7	1	2016	2016	217	934	935								18 58
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	159780	Argos Doppler; Global Positioning System	J		55	2016-05-08	2016-07-02	3	5	7	1	2016	2016	217	934	935								18 58
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	159782	Argos Doppler; Global Positioning System	J		12	2016-05-09	2016-05-20	1	5	5	1	2016	2016	217	934	935								18 58
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	101217a	Argos Doppler		J	164	2010-10-20	2011-04-13	7	1	12	2	2010	2011	98	388									27
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	142187b	Argos Doppler		J	59	2014-10-10	2015-01-27	4	1	12	2	2014	2015	100	388									27
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	159707	Argos Doppler			52	2017-05-20	2017-07-19	3	5	7	1	2017	2017	218	51									14 31
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	169763	Argos Doppler			29	2017-06-09	2017-07-07	2	6	7	1	2017	2017	218	51									14 31
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	169764	Argos Doppler			36	2017-06-17	2017-07-25	2	6	7	1	2017	2017	218	50									14 31
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	169765	Argos Doppler			64	2017-05-20	2017-07-31	3	5	7	1	2017	2017	218	51									14 31
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	169767	Argos Doppler			27	2017-05-06	2017-07-02	3	5	7	1	2017	2017	218	50									14 31
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	169768	Argos Doppler			44	2017-05-20	2017-07-03	3	5	7	1	2017	2017	218	51									14 31
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	169769	Argos Doppler			26	2018-05-27	2018-06-26	2	5	6	1	2018	2018	218	50									14 31
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	169770	Argos Doppler			12	2017-07-12	2017-07-31	1	7	7	1	2017	2017	218	50									14 31
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	169771	Argos Doppler			21	2017-06-01	2017-06-21	1	6	6	1	2017	2017	218	51									14 31
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	175216	Argos Doppler			37	2018-05-19	2018-07-03	3	5	7	1	2018	2018	218	50									14 31
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	175218	Argos Doppler			35	2018-05-19	2018-06-25	2	5	6	1	2018	2018	218	50									14 31
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	175219	Argos Doppler			49	2018-05-27	2018-07-18	3	5	7	1	2018	2018	218	50									14 31
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	175220	Argos Doppler			15	2018-06-22	2018-07-07	2	6	7	1	2018	2018	218	50									14 31
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	175221	Argos Doppler			63	2018-05-27	2018-07-30	3	5	7	1	2018	2018	218	50									14 31
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	175222	Argos Doppler			21	2018-06-07	2018-07-02	2	6	7	1	2018	2018	218	50									14 31
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	175714	Argos Doppler			8	2018-08-12	2018-08-23	1	8	8	1	2018	2018	218	50									14 31
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	VAQR201505	Argos Doppler			19	2015-05-31	2015-07-10	3	5	7	1	2015	2015	218	50									14 31
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	VAQS20112010	Argos Doppler			8	2011-06-30	2011-07-09	2	6	7	1	2011	2011	218	506									14 31
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	VAQS20122175	Argos Doppler			17	2013-06-22	2013-07-12	2	6	7	1	2013	2013	218	506									14 31
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	VAQS20132227	Argos Doppler			97	2014-10-21	2015-06-06	8	1	12	2	2014	2015	218	506									14 31
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	VAQS20132229	Argos Doppler			11	2014-07-16	2014-08-15	2	7	8	1	2014	2014	218	506									14 31
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	VAQS20142152	Argos Doppler			8	2014-09-05	2014-10-10	2	9	10	1	2014	2014	218	506									14 31
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	VAQS20142244	Argos Doppler			29	2015-05-19	2015-07-14	3	5	7	1	2015	2015	218	50									14 31
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	VAQS20152008	Argos Doppler			4	2015-05-19	2015-06-07	2	5	6	1	2015	2015	218	50									14 31
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	VAQS20152049	Argos Doppler			9	2015-06-26	2015-07-05	2	6	7	1	2015	2015	218	50									14 31
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	VAQS20162016	Argos Doppler			12	2016-08-01	2016-08-27	1	8	8	1	2016	2016	218	50									14 31
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	VAQS20162029	Argos Doppler			28	2016-07-22	2016-08-26	2	7	8	1	2016	2016	218	50									14 31
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	VAQS20162089	Argos Doppler			9	2016-07-06	2016-08-05	2	7	8	1	2016	2016	218	50									14 31
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	15029a	Argos Doppler	F	A	16	2005-05-17	2005-06-29	2	5	6	1	2005	2005	217	810	809								53
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	15031a	Argos Doppler	F	A	5	2005-06-02	2005-06-17	1	6	6	1	2005	2005	217	810	809								53
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	41113a	Argos Doppler	J	A	19	2007-08-14	2007-12-12	3	8	12	1	2007	2007	217	810									53
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	53223a	Argos Doppler	J	A	9	2004-09-21	2004-11-16	3	9	11	1	2004	2004	217	810									53
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	58952a	Argos Doppler	J	A	9	2005-07-25	2005-08-05	2	7	8	1	2005	2005	217	810									53

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<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	58953a	Argos Doppler		J	19	2005-08-04	2005-09-02	2	8	9	1	2005	2005	217	810								53
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	59209a	Argos Doppler		J	25	2005-05-27	2005-07-07	3	5	7	1	2005	2005	217	810								53
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	59210a	Argos Doppler	F	A	30	2005-05-31	2005-07-19	3	5	7	1	2005	2005	217	810	809							53
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	59950a	Argos Doppler		J	15	2005-09-07	2005-10-16	2	9	10	1	2005	2005	217	810								53
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	59977a	Argos Doppler		J	14	2006-04-17	2006-05-06	2	4	5	1	2006	2006	217	810								53
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	59978a	Argos Doppler		J	49	2006-04-25	2006-06-20	3	4	6	1	2006	2006	217	810								53
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	64883a	Argos Doppler	F	A	75	2006-04-29	2006-09-22	6	4	9	1	2006	2006	217	810	809							53
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	64884a	Argos Doppler	F	A	76	2006-05-08	2006-08-01	4	5	8	1	2006	2006	217	810	809							53
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	66226a	Argos Doppler	F	A	101	2006-05-28	2006-10-05	6	5	10	1	2006	2006	217	810	809							53
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	67840a	Argos Doppler		J	25	2006-07-28	2006-09-10	3	7	9	1	2006	2006	217	810								53
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	67841a	Argos Doppler	F	A	134	2006-08-17	2007-05-19	10	1	12	2	2006	2007	217	810								53
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	67842a	Argos Doppler		J	6	2007-04-23	2007-06-12	2	4	6	1	2007	2007	217	810								53
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	74904a	Argos Doppler		J	30	2007-04-23	2007-08-06	5	4	8	1	2007	2007	217	810								53
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	74905a	Argos Doppler		J	29	2007-05-02	2007-07-11	3	5	7	1	2007	2007	217	810								53
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	75422a	Argos Doppler		J	7	2007-05-15	2007-06-20	2	5	6	1	2007	2007	217	810								53
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	75423a	Argos Doppler		J	18	2007-07-12	2007-09-05	3	7	9	1	2007	2007	217	810								53
<i>Lepidochelys kempii</i>	75424a	Argos Doppler		J	5	2007-07-15	2007-07-22	1	7	7	1	2007	2007	217	810								53
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	131469	Argos Doppler	F	A	41	2013-11-03	2013-12-14	2	11	12	1	2013	2013	33	19								3
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	19584_97	Argos Doppler			111	1997-09-04	1998-03-16	7	1	12	2	1997	1998	216	695	698	697			5	42	45	
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	19588_97	Argos Doppler			69	1997-06-02	1997-08-22	3	6	8	1	1997	1997	216	695	698	697			5	42	45	
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	19589_97	Argos Doppler			31	1997-08-14	1997-09-21	2	8	9	1	1997	1997	216	695	698	697			5	42	45	
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	19592_98	Argos Doppler			164	1998-04-06	1998-11-10	8	4	11	1	1998	1998	77	695	698	697			5	42	45	
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	19595_97	Argos Doppler			27	1997-09-15	1997-11-16	3	9	11	1	1997	1997	77	695	698	697			5	42	45	
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	19603_99	Argos Doppler			22	1999-08-19	2000-03-26	8	1	12	2	1999	2000	216	695	698	697			5	42	45	
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	22532_99	Argos Doppler			10	1999-08-17	1999-09-10	2	8	9	1	1999	1999	216	695	698	697			5	42	45	
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	22533_00	Argos Doppler			22	2000-07-20	2000-10-03	4	7	10	1	2000	2000	216	695	698	697			5	42	45	
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	25314_99	Argos Doppler			16	1999-06-18	1999-09-17	4	6	9	1	1999	1999	216	695	698	697			5	42	45	
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	25315_00	Argos Doppler			81	2000-02-23	2000-06-17	5	2	6	1	2000	2000	216	695	698	697			5	42	45	
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	60778	Argos Doppler	F	A	11	2006-02-02	2006-02-14	1	2	2	1	2006	2006	19	212								32
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	60779	Argos Doppler	F	A	27	2006-02-03	2006-03-05	2	2	3	1	2006	2006	19	212								32
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	60780	Argos Doppler	F	A	122	2006-02-04	2006-12-01	11	2	12	1	2006	2006	19	212								32
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	60781	Argos Doppler	F	A	65	2006-02-05	2006-07-08	6	2	7	1	2006	2006	19	212								32
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	60782	Argos Doppler	F	A	60	2006-02-07	2006-04-13	3	2	4	1	2006	2006	19	212								32
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	60783	Argos Doppler	F	A	58	2006-02-08	2006-04-30	3	2	4	1	2006	2006	19	212								32
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	60784	Argos Doppler	F	A	71	2006-02-11	2006-07-05	6	2	7	1	2006	2006	19	212								32
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	60786	Argos Doppler	F	A	52	2006-02-18	2006-05-06	4	2	5	1	2006	2006	19	212								32
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	60787	Argos Doppler	F	A	86	2006-04-05	2006-08-16	5	4	8	1	2006	2006	19	212								32
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	122955a	Argos Doppler	F	A	119	2012-10-26	2013-02-22	5	1	12	2	2012	2013	57	214	675							37
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	122956a	Argos Doppler	F	A	59	2012-10-28	2012-12-31	3	10	12	1	2012	2012	57	214	675							37
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	122957a	Argos Doppler	F	A	149	2012-10-30	2013-03-28	6	1	12	2	2012	2013	57	214	675							37
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	122958	Argos Doppler	F	A	394	2012-11-01	2013-11-30	12	1	12	2	2012	2013	57	214	675							37
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	122959a	Argos Doppler	F	A	78	2012-11-02	2013-01-20	3	1	12	2	2012	2013	57	214	675							37
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	122960	Argos Doppler	F	A	390	2012-11-06	2013-12-03	12	1	12	2	2012	2013	57	214	675							37
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	132997a	Argos Doppler	F	A	157	2013-10-13	2014-03-20	6	1	12	2	2013	2014	57	214	675							37
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	132998a	Argos Doppler	F	A	170	2013-10-13	2014-04-04	7	1	12	2	2013	2014	57	214	675							37
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	132999a	Argos Doppler	F	A	111	2013-10-13	2014-01-31	4	1	12	2	2013	2014	57	214	675							37
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	133000a	Argos Doppler	F	A	199	2013-10-13	2014-05-02	8	1	12	2	2013	2014	57	214	675							37
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	133002a	Argos Doppler	F	A	193	2013-10-13	2014-04-27	7	1	12	2	2013	2014	57	214	675							37
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	133003a	Argos Doppler	F	A	17	2013-11-08	2013-11-29	1	11	11	1	2013	2013	58	214	675							37
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	133004a	Argos Doppler	F	A	95	2013-10-17	2014-01-23	4	1	12	2	2013	2014	58	214	675							37
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	13361	Argos Doppler	F	A	79	2008-11-15	2009-02-01	4	1	12	2	2008	2009	58	214	675							37
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	13362	Argos Doppler	F	A	160	2008-11-14	2009-04-22	6	1	12	2	2008	2009	58	214	675							37
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	133714a	Argos Doppler	F	A	69	2013-11-17	2014-01-25	3	1	12	2	2013	2014	58	214	675							37
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	133715a	Argos Doppler	F	A	122	2013-11-19	2014-03-21	5	1	12	2	2013	2014	58	214	675							37
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	133716a	Argos Doppler	F	A	129	2013-11-18	2014-03-30	5	1	12	2	2013	2014	58	214	675							37
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	133717	Argos Doppler	F	A	58	2015-01-01	2015-02-28	2	1	2	1	2015	2015	58	214	675							37
<i>Lepidochelys olivacea</i>	133718	Argos Doppler	F	A	53	2014-10-12	2014-12-03	3	10	12	1	2014	2014	58	214	675							37

Species	Tag ID	Sensor	Sex	Age class	Days	Start date	End date	Months	Start month	End month	Years	Start year	End year	Start marID	CiteID1	CiteID2	CiteID3	CiteID4	ProvID1	ProvID2	ProvID3	ProvID4	ProvID5
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	141641	Argos Doppler	F	A	35	2014-10-11	2014-12-09	3	10	12	1	2014	2014	58	214	675			36	37			
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	141642	Argos Doppler	F	A	4	2014-10-18	2014-11-07	2	10	11	1	2014	2014	58	214	675			36	37			
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	141643	Argos Doppler	F	A	53	2014-10-15	2014-12-16	3	10	12	1	2014	2014	58	214	675			36	37			
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	141644	Argos Doppler	F	A	22	2014-10-14	2014-11-10	2	10	11	1	2014	2014	58	214	675			36	37			
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	14750	Argos Doppler	F	A	161	2008-11-13	2009-04-22	6	1	12	2	2008	2009	58	214	675			36	37			
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	14755	Argos Doppler	F	A	9	2008-11-06	2008-11-14	1	11	11	1	2008	2008	58	214	675			36	37			
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	152853	Argos Doppler	F	A	106	2015-10-28	2016-02-15	5	1	12	2	2015	2016	57	214	675			36	37			
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	152854	Argos Doppler	F	A	36	2015-10-28	2015-12-08	3	10	12	1	2015	2015	57	214	675			36	37			
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	152855	Argos Doppler	F	A	83	2015-10-28	2016-01-31	4	1	12	2	2015	2016	57	214	675			36	37			
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	152856	Argos Doppler	F	A	65	2015-10-30	2016-01-05	4	1	12	2	2015	2016	57	214	675			36	37			
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	152857	Argos Doppler	F	A	38	2015-10-30	2015-12-16	3	10	12	1	2015	2015	57	214	675			36	37			
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	152858	Argos Doppler	F	A	65	2015-10-27	2016-01-28	4	1	12	2	2015	2016	57	214	675			36	37			
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	152859	Argos Doppler	F	A	96	2015-10-27	2016-02-05	5	1	12	2	2015	2016	57	214	675			36	37			
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	152860	Argos Doppler	F	A	151	2015-10-27	2016-03-31	6	1	12	2	2015	2016	57	214	675			36	37			
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	152861	Argos Doppler	F	A	38	2015-10-31	2015-12-11	3	10	12	1	2015	2015	57	214	675			36	37			
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	152862	Argos Doppler	F	A	67	2015-10-31	2016-01-10	4	1	12	2	2015	2016	57	214	675			36	37			
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	23098	Argos Doppler	F	A	62	2008-11-16	2009-01-16	3	1	12	2	2008	2009	58	214	675			36	37			
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	23101	Argos Doppler	F	A	161	2008-11-12	2009-04-22	6	1	12	2	2008	2009	58	214	675			36	37			
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	23102	Argos Doppler	F	A	4	2008-10-22	2008-10-25	1	10	10	1	2008	2008	58	214	675			36	37			
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	26340	Argos Doppler	F	A	150	2008-11-15	2009-04-22	6	1	12	2	2008	2009	58	214	675			36	37			
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	28600	Argos Doppler	F	A	117	2008-11-14	2009-03-10	5	1	12	2	2008	2009	58	214	675			36	37			
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	57253	Argos Doppler	F	A	109	2008-11-15	2009-03-04	5	1	12	2	2008	2009	58	214	675			36	37			
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	72766	Argos Doppler	F	A	71	2008-12-19	2009-02-27	3	1	12	2	2008	2009	58	214	675			36	37			
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	72773	Argos Doppler	F	A	140	2008-12-04	2009-04-22	5	1	12	2	2008	2009	58	214	675			36	37			
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	72776	Argos Doppler	F	A	140	2008-12-04	2009-04-22	5	1	12	2	2008	2009	58	214	675			36	37			
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	79339	Argos Doppler	F	A	32	2007-11-07	2007-12-08	2	11	12	1	2007	2007	3	549			36	37				
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	79340	Argos Doppler	F	A	64	2007-11-07	2008-01-09	3	1	12	2	2007	2008	58	549			36	37				
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	79341	Argos Doppler	F	A	22	2007-11-07	2007-11-28	1	11	11	1	2007	2007	58	549			36	37				
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	79342	Argos Doppler	F	A	24	2007-11-09	2007-12-02	2	11	12	1	2007	2007	58	549			36	37				
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	79343	Argos Doppler	F	A	8	2007-11-08	2007-11-15	1	11	11	1	2007	2007	58	549			36	37				
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	82838a	Argos Doppler	F	A	67	2008-03-26	2008-06-09	4	3	6	1	2008	2008	145	723			47					
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	82839a	Argos Doppler	F	A	210	2008-03-27	2008-12-07	9	3	12	1	2008	2008	145	723			47					
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	82840a	Argos Doppler	F	A	241	2008-03-28	2009-02-05	12	1	12	2	2008	2009	145	723			47					
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	82841a	Argos Doppler	F	A	127	2008-03-29	2008-08-21	6	3	8	1	2008	2008	145	723			47					
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	82842a	Argos Doppler	F	A	143	2008-03-29	2008-09-23	7	3	9	1	2008	2008	145	723			47					
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	82843a	Argos Doppler	F	A	385	2008-03-31	2009-07-06	12	1	12	2	2008	2009	145	723			47					
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	82844a	Argos Doppler	F	A	157	2008-04-02	2008-12-17	9	4	12	1	2008	2008	145	723			47					
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	82882a	Argos Doppler	F	A	126	2008-03-28	2008-08-10	6	3	8	1	2008	2008	145	723			47					
<i>Lepidocheilus olivacea</i>	82883a	Argos Doppler	F	A	59	2008-03-30	2008-06-09	4	3	6	1	2008	2008	145	723			47					

Figure S2.6. Frequency histograms of the number of individuals and days tracked (grey boxes) and the empirical cumulative distribution function plot (red line) for a) all species, b) *Caretta caretta*, c) *Chelonia mydas*, d) *Dermochelys coriacea*, e) *Eretmochelys imbricata*, f) *Lepidochelys kempii*, and g) *Lepidochelys olivacea*.

Figure S2.7. Frequency histograms of the number of individuals and marine regions (grey boxes) and the empirical cumulative distribution function plot (red line) for a) all species, b) *Caretta caretta*, c) *Chelonia mydas*, d) *Dermochelys coriacea*, e) *Eretmochelys imbricata*, f) *Lepidochelys kempii*, and g) *Lepidochelys olivacea*.

Appendix S3. Marine region node details for each network. Marine regions were areas that varied in size, but were represented in the network as a single node or point in the center of the area. These nodes or points were not the specific locations of sea turtles and does not assume that all sea turtles were distributed evenly throughout the marine region.

Table S3.8. Summary of tracking data and centrality metrics for each marine region node. *Cc* = *Caretta caretta*, *Cm* = *Chelonia mydas*, *Dc* = *Dermochelys coriacea*; *Ei* = *Eretmochelys imbricata*, *Lk* = *Lepidochelys kempii*, *Lo* = *Lepidochelys olivacea*. All nodes were used to calculate closeness within region networks (tracking data and neighbours); nodes with links going out, only, were used to calculate closeness within species networks. Blanks = not calculated because no locations were recorded within the marine region and the node was not present in the network.

MarID	Marine region	Basin	Points (n)	Species (n)	Animals (n)						Node closeness								
					All spp.	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	Tracking data	Neighbours	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>
1	Albanian part of the Adriatic Sea	Mediterranean	527	1	16	16	0	0	0	0	0	0.002545	0.003831	0.000102					
2	Algerian part of the Mediterranean Sea - Western Basin	Mediterranean	353	1	6	6	0	0	0	0	0	0.002128	0.003236	0.000100					
3	Angolan part of the South Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	2,364	3	36	0	0	3	0	0	33	0.000327	0.000621			0.000198			0.001764
4	Anguilla part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	19	2	3	0	0	3	0	0	0	0.000314	0.000640			0.000269			
5	Antigua and Barbuda part of the Caribbean Sea	Atlantic	1	2	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0.000262	0.000538			0.000259			
6	Antigua and Barbuda part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	23	2	5	0	0	5	0	0	0	0.000316	0.000654			0.000273			
7	Argentinean part of the Rio de La Plata	Atlantic	655	3	15	6	8	1	0	0	0	0.000259	0.000502	0.000083	0.000112	0.000194			
8	Argentinean part of the South Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	499	3	13	3	8	2	0	0	0	0.000313	0.000628	0.000083	0.000112	0.000200			
9	Ascension part of the South Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	140	3	18	0	16	2	0	0	0	0.000322	0.000617		0.000113	0.000199			
10	Bahamas part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	491	3	5	2	0	1	2	0	0	0.000292	0.000667	0.000094		0.000154	0.000706		
11	Bahraini part of the Persian Gulf	Indian	1,413	3	22	0	8	0	14	0	0	0.000184	0.000329		0.000107		0.000649		
12	Barbados part of the Caribbean Sea	Atlantic	8	2	3	1	0	2	0	0	0	0.000267	0.000547	0.000078		0.000273			
13	Barbados part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	59	2	9	1	0	8	0	0	0	0.000323	0.000665	0.000078		0.000282			

MarID	Marine region	Basin	Points (n)	Species (n)	Animals (n)						Node closeness								
					All spp.	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	Tracking data	Neighbours	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>
14	Bassas da India part of the Mozambique Channel	Indian	2	2	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0.000249	0.000466			0.000196			
15	Belizean part of the Caribbean Sea	Atlantic	98	2	4	0	4	0	0	0	0	0.000196	0.000403		0.000108				
16	Bermudian part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	278	3	15	9	1	5	0	0	0	0.000323	0.000630	0.000094	0.000105	0.000273			
17	Brazilian (Trindade) part of the South Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	57	2	4	0	0	4	0	0	0	0.000308	0.000617			0.000199			
18	Brazilian part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	12	4	5	1	0	1	1	0	2	0.000394	0.000715	0.000083		0.000154	0.000576		0.001364
19	Brazilian part of the South Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	5,515	5	62	12	19	7	15	0	9	0.000350	0.000723	0.000083	0.000111	0.000200	0.000578		0.001721
20	British Virgin Islands part of the Caribbean Sea	Atlantic	3	2	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0.000266	0.000535			0.000257			
21	British Virgin Islands part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	7	2	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0.000311	0.000655			0.000256			
22	Bruneian part of the South China Sea	Pacific	3	2	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	0.000687	0.001221	0.000078	0.000118				
23	Cameroonian part of the Gulf of Guinea	Atlantic	13	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.000215	0.000421						0.001323
24	Canadian part of the Gulf of St. Lawrence	Atlantic	63	2	3	0	0	3	0	0	0	0.000269	0.000515			0.000263			
25	Canadian part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	253	2	13	4	0	9	0	0	0	0.000331	0.000654	0.000094		0.000274			
26	Cape Verdean part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	771	2	24	19	0	5	0	0	0	0.000312	0.000634	0.000094		0.000270			
27	Cayman Islands part of the Caribbean Sea	Atlantic	195	3	17	3	9	0	5	0	0	0.000222	0.000415	0.000080	0.000118		0.000767		

MarID	Marine region	Basin	Points (n)	Species (n)	Animals (n)							Node closeness							
					All spp.	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	Tracking data	Neighbours	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>
28	Chilean part of the South Pacific Ocean	Pacific	50	1	5	5	0	0	0	0	0	0.000532	0.001307	0.000079					
29	Chinese part of the Eastern China Sea	Pacific	470	1	21	21	0	0	0	0	0	0.001086	0.001821	0.000104					
30	Chinese part of the South China Sea	Pacific	170	1	13	13	0	0	0	0	0	0.000949	0.001736	0.000103					
31	Chinese part of the Yellow Sea	Pacific	49	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0.000847	0.001443	0.000103					
32	Colombian part of the Caribbean Sea	Atlantic	17	2	5	1	0	0	4	0	0	0.000213	0.000502	0.000080				0.000732	
33	Colombian part of the North Pacific Ocean	Pacific	116	4	6	0	1	0	4	0	1	0.000831	0.001610		0.000106		0.000554		0.001399
34	Comoran part of the Mozambique Channel	Indian	3	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.000250	0.000467		0.000106				
35	Congolese part of the South Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	561	3	45	0	0	10	0	0	35	0.000314	0.000627				0.000211		0.001812
36	Costa Rican part of the Caribbean Sea	Atlantic	1	2	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0.000178	0.000362				0.000655		
37	Costa Rican part of the North Pacific Ocean	Pacific	98	4	4	0	2	0	1	0	1	0.001065	0.001626		0.000108		0.000554		0.001323
38	Croatian part of the Adriatic Sea	Mediterranean	907	1	20	20	0	0	0	0	0	0.002558	0.003145	0.000102					
39	Cuban part of the Caribbean Sea	Atlantic	246	3	17	0	4	0	13	0	0	0.000258	0.000483		0.000116		0.000803		
40	Cuban part of the Gulf of Mexico	Atlantic	4	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.000296	0.000556		0.000109				
41	Cuban part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	17	2	7	0	0	0	7	0	0	0.000252	0.000563				0.000754		
42	Cypriote part of the Mediterranean Sea - Eastern Basin	Mediterranean	3,205	2	71	35	36	0	0	0	0	0.002933	0.004115	0.000102	0.000115				
43	Democratic Republic of the Congo part of the South Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	96	3	27	0	0	2	0	0	25	0.000310	0.000620				0.000202		0.001739
44	Dominican part of the Caribbean Sea	Atlantic	8	2	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	0.000227	0.000563				0.000259		

MarID	Marine region	Basin	Points (n)	Species (n)	Animals (n)						Node closeness								
					All spp.	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	Tracking data	Neighbours	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>
45	Dominican part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	9	2	6	0	0	6	0	0	0	0.000266	0.000542				0.000267		
46	Dominican Republic part of the Caribbean Sea	Atlantic	953	2	11	0	0	0	11	0	0	0.000277	0.000580				0.000776		
47	Dominican Republic part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	12	3	2	0	0	1	1	0	0	0.000321	0.000671				0.000267	0.000651	
48	Ecuadorian (Galapagos) part of the North Pacific Ocean	Pacific	22	3	6	0	5	1	0	0	0	0.001068	0.001642			0.000113	0.000154		
49	Ecuadorian (Galapagos) part of the South Pacific Ocean	Pacific	205	3	15	0	12	3	0	0	0	0.000859	0.001626			0.000112	0.000160		
50	Egyptian part of the Mediterranean Sea - Eastern Basin	Mediterranean	1,680	2	62	25	37	0	0	0	0	0.003165	0.004115	0.000102	0.000110				
51	El Salvador part of the North Pacific Ocean	Pacific	2	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.000824	0.001603		0.000106				
52	Equatorial Guinean part of the Gulf of Guinea	Atlantic	449	5	22	0	8	11	1	0	2	0.000252	0.000510		0.000106	0.000220	0.000566		0.001692
53	Equatorial Guinean part of the South Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	221	3	19	0	0	18	0	0	1	0.000327	0.000720			0.000201			0.001695
54	Eritrean part of the Red Sea	Indian	15	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.000172	0.000316		0.000105				
55	French part of the Tyrrhenian Sea	Mediterranean	10	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0.002105	0.003436	0.000101					
56	French Polynesian part of the South Pacific Ocean	Pacific	9	2	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0.000597	0.001302			0.000160			
57	Gabonese part of the Gulf of Guinea	Atlantic	2,486	5	55	0	10	18	5	0	22	0.000280	0.000565		0.000106	0.000221	0.000566		0.001805
58	Gabonese part of the South Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	1,322	3	72	0	0	26	0	0	46	0.000328	0.000631			0.000214			0.001835
59	Gambian part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	29	1	6	6	0	0	0	0	0	0.000269	0.000633	0.000094					

MarID	Marine region	Basin	Points (n)	Species (n)	Animals (n)							Node closeness								
					All spp.	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	Tracking data	Neighbours	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	
60	Greek part of the Adriatic Sea	Mediterranean	174	1	13	13	0	0	0	0	0	0.002732	0.003968	0.000101						
61	Greek part of the Aegean Sea	Mediterranean	1,022	2	32	31	1	0	0	0	0	0.003125	0.003788	0.000102	0.000116					
62	Greek part of the Ionian Sea	Mediterranean	5,478	2	71	70	0	0	0	1	0	0.003559	0.005128	0.000103					0.020408	
63	Greek part of the Mediterranean Sea - Eastern Basin	Mediterranean	394	3	44	41	2	0	0	1	0	0.003636	0.005376	0.000103	0.000115					0.020408
64	Grenadian part of the Caribbean Sea	Atlantic	99	2	10	0	0	10	0	0	0	0.000234	0.000477							0.000268
65	Guadeloupean part of the Caribbean Sea	Atlantic	4	2	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0.000262	0.000562							0.000260
66	Guadeloupean part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	39	2	7	0	0	7	0	0	0	0.000318	0.000657							0.000273
67	Guatemalan part of the Caribbean Sea	Atlantic	9	2	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0.000172	0.000357							0.000105
68	Guatemalan part of the North Pacific Ocean	Pacific	19	2	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0.000807	0.001610							0.000108
69	Guinea Bissau part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	13	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0.000259	0.000634	0.000094						
70	Guinean part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	222	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0.000220	0.000633	0.000093						
71	Guyanese part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	15	2	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	0.000319	0.000656							0.000260
72	Haitian part of the Caribbean Sea	Atlantic	30	2	7	0	0	0	7	0	0	0.000242	0.000493							0.000759
73	High seas of the Arabian Sea	Indian	189	2	4	1	3	0	0	0	0	0.000311	0.000617	0.000082	0.000119					
74	High seas of the Bay of Bengal	Indian	30	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.000168	0.000571							0.000106
75	High seas of the Indian Ocean	Indian	692	3	21	0	8	13	0	0	0	0.000357	0.000741							0.000118 0.000200
76	High seas of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	5,394	4	64	39	1	23	0	0	1	0.000393	0.000853	0.000095	0.000106	0.000283				0.001364
77	High seas of the North Pacific Ocean	Pacific	11,757	4	145	134	1	1	0	0	9	0.001362	0.002137	0.000103	0.000109	0.000154				0.001458

MarID	Marine region	Basin	Points (n)	Species (n)	Animals (n)						Node closeness							
					All spp.	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	Tracking data	Neighbours	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>
78	High seas of the Philippine Sea	Pacific	2	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0.001030	0.001802	0.000103				
79	High seas of the South Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	3,843	5	72	1	15	41	1	0	14	0.000392	0.000829	0.000083	0.000112	0.000202	0.000554	0.001773
80	High seas of the South Pacific Ocean	Pacific	638	3	21	9	6	6	0	0	0	0.000712	0.001650	0.000079	0.000105	0.000160		
81	Honduran part of the Caribbean Sea	Atlantic	310	3	15	3	5	0	7	0	0	0.000225	0.000419	0.000080	0.000116		0.000703	
82	Ile Europa part of the Mozambique Channel	Indian	9	2	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0.000250	0.000466			0.000156		
83	Indian (Andaman and Nicobar Islands) part of the Bay of Bengal	Indian	4	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.000150	0.000568		0.000105			
84	Indian part of the Arabian Sea	Indian	21	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.000221	0.000507		0.000118			
85	Indian part of the Laccadive Sea	Indian	1	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.000251	0.000492		0.000117			
86	Indonesian part of the Celebes Sea	Pacific	187	2	3	0	3	0	0	0	0	0.000683	0.001558		0.000106			
87	Indonesian part of the Makassar Strait	Pacific	73	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.000577	0.001244		0.000105			
88	Indonesian part of the South China Sea	Pacific	118	2	3	1	2	0	0	0	0	0.000723	0.001225	0.000079	0.000118			
89	Iranian part of the Arabian Sea	Indian	5	3	3	1	0	0	1	0	1	0.000230	0.000435	0.000082		0.000554		0.001582
90	Iranian part of the Gulf of Oman	Indian	30	3	5	0	2	0	0	0	3	0.000209	0.000440		0.000130			0.001647
91	Iranian part of the Persian Gulf	Indian	1,137	4	36	0	3	0	31	0	2	0.000209	0.000379		0.000128		0.000649	0.001642
92	Irish part of the Celtic Sea	Atlantic	2	2	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0.000256	0.000501			0.000266		
93	Irish part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	14	2	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	0.000310	0.000633			0.000282		
94	Israeli part of the Mediterranean Sea - Eastern Basin	Mediterranean	603	2	28	14	14	0	0	0	0	0.002410	0.003236	0.000101	0.000111			
95	Italian part of the Adriatic Sea	Mediterranean	881	1	32	32	0	0	0	0	0	0.002890	0.004167	0.000102				

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					All spp.	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	Tracking data	Neighbours	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>
96	Italian part of the Ionian Sea	Mediterranean	933	2	29	28	0	0	0	1	0	0.003546	0.005291	0.000103				0.020833
97	Italian part of the Ligurian Sea	Mediterranean	9	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0.002070	0.003436	0.000078				
98	Italian part of the Mediterranean Sea - Eastern Basin	Mediterranean	982	2	45	44	0	0	0	1	0	0.003546	0.005464	0.000103				0.021277
99	Italian part of the Mediterranean Sea - Western Basin	Mediterranean	80	1	8	8	0	0	0	0	0	0.002320	0.004329	0.000101				
100	Italian part of the Tyrrhenian Sea	Mediterranean	1,826	2	27	26	0	0	0	1	0	0.002924	0.004505	0.000102				0.017857
101	Jamaican part of the Caribbean Sea	Atlantic	101	2	7	0	0	0	7	0	0	0.000226	0.000432				0.000737	
102	Japanese part of the Eastern China Sea	Pacific	257	1	30	30	0	0	0	0	0	0.001236	0.002070	0.000105				
103	Japanese part of the Japan Sea	Pacific	478	1	28	28	0	0	0	0	0	0.001174	0.002151	0.000103				
104	Japanese part of the North Pacific Ocean	Pacific	901	1	96	96	0	0	0	0	0	0.001372	0.002381	0.000104				
105	Japanese part of the Philippine Sea	Pacific	665	1	55	55	0	0	0	0	0	0.001431	0.002315	0.000104				
106	Japanese part of the Sea of Okhotsk	Pacific	120	1	17	17	0	0	0	0	0	0.001088	0.001916	0.000102				
107	Japanese part of the Seto Naikai or Inland Sea	Pacific	10	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0.001030	0.001832	0.000103				
108	Johnston Atoll part of the North Pacific Ocean	Pacific	13	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.000995	0.001587					0.001437
109	Joint regime area Argentina / Uruguay part of the Rio de La Plata	Atlantic	9	3	5	3	1	1	0	0	0	0.000227	0.000502	0.000083	0.000112	0.000194		
110	Joint regime area Argentina / Uruguay part of the South Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	387	3	15	6	8	1	0	0	0	0.000269	0.000502	0.000083	0.000112	0.000198		
111	Joint regime area Croatia / Slovenia part of the Adriatic Sea	Mediterranean	12	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0.002075	0.003115	0.000101				

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112	Joint regime area Honduras / Cayman Islands part of the Caribbean Sea	Atlantic	1	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.000195	0.000357	0.000116					
113	Joint regime area Japan / Korea part of the Eastern China Sea	Pacific	220	1	13	13	0	0	0	0	0	0.001208	0.001938	0.000104					
114	Joint regime area Japan / Korea part of the Japan Sea	Pacific	3	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0.000923	0.001862	0.000102					
115	Joint regime area Senegal / Guinea Bissau part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	45	1	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	0.000314	0.000633	0.000094					
116	Kenyan part of the Indian Ocean	Indian	9	2	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0.000213	0.000568	0.000105					
117	Kuwaiti part of the Persian Gulf	Indian	53	2	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0.000163	0.000328				0.000554		
118	Lebanese part of the Mediterranean Sea - Eastern Basin	Mediterranean	241	2	25	11	14	0	0	0	0	0.002331	0.003115	0.000101	0.000111				
119	Libyan part of the Mediterranean Sea - Eastern Basin	Mediterranean	3,760	2	83	61	22	0	0	0	0	0.003344	0.004444	0.000102	0.000110				
120	Madagascan part of the Mozambique Channel	Indian	45	3	2	0	1	1	0	0	0	0.000214	0.000574	0.000105	0.000154				
121	Malaysian part of the Celebes Sea	Pacific	570	2	11	0	11	0	0	0	0	0.000801	0.001318	0.000108					
122	Malaysian part of the South China Sea	Pacific	974	2	13	2	11	0	0	0	0	0.000839	0.001443	0.000079	0.000118				
123	Malaysian part of the Sulu Sea	Pacific	633	2	25	0	25	0	0	0	0	0.000998	0.001437	0.000119					
124	Maldives part of the Arabian Sea	Indian	56	2	6	0	6	0	0	0	0	0.000260	0.000595	0.000119					
125	Maldives part of the Indian Ocean	Indian	2	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.000250	0.000594	0.000119					
126	Maldives part of the Laccadive Sea	Indian	157	2	6	0	6	0	0	0	0	0.000304	0.000587	0.000120					

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127	Maltese part of the Mediterranean Sea - Eastern Basin	Mediterranean	453	2	42	41	0	0	0	1	0	0.003236	0.003922	0.000102				0.017857	
128	Marshall Islands part of the North Pacific Ocean	Pacific	23	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.000995	0.001587						0.001437
129	Martinican part of the Caribbean Sea	Atlantic	26	2	10	0	0	10	0	0	0	0.000269	0.000564				0.000272		
130	Martinican part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	22	2	8	0	0	8	0	0	0	0.000269	0.000664				0.000274		
131	Mauritanian part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	755	2	15	14	0	1	0	0	0	0.000313	0.000634	0.000094			0.000268		
132	Mauritian part of the Indian Ocean	Indian	8	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.000287	0.000568		0.000117				
133	Mexican part of the Caribbean Sea	Atlantic	46	2	5	0	5	0	0	0	0	0.000222	0.000469			0.000108			
134	Mexican part of the Gulf of California	Pacific	349	4	13	5	6	1	1	0	0	0.000807	0.001277	0.000102	0.000109	0.000158	0.000566		
135	Mexican part of the Gulf of Mexico	Atlantic	33	3	3	0	2	0	1	0	0	0.000253	0.000465		0.000108		0.000566		
136	Mexican part of the North Pacific Ocean	Pacific	1,044	4	17	4	6	1	6	0	0	0.001033	0.001610	0.000102	0.000108	0.000156	0.000554		
137	Montenegrin Exclusive economic Zone part of the Adriatic Sea	Mediterranean	26	1	8	8	0	0	0	0	0	0.002137	0.003115	0.000101					
138	Moroccan part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	477	2	11	10	0	1	0	0	0	0.000312	0.000636	0.000094		0.000257			
139	Mozambican part of the Indian Ocean	Indian	31	3	11	0	1	10	0	0	0	0.000291	0.000574		0.000107	0.000198			
140	Mozambican part of the Mozambique Channel	Indian	843	3	20	0	3	17	0	0	0	0.000301	0.000575		0.000109	0.000199			
141	Namibian part of the South Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	142	2	7	0	0	7	0	0	0	0.000310	0.000620			0.000200			
142	Nicaraguan part of the Caribbean Sea	Atlantic	2,375	2	9	3	0	0	6	0	0	0.000202	0.000426	0.000080			0.000705		

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143	Nicaraguan part of the North Pacific Ocean	Pacific	4	2	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0.000845	0.001610	0.000105					
144	North Korean part of the Japan Sea	Pacific	3	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0.000760	0.001395	0.000101					
145	Omani part of the Arabian Sea	Indian	4,900	4	48	10	3	0	26	0	9	0.000268	0.000517	0.000082	0.000126		0.000679	0.001650	
146	Omani part of the Gulf of Oman	Indian	383	4	23	1	1	0	19	0	2	0.000240	0.000438	0.000082	0.000126		0.000707	0.001634	
147	Omani part of the Persian Gulf	Indian	137	3	4	0	0	0	2	0	2	0.000208	0.000378				0.000654	0.001629	
148	Overlapping claim Chagos Archipelago: UK / Mauritius part of the Indian Ocean	Indian	802	2	8	0	8	0	0	0	0	0.000288	0.000568	0.000121					
149	Overlapping claim Kuril Islands: Japan / Russia part of the North Pacific Ocean	Pacific	157	1	29	29	0	0	0	0	0	0.001133	0.001984	0.000103					
150	Overlapping claim Kuril Islands: Japan / Russia part of the Sea of Okhotsk	Pacific	70	1	14	14	0	0	0	0	0	0.001037	0.001792	0.000102					
151	Overlapping claim Navassa Island: USA / Haiti / Jamaica part of the Caribbean Sea	Atlantic	1	2	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0.000210	0.000416				0.000713		
152	Overlapping claim: Qatar / Saudi Arabia / United Arab Emirates part of the Persian Gulf	Indian	18	2	6	0	0	0	6	0	0	0.000171	0.000291				0.000645		
153	Overlapping claim Senkaku Islands: Japan / China / Taiwan part of the Eastern China Sea	Pacific	173	1	29	29	0	0	0	0	0	0.001176	0.001634	0.000104					
154	Overlapping claim: South China Sea part of the South China Sea	Pacific	12	2	4	1	3	0	0	0	0	0.000745	0.001488	0.000080	0.000118				

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155	Overlapping claim: Western Saharan part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	868	2	20	18	0	2	0	0	0	0.000313	0.000634	0.000094		0.000269			
156	Overlapping claim: Iran / United Arab Emirates part of the Persian Gulf	Indian	23	4	7	0	2	0	3	0	2	0.000183	0.000329		0.000126		0.000640		0.001580
157	Overlapping claim: Trinidad and Tobago / Venezuela / Guyana part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	1	2	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0.000265	0.000539			0.000267			
158	Pakistani part of the Arabian Sea	Indian	90	2	2	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.000230	0.000514	0.000082					0.001522
159	Palestinian part of the Mediterranean Sea - Eastern Basin	Mediterranean	14	2	10	3	7	0	0	0	0	0.002342	0.002525	0.000101	0.000111				
160	Panamanian part of the Caribbean Sea	Atlantic	3	2	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0.000186	0.000420				0.000692		
161	Panamanian part of the North Pacific Ocean	Pacific	486	4	5	0	1	0	3	0	1	0.000831	0.001292		0.000105		0.000554		0.001364
162	Peruvian part of the South Pacific Ocean	Pacific	346	2	22	14	0	8	0	0	0	0.000621	0.001307	0.000079		0.000162			
163	Philippines part of the Celebes Sea	Pacific	11	2	4	0	4	0	0	0	0	0.000826	0.001595		0.000108				
164	Philippines part of the Philippine Sea	Pacific	80	2	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	0.001214	0.002008	0.000102	0.000105				
165	Philippines part of the South China Sea	Pacific	178	2	6	0	6	0	0	0	0	0.000826	0.001764		0.000118				
166	Philippines part of the Sulu Sea	Pacific	707	2	28	0	28	0	0	0	0	0.001029	0.001626		0.000118				
167	Portuguese (Azores) part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	148	2	5	1	0	4	0	0	0	0.000310	0.000630	0.000094		0.000270			
168	Portuguese (Madeira) part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	613	2	21	17	0	4	0	0	0	0.000325	0.000633	0.000094		0.000270			

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169	Portuguese part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	178	1	4	4	0	0	0	0	0	0.000311	0.000633	0.000094					
170	Puerto Rican part of the Caribbean Sea	Atlantic	11	2	2	0	0	0	2	0	0	0.000237	0.000564						0.000576
171	Qatari part of the Persian Gulf	Indian	5,312	3	79	1	23	0	55	0	0	0.000189	0.000329	0.000078	0.000107				0.000652
172	Russian Exclusive economic Zone part of the Japan Sea	Pacific	178	1	19	19	0	0	0	0	0	0.000957	0.001684	0.000102					
173	Russian Exclusive economic Zone part of the North Pacific Ocean	Pacific	24	1	7	7	0	0	0	0	0	0.001028	0.001764	0.000102					
174	Russian Exclusive economic Zone part of the Sea of Okhotsk	Pacific	73	1	10	10	0	0	0	0	0	0.000909	0.001832	0.000101					
175	Saint Lucia part of the Caribbean Sea	Atlantic	31	2	10	0	0	10	0	0	0	0.000270	0.000479						0.000273
176	Saint Vincent and the Grenadines part of the Caribbean Sea	Atlantic	76	2	11	0	0	11	0	0	0	0.000239	0.000479						0.000271
177	Saint-Pierre and Miquelon part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	2	2	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	0.000269	0.000515						0.000263
178	Sao Tome and Principe part of the Gulf of Guinea	Atlantic	14	2	7	0	0	7	0	0	0	0.000236	0.000644						0.000221
179	Sao Tome and Principe part of the South Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	35	2	14	0	0	14	0	0	0	0.000281	0.000564						0.000204
180	Saudi Arabian part of the Persian Gulf	Indian	1,683	3	16	0	2	0	14	0	0	0.000184	0.000330		0.000107				0.000650
181	Saudi Arabian part of the Red Sea	Indian	4	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.000226	0.000316		0.000105				
182	Senegalese part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	360	1	14	14	0	0	0	0	0	0.000313	0.000636	0.000094					

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183	Seychellois part of the Indian Ocean	Indian	732	2	5	0	5	0	0	0	0	0.000287	0.000569		0.000117				
184	Sierra Leonian part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	239	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0.000191	0.000631	0.000092					
185	Slovenian part of the Adriatic Sea	Mediterranean	43	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0.002075	0.003115	0.000101					
186	Somali part of the Gulf of Aden	Indian	23	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0.000195	0.000423	0.000082					
187	Somali part of the Indian Ocean	Indian	240	2	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0.000287	0.000590		0.000105				
188	South African part of the Indian Ocean	Indian	789	2	30	0	0	30	0	0	0	0.000342	0.000678			0.000201			
189	South African part of the South Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	152	2	8	0	0	8	0	0	0	0.000327	0.000676			0.000201			
190	South Korean part of the Eastern China Sea	Pacific	37	1	5	5	0	0	0	0	0	0.000975	0.001667	0.000104					
191	South Korean part of the Japan Sea	Pacific	21	1	4	4	0	0	0	0	0	0.001008	0.001745	0.000103					
192	South Korean part of the Yellow Sea	Pacific	6	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0.000778	0.001650	0.000102					
193	Spanish (Canary Islands) part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	2,919	3	44	38	3	3	0	0	0	0.000312	0.000634	0.000095	0.000105	0.000270			
194	Spanish part of the Balearic (Iberian Sea)	Mediterranean	29	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0.001942	0.002525	0.000098					
195	Spanish part of the Mediterranean Sea - Western Basin	Mediterranean	365	1	6	6	0	0	0	0	0	0.002703	0.003236	0.000100					
196	Spanish part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	62	2	4	2	0	2	0	0	0	0.000310	0.000633	0.000093		0.000267			
197	Sri Lankan part of the Bay of Bengal	Indian	6	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.000190	0.000573		0.000107				
198	Sri Lankan part of the Indian Ocean	Indian	22	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.000217	0.000571		0.000108				
199	Sri Lankan part of the Laccadive Sea	Indian	4	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.000254	0.000573		0.000109				
200	St. Helena part of the South Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	79	2	7	0	0	7	0	0	0	0.000308	0.000617			0.000200			

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201	Surinamese part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	29	2	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0.000310	0.000636			0.000267			
202	Syrian part of the Mediterranean Sea - Eastern Basin	Mediterranean	675	2	16	9	7	0	0	0	0	0.002114	0.003145	0.000101	0.000115				
203	Taiwanese part of the Eastern China Sea	Pacific	83	1	22	22	0	0	0	0	0	0.001049	0.002033	0.000104					
204	Taiwanese part of the Philippine Sea	Pacific	43	1	20	20	0	0	0	0	0	0.001189	0.002058	0.000104					
205	Taiwanese part of the South China Sea	Pacific	53	1	12	12	0	0	0	0	0	0.001013	0.001821	0.000103					
206	Tanzanian part of the Indian Ocean	Indian	30	2	3	0	3	0	0	0	0	0.000250	0.000571		0.000106				
207	Trinidad and Tobago part of the Caribbean Sea	Atlantic	35	2	3	0	0	3	0	0	0	0.000233	0.000562			0.000268			
208	Trinidad and Tobago part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	60	2	4	0	0	4	0	0	0	0.000270	0.000563			0.000272			
209	Tunisian part of the Mediterranean Sea - Eastern Basin	Mediterranean	6,629	2	66	64	2	0	0	0	0	0.003425	0.004274	0.000102	0.000105				
210	Tunisian part of the Mediterranean Sea - Western Basin	Mediterranean	64	1	7	7	0	0	0	0	0	0.002618	0.004115	0.000101					
211	Turkish part of the Aegean Sea	Mediterranean	173	1	10	10	0	0	0	0	0	0.002457	0.003788	0.000101					
212	Turkish part of the Mediterranean Sea - Eastern Basin	Mediterranean	787	2	34	21	13	0	0	0	0	0.002755	0.004016	0.000102	0.000115				
213	Turks and Caicos part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	36	3	2	0	0	1	1	0	0	0.000319	0.000652			0.000156	0.000678		
214	United Arab Emirates part of the Gulf of Oman	Indian	15	4	4	0	1	0	2	0	1	0.000207	0.000373		0.000129		0.000702		0.001558
215	United Arab Emirates part of the Persian Gulf	Indian	7,751	3	52	0	7	0	45	0	0	0.000194	0.000330		0.000126		0.000653		

MarID	Marine region	Basin	Points (n)	Species (n)	Animals (n)							Node closeness							
					All spp.	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	Tracking data	Neighbours	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>
216	United States (Hawaii) part of the North Pacific Ocean	Pacific	294	2	23	14	0	0	0	0	9	0.001052	0.001587	0.000102					0.001447
217	United States part of the Gulf of Mexico	Atlantic	1,378	4	36	1	7	0	1	27	0	0.000292	0.000546	0.000094	0.000108		0.000554	0.017857	
218	United States part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	16,228	4	157	104	16	9	0	28	0	0.000353	0.000676	0.000095	0.000108	0.000277		0.017857	
219	Uruguayan part of the Rio de La Plata	Atlantic	228	3	12	4	7	1	0	0	0	0.000263	0.000502	0.000083	0.000112	0.000195			
220	Uruguayan part of the South Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	252	3	13	2	8	3	0	0	0	0.000320	0.000629	0.000083	0.000112	0.000199			
221	Venezuelan part of the Caribbean Sea	Atlantic	36	3	6	0	0	5	1	0	0	0.000236	0.000506			0.000260	0.000554		
222	Venezuelan part of the North Atlantic Ocean	Atlantic	17	2	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	0.000268	0.000560			0.000263			
223	Vietnamese part of the South China Sea	Pacific	164	2	10	3	7	0	0	0	0	0.000886	0.001437	0.000080	0.000119				
224	Virgin Islander part of the Caribbean Sea	Atlantic	8	3	2	0	0	1	1	0	0	0.000237	0.000558			0.000246	0.000566		
225	Yemeni part of the Arabian Sea	Indian	475	2	7	6	1	0	0	0	0	0.000265	0.000510	0.000082	0.000108				
226	Yemeni part of the Gulf of Aden	Indian	76	2	3	2	1	0	0	0	0	0.000225	0.000425	0.000082	0.000107				
227	Yemeni part of the Red Sea	Indian	1	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.000196	0.000363		0.000106				

Appendix S4. Link details for each network. Routes were connections between nodes that varied in length, but were represented in the network as a single link or line. These links or lines were not the specific tracks of sea turtles and does not assume that sea turtles travelled these distances between marine regions.

Table S4.9. Summary of tracking data and centrality metrics for each link between marine region nodes (link = start MarID -> end MarID). *Cc* = *Caretta caretta*, *Cm* = *Chelonia mydas*, *Dc* = *Dermochelys coriacea*; *Ei* = *Eretmochelys imbricata*, *Lk* = *Lepidochelys kempii*, *Lo* = *Lepidochelys olivacea*. Blanks = not calculated because no locations were recorded within the marine region and the link was not present in the network. For marine region names within links, refer to MarID in Table S3.8.

Link	Basin	Animals (n)	Species (n)	Routes (n)							Link betweenness								
				All spp.	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	Tracking data	Neighbours	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	
1->137	Mediterranean	5	1	7	7	0	0	0	0	0	6.00	8.42	14.00						
1->38	Mediterranean	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	1.50		1.00						
1->60	Mediterranean	3	1	4	4	0	0	0	0	0	2.00	2.48	2.00						
1->62	Mediterranean	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	23.50	28.45	20.58						
1->95	Mediterranean	7	1	9	9	0	0	0	0	0	3.50	4.48	6.42						
10->218	Atlantic	1	1	8	8	0	0	0	0	0	344.50	6.39	22.00						
10->41	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	2,077.00	298.19					99.00		
100->195	Mediterranean	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	4.00		3.50						
100->55	Mediterranean	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	29.00	17.41	29.00						
100->96	Mediterranean	2	1	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	62.00	46.72	54.67						
100->97	Mediterranean	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	30.00	17.41	30.00						
100->98	Mediterranean	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	50.00	19.52	34.67						
100->99	Mediterranean	4	1	6	6	0	0	0	0	0	14.00	12.29	15.83						
101->142	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	0	0	2	0	0	10.50	15.34					27.00		
101->151	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	122.00	12.43					14.00		
101->32	Atlantic	2	1	5	0	0	0	5	0	0	57.00	120.03					6.00		
101->72	Atlantic	3	1	3	0	0	0	3	0	0	470.50	53.62					69.17		
101->81	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	0	0	2	0	0	37.00	53.44					4.00		
102->105	Pacific	16	1	20	20	0	0	0	0	0	92.50	54.12	64.33						
102->113	Pacific	12	1	17	17	0	0	0	0	0	225.23	16.06	132.17						
102->153	Pacific	7	1	8	8	0	0	0	0	0	1.83	27.55	1.83						
102->203	Pacific	5	1	5	5	0	0	0	0	0	3.00	16.71	19.00						
102->29	Pacific	5	1	16	16	0	0	0	0	0	126.80	36.28	123.38						
103->104	Pacific	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	59.17	186.75	42.48						
103->106	Pacific	6	1	6	6	0	0	0	0	0	39.00	20.72	25.33						
103->172	Pacific	19	1	22	22	0	0	0	0	0	96.50	31.75	60.33						
103->191	Pacific	2	1	4	4	0	0	0	0	0	61.17	74.52	28.62						
104->105	Pacific	10	1	14	14	0	0	0	0	0	633.83	489.53	287.38						
104->149	Pacific	21	1	24	24	0	0	0	0	0	48.50	31.19	36.00						
104->77	Pacific	73	1	85	85	0	0	0	0	0	179.00	594.88	75.33						
105->102	Pacific	6	1	8	8	0	0	0	0	0	277.20	54.12	250.38						
105->104	Pacific	36	1	39	39	0	0	0	0	0	175.50	489.53	99.33						
105->107	Pacific	2	1	4	4	0	0	0	0	0	46.00	37.82	29.00						
105->153	Pacific	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	134.63		16.00						
105->164	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	37.00	263.77	29.00						
105->204	Pacific	4	1	4	4	0	0	0	0	0	222.03	82.82	36.33						
105->77	Pacific	6	1	6	6	0	0	0	0	0	110.00		0.00						
105->78	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	46.00	38.97	29.00						
106->104	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	91.67	34.58	69.90						
106->149	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	4.00	21.38	3.50						
106->174	Pacific	8	1	9	9	0	0	0	0	0	8.50	2.74	6.33						
107->105	Pacific	1	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	45.00	37.82	32.00						
108->77	Pacific	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	45.00	55.00							3.00

Link	Basin	Animals (n)	Species (n)	Routes (n)							Link betweenness							
				All spp.	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	Tracking data	Neighbours	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>
109->110	Atlantic	3	3	4	1	2	1	0	0	0	133.50	1.00	6.00	4.50	21.00			
109->7	Atlantic	4	2	5	4	1	0	0	0	0	1.50	1.00	2.00	1.50				
11->171	Indian	18	2	150	0	132	0	18	0	0	133.50	1.83		1.00		4.00		
11->180	Indian	8	2	35	0	2	0	33	0	0	3.00	2.33		1.00		3.00		
110->109	Atlantic	2	2	3	0	2	1	0	0	0	121.00	1.00		7.00	26.00			
110->219	Atlantic	6	3	9	4	3	2	0	0	0	2.50	1.00	5.50	2.50	25.00			
110->220	Atlantic	7	3	8	2	5	1	0	0	0	75.00	80.58	16.00	7.00	8.00			
110->7	Atlantic	14	3	35	22	10	3	0	0	0	119.00	1.00	10.00	5.00	26.00			
110->8	Atlantic	6	3	13	8	4	1	0	0	0	192.00	55.42	8.00	7.00	64.00			
111->185	Mediterranean	1	1	4	4	0	0	0	0	0	1.00	1.00	1.00					
111->38	Mediterranean	1	1	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	7.75	1.50	7.00					
111->95	Mediterranean	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	21.25	27.50	22.00					
112->81	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	135.00	139.00		11.00				
113->103	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	162.50	55.15	95.67					
113->105	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	56.03		38.33					
113->114	Pacific	1	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	46.00	2.62	29.00					
113->190	Pacific	4	1	8	8	0	0	0	0	0	14.57	14.40	31.67					
113->191	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	42.00	16.36	25.00					
113->29	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	46.67	39.96	20.65					
114->190	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	23.92	16.69	20.00					
114->191	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	21.08	8.00	12.00					
115->182	Atlantic	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	10.00	2.50	12.00					
115->59	Atlantic	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	4.00		4.00					
115->69	Atlantic	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	360.00	1.50	54.00					
115->76	Atlantic	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	514.00	135.00	60.00					
118->202	Mediterranean	3	1	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	1.00	3.17	1.50					
118->42	Mediterranean	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	8.67	24.50	18.50					
118->50	Mediterranean	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	18.33			3.00				
118->94	Mediterranean	16	2	19	6	13	0	0	0	0	4.00	4.33	12.00	7.00				
119->127	Mediterranean	9	1	14	14	0	0	0	0	0	9.25	8.02	7.00					
119->209	Mediterranean	46	2	105	103	2	0	0	0	0	108.00	16.13	96.92	10.00				
119->50	Mediterranean	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	35.50	25.13		4.00				
119->63	Mediterranean	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	23.25	15.97	64.67					
119->98	Mediterranean	3	1	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	0.00	17.96	0.00					
12->13	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	123.50	113.00			29.83			
12->175	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	459.00	55.94			125.17			
12->176	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	106.50	73.08			35.00			
121->163	Pacific	2	1	3	0	3	0	0	0	0	1.00	13.87		1.00				
121->86	Pacific	2	1	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	46.80	18.65		9.13				
122->123	Pacific	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	122.13	11.71		21.00				
122->154	Pacific	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	12.00	8.44		22.00				
122->165	Pacific	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	16.33	44.40		3.00				
122->22	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	25.00	18.02	34.00					
122->88	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	5.50	16.55	33.00					
123->121	Pacific	5	1	5	0	5	0	0	0	0	91.80	8.75		15.13				
123->122	Pacific	3	1	3	0	3	0	0	0	0	15.00	11.71		15.00				
123->163	Pacific	3	1	3	0	3	0	0	0	0	89.47	12.57		13.80				
123->165	Pacific	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	14.33	35.07		0.00				
123->166	Pacific	24	1	128	0	128	0	0	0	0	215.00	7.85		11.50				

Link	Basin	Animals (n)	Species (n)	Routes (n)							Link betweenness								
				All spp.	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	Tracking data	Neighbours	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	
124->126	Indian	4	1	6	0	6	0	0	0	0	1,063.00	3.43		127.00					
124->73	Indian	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	298.00	25.13		4.00					
124->84	Indian	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	120.50	41.42		15.00					
125->124	Indian	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	145.00	2.67		23.00					
126->124	Indian	4	1	5	0	5	0	0	0	0	1.50	3.43		2.00					
126->199	Indian	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	615.00	6.17		85.00					
126->73	Indian	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	22.00			1.00					
126->75	Indian	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	315.00	175.71		20.00					
126->85	Indian	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	122.50	29.03		16.00					
127->119	Mediterranean	18	1	23	23	0	0	0	0	0	4.00	8.02	2.67						
127->209	Mediterranean	13	1	13	13	0	0	0	0	0	5.00	4.17	1.67						
127->62	Mediterranean	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	13.75		10.17						
127->98	Mediterranean	23	2	44	42	0	0	0	2	0	8.50	17.82	17.00				4.00		
128->77	Pacific	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	45.00	55.00							3.00
129->130	Atlantic	5	1	5	0	0	5	0	0	0	10.67	90.27		36.50					
129->176	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	19.00			17.50					
129->44	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	243.00	4.53		79.00					
129->45	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	8.00	12.95		8.00					
129->66	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	194.67			37.17					
13->12	Atlantic	2	2	3	1	0	2	0	0	0	653.00	113.00	22.00	181.00					
13->130	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	65.70	8.57		29.00					
13->208	Atlantic	3	1	4	0	0	4	0	0	0	248.50	64.72		185.50					
13->222	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	142.00			34.50					
13->71	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	17.67	7.34		18.00					
13->76	Atlantic	6	1	6	0	0	6	0	0	0	1,353.83	650.01		285.33					
130->13	Atlantic	6	1	7	0	0	7	0	0	0	169.67	8.57		103.00					
130->45	Atlantic	2	1	3	0	0	3	0	0	0	9.00	56.57		9.00					
131->155	Atlantic	3	1	13	13	0	0	0	0	0	8.00	3.00	13.00						
131->182	Atlantic	9	1	19	19	0	0	0	0	0	11.00	2.83	18.00						
131->26	Atlantic	4	1	16	16	0	0	0	0	0	2.33	1.83	8.17						
131->76	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	125.00	133.33		41.00					
132->183	Indian	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	135.00	1.50		13.00					
133->135	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	274.50	6.41		6.00					
133->15	Atlantic	3	1	3	0	3	0	0	0	0	113.00	132.12		6.00					
134->136	Pacific	6	4	6	2	2	1	1	0	0	49.00	55.00	34.00	4.00	2.00	1.00			
135->133	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	3.00	6.41		3.00					
135->217	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	405.50	61.17				16.00			
136->51	Pacific	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	6.00			6.00					
136->68	Pacific	2	1	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	2.00	3.00		2.00					
136->77	Pacific	2	2	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	135.00	105.00	66.00		2.00				
137->1	Mediterranean	1	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	2.00	8.42	2.00						
137->38	Mediterranean	8	1	9	9	0	0	0	0	0	28.00	2.50	28.00						
138->155	Atlantic	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	5.33	2.83	3.33						
138->168	Atlantic	3	1	4	4	0	0	0	0	0	64.33	2.33	0.50						
138->169	Atlantic	3	1	5	5	0	0	0	0	0	3.50	2.50	9.00						
138->193	Atlantic	11	2	22	21	0	1	0	0	0	65.33	2.00	20.17		41.00				
139->140	Indian	7	1	9	0	0	9	0	0	0	5.00	5.67		11.40					
139->188	Indian	4	1	4	0	0	4	0	0	0	47.67	74.17		7.40					
139->206	Indian	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	119.00	5.17		2.00					

Link	Basin	Animals (n)	Species (n)	Routes (n)							Link betweenness							
				All spp.	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	Tracking data	Neighbours	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>
139->75	Indian	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	80.33	120.33				2.19		
14->140	Indian	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	135.00	69.83				21.00		
140->139	Indian	4	1	4	0	0	4	0	0	0	2.00	5.67				2.00		
140->14	Indian	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	122.00	69.83				26.00		
140->188	Indian	10	1	11	0	0	11	0	0	0	256.00					41.40		
140->206	Indian	2	1	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	127.00			2.00				
140->34	Indian	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	184.50	38.00		2.00				
140->82	Indian	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	184.50	69.83				54.00		
141->189	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	9.50	24.50				6.50		
141->3	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	6.00	2.50				1.00		
141->79	Atlantic	4	1	6	0	0	6	0	0	0	119.50	113.00				13.50		
142->101	Atlantic	1	1	2	0	0	0	2	0	0	7.00	15.34					15.00	
142->27	Atlantic	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	13.00		2.00					
142->32	Atlantic	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	6.00	223.01	3.00					
142->36	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	243.00	77.45				27.00		
142->81	Atlantic	4	2	21	2	0	0	19	0	0	149.50	68.14	2.00			5.00		
144->172	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	45.00	26.47	32.00					
145->146	Indian	5	3	5	1	0	0	2	0	2	1,094.33	543.81	7.00			12.00		6.00
145->158	Indian	2	2	3	2	0	0	0	0	1	112.00	5.96	7.00					2.00
145->181	Indian	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	123.00			7.00				
145->225	Indian	7	2	24	23	1	0	0	0	0	600.00	87.00	15.00	28.00				
145->73	Indian	2	2	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	1,610.00	1,117.35	4.00	98.00				
145->89	Indian	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	339.17	64.42	7.00					
146->145	Indian	18	3	19	1	1	0	17	0	0	1,343.50	543.81	7.00	120.00		2.00		
146->147	Indian	2	2	5	0	0	0	1	0	4	649.00	98.70				18.00		9.00
146->214	Indian	3	2	3	0	0	0	2	0	1	122.00	47.87				2.00		8.00
146->89	Indian	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	10.50	6.93				3.00		
146->90	Indian	2	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	3	232.33	1.93						7.00
147->146	Indian	1	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	3	125.50	98.70						2.00
147->215	Indian	2	1	2	0	0	0	2	0	0	182.00	101.25				32.00		
147->91	Indian	2	1	20	0	0	0	0	0	20	370.83	4.00						11.00
148->125	Indian	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	10.00	13.83		10.00				
148->75	Indian	6	1	6	0	6	0	0	0	0	127.00	125.17		5.00				
149->104	Pacific	9	1	9	9	0	0	0	0	0	49.50	31.19	26.00					
149->150	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	44.00	7.00	26.00					
149->173	Pacific	3	1	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	2.00	7.01	2.50					
149->77	Pacific	21	1	23	23	0	0	0	0	0	8.00	55.20	2.00					
15->133	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	134.00	132.12		2.00				
15->67	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	123.00	22.31		7.00				
150->104	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	41.00	37.19	28.00					
150->106	Pacific	6	1	9	9	0	0	0	0	0	12.50	5.78	8.00					
150->149	Pacific	5	1	6	6	0	0	0	0	0	1.50	7.00	2.50					
150->174	Pacific	1	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	2.00	6.86	1.50					
151->72	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	135.00	68.44					19.00	
152->171	Indian	2	1	2	0	0	0	2	0	0	2.00	34.58					1.00	
152->180	Indian	3	1	8	0	0	0	8	0	0	2.00	35.58					3.00	
152->215	Indian	3	1	3	0	0	0	3	0	0	131.00	68.83					3.00	
153->102	Pacific	23	1	29	29	0	0	0	0	0	16.50	27.55	11.33					
153->113	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	11.17		11.17					

Link	Basin	Animals (n)	Species (n)	Routes (n)							Link betweenness								
				All spp.	<i>Cc</i>	<i> Cm</i>	<i> Dc</i>	<i> Ei</i>	<i> Lk</i>	<i> Lo</i>	Tracking data	Neighbours	<i>Cc</i>	<i> Cm</i>	<i> Dc</i>	<i> Ei</i>	<i> Lk</i>	<i> Lo</i>	
153->203	Pacific	3	1	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	2.00	17.07	2.00						
153->29	Pacific	8	1	18	18	0	0	0	0	0	127.63	10.39	17.33						
154->122	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	3.63	8.44	3.00						
154->165	Pacific	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	50.07	31.12		6.37					
154->22	Pacific	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	21.00	36.98		7.50					
154->223	Pacific	2	1	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	9.63	4.08		15.63					
155->131	Atlantic	4	2	16	15	0	1	0	0	0	10.33	3.00	13.17		40.00				
155->138	Atlantic	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	2.50	2.83	2.50						
155->193	Atlantic	15	1	33	33	0	0	0	0	0	3.00	1.83	9.50						
155->76	Atlantic	3	2	3	2	0	1	0	0	0	127.50	133.33	13.00		40.00				
156->215	Indian	3	1	4	0	0	0	4	0	0	6.00	3.00				7.00			
156->91	Indian	4	2	6	0	2	0	0	0	4	129.00	69.50		24.00					7.00
157->13	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	195.50	60.43			54.50				
158->145	Indian	1	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	124.50	5.96	7.00						
158->89	Indian	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	11.00	63.51							14.00
159->50	Mediterranean	9	2	10	2	8	0	0	0	0	28.00		30.00	3.00					
159->94	Mediterranean	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	2.00	30.00		7.00					
16->76	Atlantic	14	2	18	12	0	6	0	0	0	135.00	139.00	22.00		41.00				
160->32	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	269.00	189.45				37.00			
161->37	Pacific	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	5.00	29.50							2.00
162->28	Pacific	5	1	7	7	0	0	0	0	0	5.00	1.00	2.00						
162->80	Pacific	15	2	20	14	0	6	0	0	0	100.00	54.00	2.00		4.00				
163->121	Pacific	3	1	6	0	6	0	0	0	0	1.00	13.87		1.00					
163->86	Pacific	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	51.20	5.78		10.87					
164->204	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	309.00	22.53	32.00						
165->166	Pacific	2	1	6	0	6	0	0	0	0	80.73	11.68		16.87					
166->123	Pacific	24	1	124	0	124	0	0	0	0	14.00	7.85		19.80					
166->163	Pacific	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	6.73	5.39		3.07					
166->164	Pacific	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	273.00	74.32		8.00					
166->165	Pacific	4	1	8	0	8	0	0	0	0	1.00	11.68		2.50					
167->76	Atlantic	4	2	5	1	0	4	0	0	0	135.00	139.00	22.00		41.00				
168->138	Atlantic	4	1	7	7	0	0	0	0	0	1.00	2.33	3.00						
168->193	Atlantic	16	2	33	30	0	3	0	0	0	3.00	1.33	4.00		153.00				
168->76	Atlantic	8	2	13	12	0	1	0	0	0	194.33	135.33	15.00		37.00				
169->138	Atlantic	2	1	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	3.50	2.50	6.00						
169->196	Atlantic	2	1	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	2.00	1.00	20.00						
169->76	Atlantic	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	131.00	135.50	36.00						
17->79	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	135.00	139.00			21.00				
170->224	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	194.00	6.55					32.00		
171->11	Indian	22	2	159	0	132	0	27	0	0	122.00	1.83		1.00			8.00		
171->152	Indian	4	1	4	0	0	0	4	0	0	61.50	34.58					8.00		
171->180	Indian	3	2	14	0	1	0	13	0	0	1.00	1.50		1.00			2.00		
171->215	Indian	25	1	53	0	0	0	53	0	0	4.00	2.33					7.50		
171->91	Indian	13	1	19	0	0	0	19	0	0	258.00	166.58					0.00		
172->103	Pacific	7	1	10	10	0	0	0	0	0	60.33	31.75	36.10						
172->106	Pacific	9	1	9	9	0	0	0	0	0	23.67	22.89	21.90						
172->144	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	46.00	26.47	29.00						
172->174	Pacific	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	10.50	23.35	8.33						
173->149	Pacific	3	1	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	18.00	7.01	1.50						

Link	Basin	Animals (n)	Species (n)	Routes (n)							Link betweenness								
				All spp.	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	Tracking data	Neighbours	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	
173->174	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	36.50	32.90	19.33						
173->77	Pacific	4	1	5	5	0	0	0	0	0	32.50	45.28	30.00						
174->106	Pacific	8	1	10	10	0	0	0	0	0	42.50	2.74	30.50						
174->150	Pacific	2	1	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	1.50	6.86	2.00						
174->173	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	12.50	32.90	6.00						
175->129	Atlantic	10	1	10	0	0	10	0	0	0	388.00	53.41				145.67			
175->13	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	244.00					77.00			
176->12	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	7.50	73.08				4.00			
176->175	Atlantic	10	1	10	0	0	10	0	0	0	160.00	2.33				96.50			
176->64	Atlantic	4	1	5	0	0	5	0	0	0	20.50	2.20				22.00			
177->25	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	135.00	138.00				41.00			
178->179	Atlantic	6	1	6	0	0	6	0	0	0	129.50	38.23				23.00			
178->52	Atlantic	1	1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	5.50	230.48				5.00			
179->53	Atlantic	14	1	14	0	0	14	0	0	0	264.50	68.30				46.00			
18->19	Atlantic	2	2	4	1	0	0	3	0	0	4,690.00	2.83	8.00			2.00			
18->76	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	3,672.00	74.50							10.00
180->11	Indian	5	2	31	0	2	0	29	0	0	1.50	2.33		1.00		2.00			
180->117	Indian	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	123.00	3.50				11.00			
180->152	Indian	4	1	10	0	0	0	10	0	0	60.50	35.58				2.00			
180->171	Indian	5	2	14	0	1	0	13	0	0	0.50	1.50		1.00		2.50			
180->215	Indian	4	1	10	0	0	0	10	0	0	131.00	2.83				1.50			
182->115	Atlantic	3	1	4	4	0	0	0	0	0	16.00	2.50	16.00						
182->131	Atlantic	9	1	23	23	0	0	0	0	0	10.00	2.83	12.00						
182->26	Atlantic	6	1	8	8	0	0	0	0	0	1.00	2.00	3.00						
182->59	Atlantic	5	1	9	9	0	0	0	0	0	4.00	2.33	5.00						
182->76	Atlantic	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	254.00	133.00	31.00						
183->75	Indian	2	1	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	269.00	135.75		25.00					
184->70	Atlantic	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	135.00	1.50	22.00						
185->111	Mediterranean	1	1	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	1.00	1.00	1.00						
185->38	Mediterranean	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	7.75	1.50	1.00						
185->95	Mediterranean	1	1	6	6	0	0	0	0	0	21.25	27.50	28.00						
186->226	Indian	2	1	4	4	0	0	0	0	0	135.00	4.00	7.00						
188->139	Indian	6	1	6	0	0	6	0	0	0	2.50	74.17				2.50			
188->140	Indian	11	1	14	0	0	14	0	0	0	21.00					96.00			
188->189	Indian-Atlantic	4	1	5	0	0	5	0	0	0	5.83	2.63				25.21			
188->75	Indian	12	1	19	0	0	19	0	0	0	122.50	41.33				21.38			
188->79	Indian-Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	316.83	161.88				16.71			
189->141	Atlantic	1	1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	2.83	24.50				5.00			
189->188	Atlantic-Indian	2	1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	125.00	2.63				112.50			
189->79	Atlantic	6	1	13	0	0	13	0	0	0	107.50	91.50				29.71			
19->18	Atlantic	3	3	5	1	0	0	3	0	1	276.00	2.83	8.00			1.00			2.00
19->220	Atlantic	7	3	10	3	3	4	0	0	0	702.00	138.44	18.00	18.00	126.00				
19->79	Atlantic	5	4	6	1	0	3	1	0	1	4,260.00	58.00	2.00		30.00	2.00			9.00
190->113	Pacific	3	1	5	5	0	0	0	0	0	52.45	14.40	43.67						
190->192	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	30.70	1.83	26.82						
190->29	Pacific	2	1	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	76.40	30.18	39.82						
191->103	Pacific	2	1	4	4	0	0	0	0	0	34.00	74.52	22.00						
191->113	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	49.75	16.36	26.48						
191->190	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	39.50	26.27	20.13						

Link	Basin	Animals (n)	Species (n)	Routes (n)							Link betweenness								
				All spp.	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	Tracking data	Neighbours	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	
192->190	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	35.27	1.83	25.83						
192->31	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	12.57	6.33	8.65						
193->138	Atlantic	10	2	22	21	0	1	0	0	0	2.00	2.00	5.50				40.00		
193->155	Atlantic	20	2	44	42	0	2	0	0	0	117.00	1.83	19.83				79.00		
193->168	Atlantic	17	1	37	37	0	0	0	0	0	2.00	1.33	3.50						
193->76	Atlantic	5	2	6	5	0	1	0	0	0	192.33	134.50	26.83				76.00		
194->195	Mediterranean	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	30.00	30.00	30.00						
195->194	Mediterranean	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	29.00	30.00	29.00						
195->2	Mediterranean	4	1	16	16	0	0	0	0	0	38.00	3.00	53.50						
195->99	Mediterranean	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	49.50	55.00	28.00						
196->169	Atlantic	1	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	1.50	1.00	22.00						
196->76	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	133.50	135.50					41.00		
197->74	Indian	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	252.00	3.28		40.00					
198->197	Indian	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	375.00	1.67		57.00					
199->198	Indian	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	496.00	2.67		72.00					
2->195	Mediterranean	4	1	16	16	0	0	0	0	0	4.00	3.00	4.00						
2->210	Mediterranean	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	34.50	14.00	51.50						
2->99	Mediterranean	3	1	4	4	0	0	0	0	0	5.50	15.00	4.50						
20->4	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	421.03	60.30					83.00		
200->79	Atlantic	6	1	6	0	0	6	0	0	0	135.00	139.00					21.00		
201->76	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	135.00	126.94					41.00		
202->118	Mediterranean	9	2	9	3	6	0	0	0	0	3.50	3.17	2.50	5.50					
202->212	Mediterranean	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	17.00	14.80	25.00						
202->42	Mediterranean	5	2	5	4	1	0	0	0	0	10.00	14.37	2.50	6.00					
203->102	Pacific	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	19.67	16.71	15.50						
203->153	Pacific	13	1	14	14	0	0	0	0	0	4.17	17.07	5.00						
203->204	Pacific	2	1	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	3.98	8.38	5.67						
203->205	Pacific	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	1.00	29.11	1.00						
203->29	Pacific	11	1	13	13	0	0	0	0	0	46.67	17.41	4.00						
203->30	Pacific	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	101.50	72.74	6.00						
204->102	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	80.00	54.77	17.67						
204->105	Pacific	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	177.00	82.82	32.00						
204->153	Pacific	6	1	6	6	0	0	0	0	0	10.00		8.33						
204->203	Pacific	10	1	11	11	0	0	0	0	0	163.50	8.38	2.00						
204->205	Pacific	4	1	5	5	0	0	0	0	0	123.50	24.60	30.00						
205->203	Pacific	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	2.00	29.11	2.00						
205->204	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	19.98	24.60	13.00						
205->29	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	13.50	71.85	12.50						
205->30	Pacific	12	1	13	13	0	0	0	0	0	101.50	8.89	18.00						
206->116	Indian	2	1	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	124.00	2.25		3.00					
207->176	Atlantic	1	1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	9.50	35.95					16.67		
207->208	Atlantic	2	1	5	0	0	5	0	0	0	165.07	3.70					52.00		
207->221	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	3.50	40.84					3.00		
207->64	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1.00	100.85					1.00		
208->12	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	15.50	9.40					4.00		
208->13	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	618.47	64.72					110.50		
208->207	Atlantic	3	1	6	0	0	6	0	0	0	106.00	3.70					42.67		
208->221	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	153.50	66.44					93.00		
208->222	Atlantic	1	1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	10.00	1.97					11.50		

Link	Basin	Animals (n)	Species (n)	Routes (n)							Link betweenness								
				All spp.	Cc	Cm	Dc	Ei	Lk	Lo	Tracking data	Neighbours	Cc	Cm	Dc	Ei	Lk	Lo	
208->64	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	107.00						39.17		
209->119	Mediterranean	27	1	79	79	0	0	0	0	0	49.75	16.13	67.67						
209->127	Mediterranean	6	1	7	7	0	0	0	0	0	1.50	4.17	0.00						
209->195	Mediterranean	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	74.50		69.00						
209->210	Mediterranean	4	1	4	4	0	0	0	0	0	28.50	4.58	32.67						
209->98	Mediterranean	17	1	44	44	0	0	0	0	0	53.00	13.32	58.00						
21->4	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	135.00	7.47					41.00		
210->100	Mediterranean	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	13.50	6.46	9.50						
210->2	Mediterranean	4	1	4	4	0	0	0	0	0	3.00	14.00	3.00						
210->209	Mediterranean	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	49.00	4.58	71.67						
210->99	Mediterranean	4	1	5	5	0	0	0	0	0	6.50	3.00	10.67						
211->61	Mediterranean	5	1	6	6	0	0	0	0	0	3.33	1.00	9.00						
211->63	Mediterranean	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	26.67	25.17	21.00						
212->202	Mediterranean	6	2	6	1	5	0	0	0	0	1.50	14.80	11.50	5.50					
212->211	Mediterranean	4	1	4	4	0	0	0	0	0	6.00	3.83	5.00						
212->42	Mediterranean	7	2	7	4	3	0	0	0	0	4.50	7.00	4.00	13.50					
212->61	Mediterranean	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	2.83	3.83	3.00						
212->63	Mediterranean	9	2	12	11	1	0	0	0	0	36.00	33.13	45.00	2.00					
213->10	Atlantic	2	2	2	0	0	1	1	0	0	159.00	14.47					42.00	91.00	
214->146	Indian	2	2	2	0	0	0	1	0	1	124.00	47.87						3.00	7.00
214->147	Indian	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	6.83							9.00	
214->90	Indian	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	4.17	91.13		25.00					
215->156	Indian	5	2	6	0	2	0	4	0	0	6.50	3.00		4.00				10.00	
215->171	Indian	20	1	50	0	0	0	50	0	0	223.33	2.33						19.50	
215->180	Indian	6	1	16	0	0	0	16	0	0	223.33	2.83						14.00	
215->91	Indian	19	2	39	0	1	0	38	0	0	387.00	100.42		25.00				10.00	
216->77	Pacific	19	2	24	13	0	0	0	0	11	45.00	55.00	32.00						3.00
217->218	Atlantic	3	2	4	2	2	0	0	0	0	528.00	172.80	22.00	3.00					
218->10	Atlantic	2	1	9	9	0	0	0	0	0	2,126.00	6.39	20.00						
218->217	Atlantic	3	2	4	2	2	0	0	0	0	109.50	172.80	20.00	6.00					
218->25	Atlantic	2	1	3	0	0	3	0	0	0	42.00	54.53					3.00		
218->76	Atlantic	31	3	45	35	1	9	0	0	0	1,532.00	1,164.99	60.00	14.00	38.00				
219->110	Atlantic	6	3	11	3	4	4	0	0	0	3.00	1.00	2.00	3.00	21.00				
219->220	Atlantic	7	2	7	2	5	0	0	0	0	131.00	80.58	4.00	3.00					
219->7	Atlantic	5	2	7	6	1	0	0	0	0	1.00	1.00	2.00	1.00					
22->122	Pacific	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	45.00	18.02		12.50					
220->110	Atlantic	5	3	6	3	2	1	0	0	0	354.00	80.58	20.00	16.00	88.00				
220->19	Atlantic	12	3	14	3	8	3	0	0	0	212.50	138.44	12.00	6.00	20.00				
220->219	Atlantic	1	1	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	118.00	80.58		4.00					
220->79	Atlantic	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	120.00	314.36	6.00						
220->8	Atlantic	1	1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	118.00	1.50					22.00		
221->207	Atlantic	2	1	4	0	0	4	0	0	0	55.57	40.84					26.00		
221->224	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	258.17	73.27					81.00		
221->64	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	83.07	35.95					13.17		
222->208	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	127.33	1.97					33.83		
222->221	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	156.17	55.12					6.67		
222->71	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	6.00	120.34					9.00		
223->122	Pacific	2	2	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	73.33	11.39	93.00	1.50					
223->123	Pacific	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	290.47			9.63					

Link	Basin	Animals (n)	Species (n)	Routes (n)							Link betweenness								
				All spp.	Cc	Cm	Dc	Ei	Lk	Lo	Tracking data	Neighbours	Cc	Cm	Dc	Ei	Lk	Lo	
223->154	Pacific	4	2	4	1	3	0	0	0	0	73.33	4.08	31.00	2.50					
223->88	Pacific	2	1	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	40.50	8.40		7.00					
224->20	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	408.03	27.58			82.00				
224->221	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	57.13	73.27				17.00			
225->145	Indian	6	1	16	16	0	0	0	0	0	48.00	87.00	12.00						
225->226	Indian	3	2	8	7	1	0	0	0	0	484.00	540.00	12.00	24.00					
225->73	Indian	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	345.00	717.00	3.00						
226->186	Indian	2	1	4	4	0	0	0	0	0	122.00	4.00	7.00						
226->225	Indian	2	1	6	6	0	0	0	0	0	264.00	540.00	12.00						
226->227	Indian	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	246.00	411.00		18.00					
227->54	Indian	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	124.00	138.00		10.00					
24->25	Atlantic	3	1	3	0	0	3	0	0	0	135.00	138.00			41.00				
25->177	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	122.00	138.00			40.00				
25->218	Atlantic	3	1	3	0	0	3	0	0	0	66.00	54.53			3.00				
25->24	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	122.00	138.00			40.00				
25->76	Atlantic	11	2	15	7	0	8	0	0	0	333.00	356.48	22.00		114.00				
26->131	Atlantic	8	1	17	17	0	0	0	0	0	113.00	1.83	12.00						
26->182	Atlantic	12	1	20	20	0	0	0	0	0	117.00	2.00	14.00						
26->59	Atlantic	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	114.00	1.33	11.00						
26->76	Atlantic	6	2	8	4	0	4	0	0	0	127.00	134.50	18.00		41.00				
27->112	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	122.00			1.00					
27->39	Atlantic	4	2	4	0	3	0	1	0	0	119.00	108.04		6.00			8.33		
27->81	Atlantic	10	3	11	4	4	0	3	0	0	15.00	5.83	3.00	5.00			15.67		
28->162	Pacific	5	1	7	7	0	0	0	0	0	51.00	1.00	2.00						
29->102	Pacific	4	1	16	16	0	0	0	0	0	49.50	36.28	36.67						
29->113	Pacific	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	37.67	39.96	30.00						
29->153	Pacific	8	1	17	17	0	0	0	0	0	7.67	10.39	7.67						
29->190	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	47.30	30.18	9.67						
29->203	Pacific	2	1	5	5	0	0	0	0	0	7.48	17.41	9.17						
29->205	Pacific	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	10.98	71.85	9.00						
29->30	Pacific	3	1	4	4	0	0	0	0	0	299.00	44.32	150.00						
29->31	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	59.30	34.25	29.18						
3->141	Atlantic	1	1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	3.00	2.50			1.00				
3->35	Atlantic	5	1	5	0	0	0	0	0	5	2.00	3.97							1.50
3->43	Atlantic	22	1	32	0	0	0	0	0	32	2.00	1.50							3.50
3->58	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	12.00								10.00
3->79	Atlantic	9	2	11	0	0	1	0	0	10	126.00	133.03			20.00				4.50
30->205	Pacific	6	1	7	7	0	0	0	0	0	2.50	8.89	2.50						
30->223	Pacific	3	1	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	469.00	52.17	150.00						
30->29	Pacific	2	1	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	29.50	44.32	24.50						
31->192	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	18.13	6.33	4.67						
31->29	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	52.73	34.25	36.17						
32->101	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	0	0	2	0	0	6.00	120.03				6.00			
32->142	Atlantic	4	2	5	1	0	0	4	0	0	50.00	223.01	3.00			9.00			
32->72	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	367.00	50.16				47.83			
33->161	Pacific	2	2	2	0	1	0	0	0	1	51.00	25.50		5.00					2.00
34->120	Indian	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	62.50	38.33		2.00					
35->3	Atlantic	24	1	28	0	0	0	0	0	28	5.50	3.97							7.50
35->43	Atlantic	7	2	7	0	0	2	0	0	5	4.00	3.47			5.00				2.50

Link	Basin	Animals (n)	Species (n)	Routes (n)							Link betweenness								
				All spp.	Cc	Cm	Dc	Ei	Lk	Lo	Tracking data	Neighbours	Cc	Cm	Dc	Ei	Lk	Lo	
35->58	Atlantic	22	2	37	0	0	8	0	0	29	10.00	11.43				13.50			5.00
35->79	Atlantic	5	2	5	0	0	1	0	0	4	125.00	130.00				10.50			3.00
36->160	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	256.00	61.55						32.00	
37->143	Pacific	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	47.00	3.83			4.00				
37->33	Pacific	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	97.00	2.00			8.00				
38->111	Mediterranean	1	1	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	8.00	1.50			7.83				
38->137	Mediterranean	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	6.00	2.50			1.50				
38->185	Mediterranean	1	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	8.00	1.50			2.00				
38->62	Mediterranean	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	60.00				30.50				
38->95	Mediterranean	16	1	26	26	0	0	0	0	0	4.50	26.50			27.00				
39->101	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	619.00	64.71						65.33	
39->133	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	218.00	16.23			4.00				
39->135	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	121.00	22.15						30.00	
39->27	Atlantic	5	1	5	0	0	0	5	0	0	224.00	108.04						19.00	
39->40	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	680.50	184.31			20.00				
39->41	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	0	0	2	0	0	20.00	354.75						4.00	
39->81	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	613.00	235.21			1.00				
4->6	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	122.73	10.92					44.67		
4->76	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	665.47	176.53					140.00		
40->218	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	693.50	645.92			20.00				
41->10	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	123.50	298.19						3.00	
41->39	Atlantic	3	1	3	0	0	0	3	0	0	1,986.50	354.75						105.00	
42->118	Mediterranean	12	2	12	5	7	0	0	0	0	25.50	24.50			26.00		4.50		
42->202	Mediterranean	10	2	10	8	2	0	0	0	0	27.00	14.37			16.00		1.00		
42->212	Mediterranean	9	2	10	6	4	0	0	0	0	9.83	7.00			8.00		2.00		
42->50	Mediterranean	34	2	34	13	21	0	0	0	0	25.00	5.73			8.83		15.00		
42->63	Mediterranean	2	2	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	17.83	70.10			34.17		2.00		
42->94	Mediterranean	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	9.42	22.97			14.50				
43->3	Atlantic	24	1	35	0	0	0	0	0	35	5.00	1.50							8.00
43->35	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	4.00	3.47							0.50
43->79	Atlantic	4	2	4	0	0	2	0	0	2	126.00	134.03					22.00		1.50
44->129	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	74.33	4.53					31.50		
44->65	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	181.67	3.61					48.50		
45->130	Atlantic	3	1	3	0	0	3	0	0	0	16.00	56.57					17.00		
45->66	Atlantic	4	1	4	0	0	4	0	0	0	122.00	55.70					27.00		
46->170	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	0	0	2	0	0	181.00	17.01						45.00	
46->47	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	771.50	574.52						81.00	
46->72	Atlantic	6	1	8	0	0	0	8	0	0	16.00	125.19						8.00	
47->213	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	33.00	13.93						86.00	
47->76	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	863.50	752.81					41.00		
48->37	Pacific	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	24.00	7.17			8.00				
48->49	Pacific	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	5.00	1.83			2.00				
48->77	Pacific	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	252.00	47.00			2.00				
49->48	Pacific	6	2	6	0	5	1	0	0	0	235.00	1.83			6.00		4.00		
49->80	Pacific	7	2	7	0	5	2	0	0	0	8.00	4.00			2.00		2.00		
5->66	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	135.00	58.01					41.00		
50->119	Mediterranean	33	2	33	11	22	0	0	0	0	66.00	25.13			48.33		18.00		
50->159	Mediterranean	2	2	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	26.00				26.50		11.00		
50->42	Mediterranean	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	14.00	5.73			6.00				

Link	Basin	Animals (n)	Species (n)	Routes (n)							Link betweenness								
				All spp.	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	Tracking data	Neighbours	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	
50->63	Mediterranean	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	39.33	32.97	34.50						
50->94	Mediterranean	3	1	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	16.58	33.37	13.50						
51->143	Pacific	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	4.00	2.33		4.00					
52->178	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1.00	230.48			0.00				
52->23	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	123.00	139.00							9.00
52->57	Atlantic	18	4	39	0	10	26	1	0	2	136.50	45.52		1.00	32.00	1.00			9.00
53->58	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	13.00	26.47							10.00
53->79	Atlantic	17	1	18	0	0	18	0	0	0	383.50	91.67			63.00				
55->100	Mediterranean	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	26.00	17.41	26.00						
55->99	Mediterranean	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	4.00	11.59	4.00						
56->80	Pacific	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	51.00	55.00							3.00
57->178	Atlantic	7	1	7	0	0	7	0	0	0	121.00	72.00							2.00
57->179	Atlantic	4	1	4	0	0	4	0	0	0	3.00	2.90							4.00
57->52	Atlantic	19	4	40	0	10	25	1	0	4	242.00	45.52		1.00	1.00	1.00			16.00
57->58	Atlantic	25	2	26	0	0	7	0	0	19	263.50	105.62			51.00				16.00
58->179	Atlantic	4	1	4	0	0	4	0	0	0	119.00	32.83							2.00
58->35	Atlantic	45	2	73	0	0	12	0	0	61	125.50	11.43							8.00
58->53	Atlantic	5	2	5	0	0	4	0	0	1	3.00	26.47							8.00
58->57	Atlantic	1	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	480.00	105.62							21.00
58->79	Atlantic	16	2	16	0	0	12	0	0	4	378.00	281.44			73.50				12.00
59->182	Atlantic	5	1	10	10	0	0	0	0	0	134.00	2.33	21.00						
59->26	Atlantic	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1.00	1.33	1.00						
6->5	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	122.00	56.37							40.00
6->66	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	9.40	4.65							15.00
6->76	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	131.00	226.75							37.00
60->1	Mediterranean	9	1	9	9	0	0	0	0	0	4.50	2.48	2.00						
60->62	Mediterranean	4	1	4	4	0	0	0	0	0	24.00	9.67	24.00						
60->95	Mediterranean	3	1	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	3.50	4.50	4.00						
61->119	Mediterranean	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	10.00		10.00						
61->211	Mediterranean	7	1	8	8	0	0	0	0	0	23.00	1.00	24.00						
61->212	Mediterranean	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1.50	3.83		10.00					
61->42	Mediterranean	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	7.83		9.00						
61->62	Mediterranean	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	8.50		13.00						
61->63	Mediterranean	9	1	10	10	0	0	0	0	0	3.50	25.17	5.00						
62->1	Mediterranean	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	23.00	28.45	29.00						
62->127	Mediterranean	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	6.33		4.00						
62->38	Mediterranean	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	36.00		22.83						
62->60	Mediterranean	10	1	11	11	0	0	0	0	0	14.25	9.67	12.00						
62->61	Mediterranean	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	25.00		22.67						
62->63	Mediterranean	19	2	27	22	0	0	0	5	0	95.00	54.25	77.58					4.00	
62->95	Mediterranean	3	1	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	28.00	45.08	28.83						
62->96	Mediterranean	12	1	15	15	0	0	0	0	0	4.00	3.15	14.75						
62->98	Mediterranean	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	37.50	41.80	11.25						
63->119	Mediterranean	15	1	16	16	0	0	0	0	0	40.50	15.97	38.92						
63->212	Mediterranean	6	2	8	7	1	0	0	0	0	21.50	33.13	34.50	4.00					
63->42	Mediterranean	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	64.58	70.10	63.00						
63->50	Mediterranean	5	2	5	4	1	0	0	0	0	30.08	32.97	56.50	5.00					
63->61	Mediterranean	8	1	9	9	0	0	0	0	0	22.17	25.17	25.33						
63->62	Mediterranean	8	2	14	9	0	0	0	5	0	73.25	54.25	68.00					1.00	

Link	Basin	Animals (n)	Species (n)	Routes (n)							Link betweenness								
				All spp.	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	Tracking data	Neighbours	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	
63->96	Mediterranean	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	9.50	50.77	7.50						
63->98	Mediterranean	6	1	6	6	0	0	0	0	0	24.00	72.88	33.83						
64->176	Atlantic	10	1	12	0	0	12	0	0	0	40.00	2.20						52.33	
64->207	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	4.50	100.85							3.00
64->208	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	166.57								4.50
64->221	Atlantic	3	1	3	0	0	3	0	0	0	13.50	35.95							16.50
65->66	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	194.67	66.51							49.50
66->130	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	73.30	8.70							28.50
66->45	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	108.00	55.70							26.00
66->6	Atlantic	3	1	3	0	0	3	0	0	0	126.67	4.65							46.33
66->76	Atlantic	4	1	4	0	0	4	0	0	0	723.33	334.65							135.00
68->136	Pacific	2	1	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	48.00	3.00		3.00					
69->115	Atlantic	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	399.00	1.50	60.00						
69->70	Atlantic	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	242.00	2.50	38.00						
7->109	Atlantic	4	2	5	4	1	0	0	0	0	1.00	1.00	8.00	1.00					
7->110	Atlantic	10	3	28	22	5	1	0	0	0	3.00	1.00	6.00	2.00	20.00				
7->219	Atlantic	11	3	15	7	6	2	0	0	0	1.50	1.00	2.50	2.50	1.00				
7->8	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	130.00	55.42		1.00					
70->184	Atlantic	1	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	122.00	1.50	20.00						
70->69	Atlantic	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	268.00	2.50	42.00						
71->157	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	182.50	55.37							53.50
71->208	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	290.00	71.28							24.00
71->222	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	124.50	120.34							2.50
72->101	Atlantic	6	1	8	0	0	0	8	0	0	36.50	53.62							17.00
72->32	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	9.50	50.16							3.00
72->46	Atlantic	4	1	4	0	0	0	4	0	0	955.50	125.19							129.00
73->124	Indian	2	1	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	1,053.00	25.13		99.00					
73->145	Indian	1	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	2,226.00	1,117.35	7.00						
73->75	Indian	2	1	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	2,100.00	2,482.01		32.00					
74->83	Indian	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	127.00	2.20		21.00					
75->132	Indian	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	122.00	137.50		16.00					
75->139	Indian	2	1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	234.50	120.33							21.50
75->140	Indian	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	702.00	302.33							0.00
75->183	Indian	5	1	5	0	5	0	0	0	0	121.00	135.75		15.00					
75->187	Indian	2	1	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	123.00	114.67		17.00					
75->188	Indian	4	1	7	0	0	7	0	0	0	27.00	41.33							5.50
75->73	Indian	2	1	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	3,091.00	2,482.01		31.00					
75->79	Indian-Atlantic	3	1	4	0	0	4	0	0	0	2,529.33	4,093.13							33.07
76->115	Atlantic	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	460.00	135.00	52.00						
76->13	Atlantic	4	2	4	1	0	3	0	0	0	1,116.57	650.01	42.00						357.50
76->138	Atlantic	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	116.50	133.50	14.00						
76->16	Atlantic	15	3	21	13	1	7	0	0	0	122.00	139.00	20.00	8.00	40.00				
76->167	Atlantic	5	2	6	1	0	5	0	0	0	122.00	139.00	20.00		40.00				
76->168	Atlantic	8	2	11	7	0	4	0	0	0	119.00	135.33	16.00		189.00				
76->169	Atlantic	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	118.50	135.50	29.00						
76->18	Atlantic	2	2	2	0	0	1	0	0	1	4,692.00	74.50			41.00				1.00
76->193	Atlantic	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	229.00	134.50	20.00						
76->196	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	120.00	135.50			40.00				
76->201	Atlantic	1	1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	122.00	126.94			40.00				

Link	Basin	Animals (n)	Species (n)	Routes (n)							Link betweenness								
				All spp.	Cc	Cm	Dc	Ei	Lk	Lo	Tracking data	Neighbours	Cc	Cm	Dc	Ei	Lk	Lo	
76->21	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	122.00	275.98					40.00		
76->213	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	113.00	114.00					82.00		
76->218	Atlantic	12	2	19	17	0	2	0	0	0	2,164.50	1,164.99	54.00				37.00		
76->25	Atlantic	9	2	13	7	0	6	0	0	0	318.00	356.48	20.00				111.00		
76->26	Atlantic	10	2	14	8	0	6	0	0	0	453.67	134.50	40.83				40.00		
76->4	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	219.17	176.53					59.67		
76->47	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	112.00	752.81					40.00		
76->66	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	362.57	334.65					65.17		
76->71	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	560.33	334.38					52.00		
77->104	Pacific	15	1	17	17	0	0	0	0	0	445.50	594.88	130.00						
77->108	Pacific	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	46.00	55.00							3.00
77->128	Pacific	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	46.00	55.00							3.00
77->149	Pacific	5	1	5	5	0	0	0	0	0	32.50	55.20	10.00						
77->173	Pacific	4	1	5	5	0	0	0	0	0	73.50	45.28	39.33						
77->216	Pacific	16	2	21	17	0	0	0	0	4	46.00	55.00	29.00						3.00
77->37	Pacific	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	161.00	72.50		4.00					
78->105	Pacific	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	45.00	38.97	32.00						
79->141	Atlantic	6	1	7	0	0	7	0	0	0	116.17	113.00					20.00		
79->17	Atlantic	4	1	4	0	0	4	0	0	0	122.00	139.00					26.00		
79->18	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	3,381.00	61.67							16.00
79->189	Atlantic	6	1	13	0	0	13	0	0	0	207.00	91.50					120.50		
79->19	Atlantic	18	3	20	2	12	6	0	0	0	322.50	58.00	8.00	14.00			141.00		
79->200	Atlantic	7	1	7	0	0	7	0	0	0	122.00	139.00					26.00		
79->3	Atlantic	8	2	11	0	0	2	0	0	9	115.50	133.03					25.00		2.00
79->43	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	116.00	134.03							2.00
79->53	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	116.00	91.67					20.00		
79->58	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	794.00	281.44							12.00
79->75	Atlantic-Indian	3	1	3	0	0	3	0	0	0	3,923.00	4,093.13					41.50		
79->9	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	122.00	139.00					26.00		
8->110	Atlantic	10	3	18	6	11	1	0	0	0	3.00	55.42	5.50	5.00			4.00		
8->220	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1.50	1.50					1.00		
8->7	Atlantic	3	2	3	2	1	0	0	0	0	1.00	55.42	2.50	1.00					
8->79	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	447.50	351.20					76.00		
80->162	Pacific	3	1	6	6	0	0	0	0	0	8.00	54.00	2.00						
80->49	Pacific	3	1	3	0	0	3	0	0	0	192.00	4.00					6.00		
80->56	Pacific	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	5.00	55.00					3.00		
81->101	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	0	0	2	0	0	15.50	53.44							11.83
81->133	Atlantic	3	1	3	0	3	0	0	0	0	19.50	86.98		6.00					
81->142	Atlantic	6	2	23	5	0	0	18	0	0	345.00	68.14	4.00				6.00		
81->15	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	131.00	27.19		6.00					
81->27	Atlantic	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	6.00	5.83	1.00						
81->32	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	68.50								11.83
81->39	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	377.00	235.21		12.00					
82->120	Indian	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	62.50	68.17					28.00		
84->124	Indian	1	1	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	269.00	41.42		25.00					
85->84	Indian	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	135.50	27.72		13.00					
86->87	Pacific	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	50.00	55.00		11.00					
88->122	Pacific	2	2	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	45.00	16.55	2.00	12.00					
89->145	Indian	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	123.50	64.42	7.00						

Link	Basin	Animals (n)	Species (n)	Routes (n)							Link betweenness								
				All spp.	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	Tracking data	Neighbours	<i>Cc</i>	<i>Cm</i>	<i>Dc</i>	<i>Ei</i>	<i>Lk</i>	<i>Lo</i>	
89->90	Indian	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	250.17	6.00							13.00
9->79	Atlantic	17	2	17	0	15	2	0	0	0	135.00	139.00	8.00	21.00					
90->146	Indian	2	2	2	0	1	0	0	0	1	125.50	1.93	105.00						6.00
90->147	Indian	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	2.50	196.05							3.00
90->158	Indian	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	10.50	496.18							13.00
90->215	Indian	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	372.17		6.00						
90->91	Indian	2	1	6	0	0	0	0	0	6	4.50	588.15							6.00
91->146	Indian	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	875.00	296.10							4.00
91->147	Indian	2	1	19	0	0	0	0	0	19	7.00	4.00							2.00
91->156	Indian	2	1	4	0	0	0	0	0	4	115.50	69.50							8.00
91->171	Indian	15	1	20	0	0	0	20	0	0	74.17	166.58					1.50		
91->180	Indian	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	74.17	166.08					0.00		
91->215	Indian	22	2	44	0	1	0	43	0	0	1.00	100.42	3.00				5.50		
91->90	Indian	3	2	6	0	1	0	0	0	5	15.50	588.15	66.00						9.00
92->93	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	137.00	139.00			43.00				
93->76	Atlantic	2	1	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	272.00	276.00			84.00				
93->92	Atlantic	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1.00	139.00			1.00				
94->118	Mediterranean	6	2	7	5	2	0	0	0	0	2.00	4.33	2.50	4.00					
94->159	Mediterranean	8	2	9	2	7	0	0	0	0	3.00	30.00	2.50	3.00					
94->42	Mediterranean	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	4.00	22.97	3.50						
94->50	Mediterranean	13	2	13	6	7	0	0	0	0	24.00	33.37	32.50	3.00					
95->1	Mediterranean	11	1	14	14	0	0	0	0	0	6.00	4.48	10.00						
95->111	Mediterranean	1	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	20.00	27.50	20.17						
95->137	Mediterranean	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	17.00	20.08	13.50						
95->185	Mediterranean	2	1	5	5	0	0	0	0	0	20.00	27.50	26.00						
95->38	Mediterranean	12	1	23	23	0	0	0	0	0	4.50	26.50	8.00						
95->60	Mediterranean	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	3.50	4.50	4.00						
95->62	Mediterranean	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	24.83	45.08	27.50						
95->96	Mediterranean	6	1	6	6	0	0	0	0	0	36.17	69.48	65.42						
96->127	Mediterranean	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1.33		0.00						
96->60	Mediterranean	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	11.25	15.32	11.00						
96->62	Mediterranean	10	2	13	12	0	0	0	1	0	26.00	3.15	14.67					6.00	
96->95	Mediterranean	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	49.00	69.48	57.33						
96->98	Mediterranean	20	2	38	37	0	0	0	1	0	42.33	25.50	87.17					2.00	
98->110	Mediterranean	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	81.00	19.52	82.33						
98->119	Mediterranean	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	4.75	17.96	0.00						
98->127	Mediterranean	33	2	56	54	0	0	0	2	0	11.83	17.82	19.50					2.00	
98->209	Mediterranean	22	1	49	49	0	0	0	0	0	44.25	13.32	56.08						
98->62	Mediterranean	2	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	14.25	41.80	13.50						
98->63	Mediterranean	4	1	4	4	0	0	0	0	0	43.00	72.88	44.67						
98->96	Mediterranean	12	2	25	23	0	0	0	2	0	17.25	25.50	26.83					6.00	
99->100	Mediterranean	3	1	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	67.50	12.29	48.83						
99->195	Mediterranean	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	3.00	55.00	3.00						
99->2	Mediterranean	4	1	5	5	0	0	0	0	0	2.00	15.00	2.50						
99->210	Mediterranean	5	1	7	7	0	0	0	0	0	8.00	3.00	9.67						

Appendix S5. List of select network metrics explored in this study. Metrics that were selected and retained for comparisons were significant (PCA sum > 80%) and uncorrelated with other metrics (Spearman's rho <0.80).

Table S5.10. Select network metrics calculated for 14 networks on whole network, sub-network, node (vertex), and link (edge) levels. †significant and uncorrelated whole network metric, ‡significant and uncorrelated sub-network metric, §significant and uncorrelated for both whole and sub-networks.

Network metrics	Measurement	Reference
Whole graph (global)		
Alpha index	Connectivity based on the number of cycles over the number of all possible cycles	Garrison & Marble, 1962; Rodrigue, Comtois, & Slack, 2017
Assortativity (degree)	Connectivity based on nodes with similar degree centrality values	Newman, 2002, 2003
Assortativity (value)	Connectivity based on nodes with similar value (number of routes)	Newman, 2002, 2003
Beta index	Connectivity based on ratio of number links to number of nodes	Garrison & Marble, 1962; Rodrigue et al., 2017
† Degree centrality (all)	Level of dominance by one or more nodes (all directions)	Freeman, 1978; Wasserman & Faust, 1994
Degree centrality (in)	Level of dominance by one or more nodes (in direction)	Freeman, 1978; Wasserman & Faust, 1994
Degree centrality (out)	Level of dominance by one or more nodes (out direction)	Freeman, 1978; Wasserman & Faust, 1994
Degree centrality, theoretical maximum (all)	Maximum level of dominance in a theoretical graph of the same number of nodes (all directions)	Freeman, 1978; Wasserman & Faust, 1994
Degree centrality, theoretical maximum (in)	Maximum level of dominance in a theoretical graph of the same number of nodes (in direction)	Freeman, 1978; Wasserman & Faust, 1994
Degree centrality, theoretical maximum (out)	Maximum level of dominance in a theoretical graph of the same number of nodes (out direction)	Freeman, 1978; Wasserman & Faust, 1994
Density (directed)	Connectivity based on the number of links over the total possible links (with direction)	Wasserman & Faust, 1994
Density (undirected)	Number of links divided by the total possible links (without direction)	Wasserman & Faust, 1994
Diameter (directed)	Length of the longest path between two nodes, considering link weights and direction	Harary, 1969
† Links/edges (directed)	Number of unique links/edges (with direction)	
Links/edges (undirected)	Number of unique links/edges (without direction)	
Gamma index	Connectivity based on the number of links over the number of all possible links	Garrison & Marble, 1962; Rodrigue et al., 2017
Nodes/vertices	Number of nodes/vertices	
Transitivity (global)	Number of triangles over the number of connected node triples, without direction; global clustering coefficient	Barrat, Barthelemy, Pastor-Satorras, & Vespignani, 2004; Wasserman & Faust, 1994
Modularity	Level of separation determined by communities defined by weighted walktrap cluster (densely connected subgraphs identified by random walks)	Clauset, Newman, & Moore, 2004
Community	Community group defined by weighted walktrap cluster (densely connected subgraphs identified by random walks)	Pons & Latapy, 2006

Network metrics	Measurement	Reference
Node/vertex (local)		
Animals (n)	Number of animals	
Betweenness	Level of dominance based on shortest paths connecting a node	Brandes, 2001; Freeman, 1978; Raghavan Unnithan, Kannan, & Jathavedan, 2014
‡	Closeness (all)	Reciprocal of the average distance between one node to all other nodes (all directions)
	Closeness (in)	Reciprocal of the average distance between one node to all other nodes (in direction)
†	Closeness (out)	Reciprocal of the average distance between one node to all other nodes (out direction)
‡	Degree centrality (all)	Number of adjacent links (all directions)
	Degree centrality (in)	Number of adjacent links (in direction)
	Degree centrality (out)	Number of adjacent links (out direction)
	Eccentricity (all)	Maximum of the shortest distance from or to the node to or from all other graph nodes
	Eccentricity (in)	Maximum of the shortest distance to the node from all other graph nodes
†	Eccentricity (out)	Maximum of the shortest distance from the node to all other graph nodes
	Eigenvector Centrality	Score of first eigenvector of the graph adjacency matrix, calculated as proportional to the connected nodes' sum of centralities
‡	Page rank	Quality ranking based on the number and quality of connections from other nodes
†	Reach (all)	Proportion of all other nodes that can be reached (all directions)
	Reach (in)	Proportion of all other nodes that can be reached (undirected)
‡	Reach (out)	Proportion of all other nodes that can be reached (in direction)
†	Strength (all)	Sum of adjacent link weights; degree centrality, with weights (all directions)
	Strength (in)	Sum of adjacent link weights; degree centrality, with weights (in direction)
	Strength (out)	Sum of adjacent link weights; degree centrality, with weights (out direction)
†	Transitivity (local)	Number of triangles connected to the node over the number of connected node triples centered on the node, without direction;
	Modularity	Level of separation determined by communities defined by weighted walktrap cluster (densely connected subgraphs identified)
†	Weight	Number of animals, rescaled from 1-5 based on Fisher-Jenks breaks where 1 is low and 5 is high path resistance

Network metrics	Measurement	Reference
Link/edge (local)		
Animals	Number of unique animals that made the connection	
§ Betweenness	Level of dominance based on shortest path connecting a link	Brandes, 2001; Freeman, 1978; Raghavan Unnithan et al., 2014
Routes	Number of times connection was made	
§ Weight	Number of times connection was made, rescaled from 1-5 based on Fisher-Jenks breaks, where 1 is low and 5 is high path	

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Figure S5.11. Box plots of regional network metrics created with tracking data. Atl-Ind = Atlantic-Indian, Med = Mediterranean, Pac = Pacific; KW test: NS = $p > 0.05$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Figure S5.12. Box plots of metrics for regional networks created with tracking data (white boxes) and based on neighbouring marine regions (grey boxes). Atl-Ind = Atlantic-Indian, Med = Mediterranean, Pac = Pacific; KW test: NS = $p > 0.05$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$).

Figure S5.13 Box plots of metrics for species networks created with tracking data. Cc = *Caretta caretta*, Cm = *Chelonia mydas*, Dc = *Dermochelys coriacea*, Ei = *Eretmochelys imbricata*, Lk = *Lepidochelys kempii*, Lo = *Lepidochelys olivacea*; KW test: NS = $p > 0.05$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$.

